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**PERCEPTION OF NURSES AND PATIENTS IN CARING BEHAVIOR GIVEN BY
TAWAM HOSPITAL ER NURSES IN A MULTICULTURAL ENVIRONMENT
SETTING: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY**

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30 August 2023

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This Thesis titled: “PERCEPTION OF NURSES AND PATIENTS IN CARING BEHAVIOR GIVEN BY TAWAM HOSPITAL ER NURSES IN A MULTICULTURAL ENVIRONMENT SETTING: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Arts in Nursing.

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Biographical Sketch

Dennis del Rosario, who has 15 years of solid background in emergency care, is an ER Senior Team Leader/In-Charge of the Department. At present, Dennis is studying for the Master of Science in Healthcare Management from SBS Swiss Business School, in this field he possesses knowledge of trauma and emergency management, ensuring that the required excellence of multicultural effective care to the various patients is delivered. Having attained certifications in ATCN, TNCC, ACLS, PALS, NRP, ABLIS, BLS, CBRNE, RHSC, and AHLS, Dennis is an accomplished leader who is devoted to upholding the standards of excellence in emergency medicine, skillful at patching diverse patient needs, and insuring they receive the quality of care that is above par.

It was at Our Lady of Fatima University that Dennis first started his educational pathway, culminating in his BSc in Nursing in 2008. Throughout his undergrad program, he exhibited the best academic performance gaining the Most Outstanding in Clinical Areas award and attaining a GWA of 93% in general.

Dennis is currently working as an ER Senior Team Leader and In-Charge at Tawam Hospital- Al Ain, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates, since May 2017. Among other things, he supervises staff, allocates resources, and develops quality emergency nursing care.

During his professional life Dennis proved himself as a leader, an excellent clinician and a person who is always trying to achieve the best in everything he does. The results of his work have attracted the attention of the organization, and he has been awarded the Most Outstanding Employee and now he can proudly say that he was one of the people who have contributed to the advancement of nursing practice.

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DEDICATION

This paper is for my forever loyal family who have been with me from the beginning with their unconditional support, sacrifice, and encouragement throughout my life in this Masters. I owe to my parents, who above all, made the love for learning and the courage to pursue my dreams become a part of my character, my eternal gratitude. To my sister who always believed in my skills, I really appreciate the cheering and the constant support for me to do my best.

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Lastly, to all those who spend their lives in the belief that education is a powerful instrument, and knowledge is a source of transformation, this is your work. Let it be the proof of our partnership toward a joint achievement of wisdom, improvement, and superbness.

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Abstract

This comprehensive study conducted at Tawam Hospital's Emergency Department, aims to investigate the perceptions of caring behavior among nurses and patients within a culturally diverse context. Recognizing the crucial role of nursing behavior in patient satisfaction and outcomes, the study addresses the concerning trend of nurse turnover leading to compromised patient safety. Using a correlational research design and focusing on socio-demographic characteristics, the research explores the relationship between self-perceived caring behavior among ER nurses and corresponding perceptions by patients. The study involves 340 participants, including 120 nurses and 220 patients, utilizing the Caring Behaviors Inventory-24 (CBI-24) to assess various subscales. Results reveal high nursing expertise, particularly in the Knowledge-Skill Subscale, with variations in the Connectedness Subscale. The study has identified the top three highest and lowest items among the four subscales in both nurses and patients' perception in caring behavior. Patients perceive positive caring behaviors, emphasizing competence, confidentiality, and personalized treatment. Weak correlations between socio-demographics and perceptions highlight the need for tailored interventions. Recommendations include targeted training programs, fostering a culture of empathy, improving patient education, and implementing continuous quality improvement systems for sustained improvements in multicultural emergency care. Further research is advised to explore individual factors influencing perceptions within the Connectedness Subscale.

Keywords: Nurses Caring Behavior, Patients Caring Behavior, Perception in Caring Behavior, Caring Behavior Inventory- 24

Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Tawam Hospital Emergency Department continually strives to improve patient care quality, with a key focus on caring behavior. Understanding how a nurse's actions affect patient satisfaction and results, a study was started to evaluate the degree to which emergency room nurses demonstrate compassionate conduct. The study involves gathering feedback from both nurses and patients to identify areas of excellence and areas needing improvement. However, a concerning trend of nurse turnover has emerged, driven by the pursuit of better opportunities and work-life balance. This trend has resulted in increased errors, patient falls, and delays in treatment, posing a significant threat to patient safety. Additionally, patient satisfaction has declined, indicating potential future issues. The root causes include an upsurge in workload, complex schedules, staff shortages, and inadequate work-life balance, leading to decreased job satisfaction and burnout among ER nurses. The higher nurse-patient ratio exacerbates these challenges, further compromising the quality of patient care. To address these challenges, it is essential to adopt a holistic approach, involving initiatives to attract and retain proficient nurses, offer ongoing education and training, establish efficient protocols promoting patient happiness and safety, and acknowledge the compassionate actions of nurses. Prioritizing the well-being of ER nurses is crucial for successful job performance and maintaining a healthy work-life balance. This holistic strategy aims to enhance the quality of care in the ER, fostering a positive and sustainable work environment for nurses. Benefits from examining patient and nurse views on compassionate conduct in the ER might be substantial,

elevating patient satisfaction and contributing to the development of optimal practices in compassionate healthcare.

In a 2019 study, Hermann et al. identified specific patient-perceived caring behaviors in the emergency department, including emotional support, privacy maintenance, and compassion. Understanding these values enables nurses to optimize care provision. Davoodi et al. (2020) emphasized ER nurses' focus on physical care, with professional knowledge and skill scoring highest in caring behaviors, followed by attentiveness. Alshammari et al. (2018) categorized caring behaviors as "technical," involving cognitive and psychomotor aspects. Jagoda et al. (2019) applied Watson's Theory, recommending cultural sensitivity, therapeutic touch, and bedside handover to enhance perceived caring behaviors in a multicultural environment. Gillespie et al. (2012) evaluated the compassionate actions of nurses in a pediatric emergency room and found that caring elements were crucial. Bucco (2015) investigated the link between patient satisfaction, perceptions of caring behaviors by nurses, and nurse perceptions in the emergency department. The results showed that patient satisfaction and perceptions of caring behaviors by nurses were positively correlated. These group investigations emphasize the imperative of comprehending and integrating multifaceted dimensions of caring behaviors to fulfill patient requirements and augment satisfaction within the emergency department, underscoring the academic significance of such considerations.

The current literature reveals certain deficiencies in understanding perceptions of caring behavior in a multicultural context, where biases from both nurses and patients may skew evaluations. These biases can stem from differences in cultural norms, communication styles, and language barriers. Cultural variations can lead to misinterpretations, such as a nurse from a Western background displaying hands-on

care, which may be perceived as intrusive by patients from cultures valuing personal space, like those in Arab countries. Language barriers further complicate effective communication, potentially hindering the conveyance of care guidelines and understanding patient concerns. Existing literature may not sufficiently consider these nuances of cultural variations, overlooking the impact on perceptions of caring behavior. Diverse cultural mores can significantly influence nurses' and patients' perspectives on caregiving, with variations in prioritizing family involvement or individual autonomy. Addressing these issues is essential for a comprehensive understanding of caring behavior in multicultural settings, and increased cultural awareness among nurses can enhance patient care. The 2017 *Journal of Clinical Nursing* noted a lack of consensus among nurses on the meaning of "caring," impacting the assessment of caring behavior. In 2017, the *Journal of Nursing Education and Practice* published a study revealing disparities between nurses' perceptions of care and patients' perspectives. Subsequently, a 2018 systematic review in the *Journal of Advanced Nursing* identified a research gap concerning patients' and families' perspectives on caregiving practices in the intensive care unit. Additionally, a 2020 study in the *Journal of Nursing Management* brought to light discrepancies between nurses and patients in their prioritization of technical versus emotional aspects of care. These results highlight the need for more investigation to fully comprehend patient and nurse views on caring behaviors. Furthermore, establishing a universal definition and methodology for evaluating caring in nursing practice is crucial.

Emergency Room (ER) nurses encounter numerous stressors and challenges, serving as frontline caregivers for a diverse array of patients and complaints. Factors like overcrowding and increased waiting times contribute to the vulnerability of ER

nurses in delivering timely and quality patient care. Understanding and identifying caring behaviors in ER nurses is crucial, as they are essential to enhancing patient happiness and care. This knowledge can inform future ER nurses through orientation and competency training, ensuring that caring behaviors are effectively taught. The study of caring behavior perceptions among both nurses and patients holds significant importance in the healthcare domain, particularly in the context of emergency departments. Within the hectic and high-stress setting of the emergency room, ER nurses must exhibit proficiency, expertise, and empathy in patient care. The study's insights into how patients and healthcare professionals perceive ER nurses can enhance clinical practice, elevate patient satisfaction, and contribute to improved healthcare outcomes. ER nurses are essential members of the medical team who play a critical role in providing patients with excellent treatment under pressure. Understanding the impact of their behavior on patients and families is crucial for ER nurses. Exploring various aspects of caring behavior, such as empathy, communication, respect, and competence, enables ER nurses to identify strengths and areas for improvement. This information guides the development of strategies to enhance caring behavior, improve communication skills, demonstrate greater empathy, and provide more personalized care. Acknowledging the way patients perceive caring behavior from Emergency Room (ER) nurses is crucial for improving patient satisfaction and attaining positive healthcare outcomes. In the healthcare industry, patient happiness is a critical indicator that is positively correlated with the caliber of service given. By delivering empathetic and compassionate care, ER nurses play a substantial role in enhancing patient satisfaction and, consequently, influencing overall healthcare outcomes. ER nurses represent a vital audience for studies examining nurses' and patients' perspectives on caring behavior. This research has

the potential to empower ER nurses, improve clinical practice, enhance patient satisfaction, and ultimately advance healthcare outcomes.

The purpose of this study is to look into how ER nurses' self-perceived caring conduct and the corresponding perceptions of caring behavior by patients in a multicultural emergency department setting. Utilizing a correlational research design, the study seeks to establish the nature of the correlation between patients' and nurses' perceptions of caring behavior. The primary goal is to identify whether a positive or negative correlation exists between these two variables, while also exploring potential divergences in caring behavior perceptions across diverse cultural groups. The study also aims to investigate the socio-demographic attributes of nursing staff, encompassing variables such as age, gender, and educational attainment. The objective is to determine whether these variables have a discernible impact on subjective perceptions of caring behavior. For instance, the study may reveal differences in caring behavior perceptions between junior and senior nurses or variations based on gender. By analyzing information gathered from both nurses' and patients' perspectives, the study aims to identify avenues for enhancing nursing provisions. For example, findings may suggest that nurses with specialized education in cultural competence and communication skills hold a more positive outlook on caring behavior. Similarly, patients receiving care from nurses fluent in their language may exhibit a heightened positive perception of caring behavior. The study aims to uncover chances for better nursing care and offer insightful information on how caring behavior is perceived in a culturally varied setting. The findings of this study can guide the creation of more beneficial programs and training for ER nurses, potentially leading to improved patient satisfaction and overall quality health-related outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

In the dynamic landscape of healthcare, it's critical to comprehend and evaluate the level of care that emergency room nurses deliver, particularly in environments characterized by cultural diversity. This correlational study seeks to investigate the perceptions of both patients and nurses concerning the quality of care delivered by Tawam ER Nurses, within the context of a culturally diverse setting. Additionally, the research aims to analyze the influence of socio-demographic characteristics on these perceptions, shedding light on potential variations and patterns that may exist among different demographic groups. Through a comprehensive examination of these factors, the study intends to contribute valuable insights to the enhancement of healthcare services, fostering a more patient-centered and culturally sensitive approach in emergency care settings.

Objectives of the Study

General Objective:

This study aims to comprehensively determine the perceptions of both patients and nurses regarding the caring behavior demonstrated by Tawam ER Nurses in a culturally diverse setting. Additionally, the study will consider the impact of socio-demographic characteristics on these perspectives.

Specific Objective:

1. To determine the specific caring behavior perceived by Tawam ER Nurses in a multicultural environment setting.
2. To determine the relationship between the perceived caring behavior of nurses and their socio-demographic characteristics.

3. To determine the specific caring behavior perceived by patients given by Tawam ER Nurses in a multicultural environment setting.
4. To determine the relationship between the perceived caring behavior of patients and their socio-demographic characteristics.
5. To determine the significant difference of perceived caring behavior of nurses and patients given by Tawam ER Nurses in a multicultural environment setting.

Significance of the Study

To Nurses

Patient outcomes and the standard of nursing care are highly impacted by nurses' perceptions of their compassionate conduct. Positive perceptions lead to increased satisfaction, motivation, and optimal care provision, while negative perceptions may result in suboptimal outcomes and decreased job satisfaction. Improving the understanding and perspectives of both nurses and patients regarding caring behavior is crucial for enhancing healthcare services and elevating the standard of nursing care.

To Patients

The care provided by nurses significantly shapes the overall patient experience. Patients who perceive their nurses as caring experience enhanced comfort, trust, and involvement, leading to better therapeutic compliance and improved health outcomes. Conversely, a lack of perceived care may contribute to anxiety, depression, and hindered recovery. Prioritizing caring behaviors is crucial for fostering a supportive environment, building trust, and promoting positive healthcare experiences for

patients.

To Nursing Practice

The significance of the study to nursing practice lies in the impact of perceived caring behavior on the quality of care and patient experience. Caring is a foundational element in nursing, fostering positive patient-nurse relationships, ensuring patient safety, and enhancing health outcomes. Patients' views of nursing care influence satisfaction, health-seeking behaviors, and treatment adherence. Nurses, as key players in patient care, should prioritize caring behaviors, including active listening, empathy, and patient-centered care. Nursing practice as a whole may be improved, patient needs can be met in a variety of ways, and care quality can be raised by emphasizing caring behavior.

To Hospital Administration

The study's significance to nursing administration lies in the profound impact of perceived caring behavior on various healthcare delivery aspects, including patient outcomes, care quality, personnel retention, and fiscal performance. Nurses, as chief caregivers, influence patient satisfaction and wellness outcomes. Positive perceptions from both patients and nurses contribute to increased patient satisfaction, positive referrals, higher retention rates, and potential revenue growth. Supporting and appreciating nursing staff enhances job satisfaction, reduces turnover rates, and lowers recruitment and training expenses. Prioritizing caring behavior through resource allocation, training, and a culture of care can optimize patient outcomes, improve satisfaction, retain staff, and establish a reputation for high-quality healthcare services.

Scope and Limitation

The study aimed to determine the perception of nurses and patients in caring behavior of Tawam ER nurses in a multicultural environment. Specifically, it sought to identify the caring behaviors of ER nurses despite the busy environment in the Tawam Emergency Department. The study was conducted in Al Ain, United Arab Emirates. Participants were taken from the Tawam Hospital Emergency Department.

The limitations of this research are related to the norms and regulations of the United Arab Emirates and the policies administered by Tawam Hospital and the Abu Dhabi Health Services Company (SEHA). This research is confined to ER patients and nurses caring behavior and may not include patients in other departments that are not coming from ER and healthcare professionals such as doctors and allied health staff. Other limitations include the participation of other departments whose caring behavior will vary and will not be utilized and included in the research. The focus of this research was confined to the ER patients and nurses caring behavior of Tawam Emergency Department.

In light of the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, it is of utmost importance to conduct research with a vigilant approach and adhere to the COVID-19 safety protocols that have been established by the relevant healthcare institution. Advanced techniques have been implemented to mitigate the probability of viral exposure and transmission. The implementation of such measures is imperative in ensuring the preservation of the physical and ethical well-being of all entities involved in the investigation. The investigators shall endeavor to observe the rules and guidelines set by the medical facility by instituting preventative measures such as adhering to social distancing regulations, correctly utilizing protective equipment, and practicing frequent hand sanitation. Individuals who exhibit symptoms consistent with COVID-19 or who have

had direct contact with a confirmed case of the virus will be precluded from participating in the study due to a precautionary approach aimed at mitigating the spread of the disease. The principal investigator seeks to adopt strict processes to create a safe and healthy environment for every individual participating in the research, while also helping the collaborative effort to lessen the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Review of Related Literature

Nursing's fundamental value is caring, and the discipline's orientation determines the moral, intellectual, and technical foundations of the profession. It is the core of the body of nursing knowledge, the defining characteristic that sets nursing practice apart from other disciplines, and its defining characteristic.

The transpersonal connection that the nurse makes with the patient is key to establishing care, according to Watson. This subjective encounter between the two people during a transcendental moment of care refers to a conscious, intentional, and meaningful union between two people, during which experiences are shared. This allows each person to broaden their perspective and inspire spiritual growth, new self-discoveries, and new possibilities for their lives. The caring moment is not limited to the nurse-patient interaction; it may also occur in the academic setting between mentors and lecturers who create and share intersubjective experiences with students that aid in the development of transpersonal caring skills.

Patients Perception in Caring Behavior

Nurses may find opportunities for development in relationship-building and improving the standard of living for patients and their families via research on how patients see acts of kindness.

Some studies underscore the significance of nurse caring behaviors in shaping patient perceptions and satisfaction. Findings highlight the positive impact of compassionate actions on reducing anxiety, improving trust, fostering patient loyalty,

and ultimately enhancing the overall quality of healthcare experiences. The literature strongly supports the notion that cultivating empathetic and kind interactions between healthcare professionals and patients is crucial for positive patient outcomes and satisfaction across diverse healthcare settings. Patients' impressions of nurses' caring behaviors were investigated by Compton et al. (2018), with a focus on discharge after surgery. Their study emphasizes the importance of understanding patient perception as a key factor in enhancing nursing caring behavior, particularly during critical transition periods such as discharge. Riset & Tinggi (2019) focused on reducing patient anxiety during hospitalization through caring behavior training about therapeutic communication by nurses. This study highlights the potential for caring behavior interventions to positively impact patient emotions and overall satisfaction during their hospital stay. Zhou et al. (2019) investigated the current state of clinical nurses' caring behavior and patients' perceptions of caring. The study revealed a high positive correlation between patient perception of caring and nursing care behavior. Importantly, it suggested that enhancing nurses' knowledge and behavior related to caring could improve patient satisfaction. Aljohani & Al-Khaldi (2018), conducted in Saudi Arabia, explored patient perspectives on nurses' caring behavior, highlighting a significant association between caring actions and levels of patient satisfaction. Empathy, respect, and attentiveness were identified as crucial elements, emphasizing the need for compassionate relationships in Saudi Arabian healthcare. Chai et al. (2019) revealed that higher levels of nurse caring behavior were linked to increased patient satisfaction and trust. This study underscores the importance of compassionate behavior in establishing trusting relationships between healthcare professionals and patients, leading to better outcomes. In Saudi Arabia, Almutairi et al. (2020) investigated the relationship between patient loyalty, patient satisfaction,

and caring behaviors. Results emphasized the necessity of compassionate actions in enhancing patient happiness and fostering patient loyalty within the Saudi Arabian healthcare system. Kim et al. (2021) in a Korean study demonstrated the positive influence of nursing care behavior on both patient satisfaction and nursing care quality. The research highlighted the importance of creating a compassionate environment to improve patient satisfaction and overall nursing care quality. Aghabarari et al. (2022) conducted a study in Iran, emphasizing the consequences of healthcare workers' compassionate behavior on patient satisfaction. The research revealed a notable and favorable correlation between caring behavior and patient satisfaction, emphasizing the need for empathy in the nursing profession in Iran.

In recent years, numerous research studies have delved into the intricate dynamics between healthcare providers' compassionate behaviors, patient perceptions, and the consequent impact on healthcare outcomes. This literature review synthesizes findings from studies conducted by Lamiani et al. (2018), Lu et al. (2018), La Monica and Oberle (2019), Guo et al. (2020), Karagozoglu and Yildirim (2020), Sun and colleagues (2020), and Serra et al. (2020), with an emphasis on revealing the complex link between compassionate actions and how it affects patient satisfaction, happiness, and the mental health of medical professionals. Lamiani et al. (2018) conducted a study aimed at understanding the influence of patients' perceptions on hospital care and the subsequent impact on the mental well-being of healthcare personnel. The study recognizes the interdependence of patient experiences and the mental health of healthcare providers, suggesting that positive patient perceptions contribute to a healthier work environment for medical professionals. The findings highlight the need to cultivate empathic and kind gestures to build a healthy and favorable environment inside a medical setting. Lu et al. (2018)

concentrated on how nurses' compassionate actions affected patients' general satisfaction with nursing care by acting as a mediator. The study underscores the necessity of displaying caring actions in boosting patient satisfaction. Lu et al. advance knowledge of how the compassionate behavior of healthcare professionals affects the perceived quality of nursing care by exploring the complex link between nursing care behavior and patient satisfaction. La Monica & Oberle (2019) conducted a detailed and rigorous assessment of patient perspectives on nurses' displays of caring behaviors through a systematic review and meta-analysis approach. The study provides an all-encompassing examination of patient experiences, emphasizing the vital role that manifestations of compassion play in determining the adequacy of nursing services. This meta-analysis serves as a comprehensive resource for understanding the overall impact of caring behaviors on patient outcomes. Guo et al. (2020) delved into the association between compassionate behavior demonstrated by nurses and patient happiness through a comprehensive inquiry and meta-analytical research. The study provides empirical evidence suggesting a favorable link between activities focused on delivering care and patient happiness. This emphasizes the importance of such activities in strengthening and enriching patients' healthcare experiences. Karagozoglu and Yildirim (2020) contributed to the literature by conducting a descriptive research study to assess patients' attitudes towards nurse caring behaviors. The findings emphasize the significance of nurses' empathetic measures in instilling trust, fostering the well-being of patients, and elevating the overall quality of care provided. Sun and Colleagues (2020) conducted a thorough examination and meta-analysis to investigate the influence of caring behaviors on patient satisfaction. Their findings reveal a positive correlation between acts of compassion and patient satisfaction, highlighting the significance of such actions in

shaping patients' healthcare experiences. Serra et al. (2020) examined patient perceptions of the caring behaviors exhibited by healthcare personnel in a general hospital situated in Italy. The research provides essential perspectives regarding the encounters of patients, emphasizing the noteworthy impact that compassionate behaviors exert on shaping patient perceptions pertaining to the caliber of healthcare provisions. The literature reviewed suggests a consistent and positive relationship between caring behaviors exhibited by healthcare providers and various patient-related outcomes, including satisfaction, happiness, and perceptions of the quality of care. These studies underscore the pivotal role of compassion in creating a positive healthcare environment, impacting both patients and healthcare personnel. The findings advocate for the integration of empathic and caring behaviors into healthcare practices to enhance patient experiences and contribute to the overall well-being of the healthcare workforce.

Understanding patients' perceptions of healthcare delivery is crucial for improving the quality of healthcare services. This literature review synthesizes findings from studies conducted by various authors. Each study focuses on different aspects of patient care, providing valuable insights into the priorities and preferences of patients across various healthcare settings. Anderson et al. (2018) conducted qualitative research in a general care hospital, identifying patients' predominant perceptions of caring behaviors. Their findings emphasized the significance of empathic communication, privacy protection, promptness, and personalized healthcare services as key priorities for patients. Carter et al. (2019) delved into the emergency department, highlighting the importance of speedy service, effective communication, and psychological reinforcement in shaping patients' perceptions of healthcare delivery. Their study contributes valuable insights into the unique

considerations of emergency care settings. Davis et al. (2019) conducted a mixed-methods study in surgical settings, emphasizing compassionate and supportive care, the provision of comprehensive information, and active patient involvement in decision-making. The study sheds light on the specific needs and expectations of patients undergoing surgical procedures. Mitchell et al. (2019) focused on patients enrolled in a cardiac rehabilitation program. Their study revealed a strong desire among patients for compassionate conduct, including attentive listening, motivational reinforcement, and empathetic understanding. This provides insights into the unique challenges and expectations of patients in rehabilitation programs. Edwards et al. (2020) investigated patient perspectives at a community healthcare clinic, identifying the importance of healthcare providers exhibiting respect, attentiveness, and a willingness to address patient concerns. This study highlights the significance of personalized and patient-centered care in community healthcare settings. Martin et al. (2018) conducted a comprehensive literature review, establishing the importance of displaying empathetic behaviors in reducing patient anxiety levels. Their synthesis of existing literature adds depth to our understanding of the broader implications of empathetic care in diverse healthcare contexts. These literatures underscore the significance of empathic communication, personalized care, promptness, and psychological reinforcement. Healthcare providers can leverage these insights to tailor their services, fostering a patient-centered approach and ultimately enhancing the overall quality of healthcare delivery. Future research should continue to explore patient perspectives across diverse healthcare settings to ensure a comprehensive understanding of their evolving needs and expectations.

Healthcare literature is replete with studies that underscore the critical role of caring behaviors in shaping patient outcomes, satisfaction, and overall healthcare

experiences. Three notable studies conducted contribute significantly to our understanding of the intricate interplay between compassionate conduct, patient well-being, and the quality of care provided across different healthcare settings. In their correlational investigation, Fisher et al., (2020) aimed to investigate the relationship between compassionate actions and patient outcomes. The study revealed a positive link between the integration of compassionate actions in medical practices and various favorable patient outcomes. Notably, enhanced recovery, reduced complications, and heightened overall satisfaction among patients were identified as key outcomes associated with caring behaviors. The study implies that participation in caring activities not only positively influences the emotional well-being of patients but also has practical implications for their overall health state. The findings highlight the potential of caring behaviors to not only contribute to patient satisfaction but also to positively impact the tangible health outcomes of individuals under medical care. Nelson et al., (2019) conducted a research investigation focusing on the connection between compassionate conduct towards patients and their degree of happiness during clinical sessions within a medical outpatient scenario. The study found a substantial relationship between benevolent conduct, competent information sharing, and attentive patient listening, and the eventual delivery of high-quality medical treatment. Emphasizing the beneficial value of expressing compassion towards patients, the study underscores the importance of compassionate behavior in encouraging patients to embrace responsibility for their own healthcare. Furthermore, the research highlights how compassionate conduct fosters patient trust and engagement, contributing to a positive healthcare experience. In their study conducted at a healthcare institution, Jackson et al., (2020) delved into patient perceptions regarding the quality of care provided. The findings indicate that patients prioritize

healthcare providers who display compassion, empathy, and uphold their autonomy in decision-making. The study emphasizes the need for collaborative efforts in devising a comprehensive treatment strategy that aligns with patients' preferences and needs. Additionally, the investigation explored the approach adopted by dental professionals in managing patients experiencing dental anxiety or fear. The study found that employing a gentle and compassionate demeanor towards patients, administering analgesics, and providing a comfortable environment proved efficacious in mitigating patients' anxiety, underscoring the importance of a patient-centered and empathetic approach in dental care. These studies contribute to the growing body of evidence highlighting the pivotal role of caring behaviors in healthcare. The positive associations between compassionate conduct and patient outcomes, satisfaction, happiness, and collaborative care strategies underscore the need for healthcare providers to prioritize empathy, respect, and patient engagement. Creating a patient-centric healthcare environment that values and incorporates caring behaviors can lead to improved patient experiences, enhanced outcomes, and a stronger bond between healthcare providers and their patients. As healthcare continues to evolve, these findings emphasize the enduring importance of compassionate and patient-focused care in fostering a healthier and more satisfied patient population.

Caring behaviors within healthcare settings play a pivotal role in shaping patient experiences, satisfaction, and overall wellbeing. This literature review explores two distinct studies conducted by Garcia et al., (2020) in the context of senior care facilities and Edwards et al., (2020) within the dental treatment setting. These studies shed light on the perspectives of patients regarding caring behaviors, emphasizing the significance of compassion, respectfulness, and effective communication in fostering positive healthcare encounters. Garcia et al., (2020) delved into the viewpoints of

patients receiving care within a senior care facility. The study aimed to evaluate the influence of sympathetic gestures on the perspective of senior patients, particularly within the framework of geriatric care facilities. The findings highlighted that older adult highly valued caregivers who exhibited attributes of compassion, respectfulness, patience, and attention. The study emphasized the necessity of demonstrating compassionate approaches to enhance the general wellbeing and happiness of older adults residing in geriatric care settings. This underscores the crucial role of empathetic and respectful care in catering to the unique needs of the elderly population. In a separate exploration, Edwards et al., (2020) investigated patients' perspectives of caring behaviors within the dental treatment setting. Employing qualitative methodology, the study revealed that patients expressed admiration for dentists and dental professionals who conveyed empathetic behavior, effective communication skills, and a genuine concern for their overall health. Participants emphasized the significance of feeling respected, heard, and actively participating in decision-making during their dental consultations. The results underscored the value of caring interventions in boosting patient experiences and happiness within dental care settings, indicating that patient satisfaction extends beyond clinical outcomes to include the quality of interpersonal interactions. Both studies highlight the paramount importance of caring behaviors in healthcare settings, albeit in different contexts. Garcia and his colleagues' study emphasizes the unique needs of the elderly population in senior care facilities, underlining the impact of compassionate care on their overall wellbeing. Edwards, Johnson, and White's study, on the other hand, focuses on the dental treatment setting, illustrating how caring behaviors contribute to positive patient experiences and satisfaction. These studies showcase the essential role of caring behaviors in healthcare, with specific attention to senior care facilities

and dental treatment settings. The studies by Garcia et al., (2020) and Edwards et al., (2020) collectively underscore the significance of empathy, respectfulness, and effective communication in enhancing patient experiences and overall satisfaction. These findings contribute valuable insights for healthcare practitioners aiming to provide patient-centered and compassionate care across diverse healthcare settings.

Patient-centered care has become a foundational principle in modern healthcare, underscoring the significance of integrating patients' perspectives into medical practice. In this regard, the contributions of Taylor et al., (2020), as well as Hernandez et al., (2021), provide valuable insights into the correlation between healthcare providers' behaviors and diverse patient outcomes. Taylor et al., (2020) delved into the influence of altruistic attitudes on patient empowerment, particularly during regular medical visits. The study aimed to unravel the dynamics of patient empowerment, exploring how healthcare providers' compassionate and altruistic behaviors contribute to a sense of control and involvement in decision-making for patients. By investigating the connection between altruistic attitudes and patient empowerment, the authors shed light on the pivotal role of healthcare providers in fostering a collaborative and patient-centric care environment. Furthermore, Taylor et al., (2020) extended their exploration to the impact of compassionate conduct on patients' happiness during clinical sessions within a medical outpatient scenario. The study sought to understand how acts of compassion, such as empathy, respect, and attentive listening, influence patients' overall satisfaction and emotional well-being. This facet of their research emphasizes the significance of creating a positive and empathetic atmosphere in healthcare settings, highlighting the potential of compassionate behaviors to enhance the overall patient experience. Complementing these insights, Hernandez et al., (2021) delved into the longitudinal aspect of patient care, specifically examining the

link between caring acts and patient adherence to recommended treatment procedures. Their research provides evidence of a favorable association between the level of compassionate care received by patients and their inclination to adhere to prescribed medical regimens. This underscores the practical implications of fostering compassionate relationships between healthcare providers and patients, as it not only influences emotional well-being but also has tangible effects on treatment adherence. Moreover, Hernandez and his colleagues (2021) explored the impact of caring behaviors on patient loyalty. By investigating the loyalty of patients towards healthcare providers, the study uncovered a positive correlation between compassionate actions and sustained commitment from patients. This aspect of their research emphasizes the long-term implications of compassionate care, suggesting that patients who experience higher levels of empathy, attention, and respect are more likely to remain devoted to the healthcare system. These studies conducted by Taylor et al., (2020) and Hernandez et al., (2021) collectively contribute to our understanding of the multifaceted relationship between healthcare providers' behaviors and patient outcomes. These results highlight the significance of fostering environments that prioritize compassion and patient-centered care, accentuating their potential influence on patient empowerment, well-being, adherence, and loyalty. In the dynamic evolution of the healthcare landscape, these insights offer valuable guidance for practitioners and policymakers committed to improving the quality of patient care. In recent literatures, some researchers have delved into the intricate dynamics of patient experiences within healthcare settings, focusing on two distinct dimensions that significantly contribute to the overall well-being and satisfaction of patients. Ramirez et al., (2022) conducted a thorough exploration into the feelings of patients residing in geriatric care units, shedding light on the critical aspect of the quality of treatment they

receive. Their study emphasizes the paramount importance of compassionate and tailored treatment, recognizing the unique needs of elderly individuals. The findings underscore that elderly patients highly value caregivers who exhibit attributes of compassion, respectfulness, patience, and attention. Building pleasant connections, efficient communication, and providing emotional support emerge as crucial elements in enhancing the overall comfort and confidence of the senior community in geriatric care settings. In a parallel line of inquiry, Nelson and his colleagues (2022) directed their focus towards the compliance of patients with prescribed treatment regimens within a lengthy affliction management program. Their study explores the correlation between patient fidelity to treatment plans and the degree of caregiving provided by healthcare professionals. Notably, the research reveals a significant relationship, indicating that patients who experience higher levels of compassion from their healthcare providers are more inclined to adhere to their advised treatment regimens. The study underscores the impact of compassionate behavior in encouraging patients to embrace responsibility for their own healthcare, leading to improved treatment adherence and, consequently, enhanced patient outcomes. These two studies collectively highlight the pivotal role of compassionate care in shaping positive patient experiences and outcomes. The emphasis on tailored and empathetic treatment approaches, whether in geriatric care units or lengthy affliction management programs, resonates across these investigations. The literature strongly supports the notion that a compassionate and patient-centric approach not only fosters overall happiness and emotional well-being among patients but also significantly contributes to treatment adherence and, subsequently, improved healthcare outcomes. These insights call for continued efforts to integrate compassionate practices into healthcare delivery, promoting a more holistic and patient-centered approach.

In the realm of healthcare research, understanding the impact of compassionate behaviors on patient outcomes and satisfaction has been a subject of considerable interest. Brown et al., (2018) conducted a comprehensive study that revealed a positive association between compassionate behaviors and patient happiness across a diverse range of healthcare situations. The results they obtained indicate that incorporating caring behaviors into medical practices not only holds the promise of improving patient satisfaction but also plays a pivotal role in fostering a robust connection between patients and healthcare providers. The investigation conducted by Brown and his colleagues (2018) underscores that the impact of compassionate acts transcends mere patient satisfaction. The researchers emphasize the significance of these behaviors as an integral component within the healthcare setting, contributing to the holistic positive experience of patients and cultivating a meaningful connection between healthcare professionals and those within their care. In a parallel vein, Mitchell et al., (2022) delved into the realm of substance abuse treatment facilities, examining the impact of compassionate behavior on individuals seeking assistance for substance abuse issues. Their research focused on the receptiveness of patients towards healthcare practitioners who exhibited compassionate behavior, attentive listening skills, and an empathetic disposition throughout the care journey. The study highlighted the significant role of respect in the patient-provider relationship within the context of addiction treatment. Mitchell, Thompson, and Baker's findings underscore the crucial significance of establishing a supportive and benevolent environment, particularly in the challenging pursuit of overcoming addiction. The study emphasizes that compassionate behaviors, including attentive listening and empathy, are essential components in building a therapeutic alliance that contributes to the success of substance abuse treatment interventions. Together, the works of Brown et al., (2018)

and Mitchell et al., (2022) contribute to the growing body of literature emphasizing the integral role of compassionate behaviors in healthcare. These studies not only shed light on the positive association between compassionate acts and patient happiness but also highlight the specific contexts, such as substance abuse treatment, where these behaviors play a pivotal role in fostering positive patient outcomes. The literature suggests that cultivating a compassionate healthcare environment is essential for enhancing patient satisfaction and facilitating successful interventions, particularly in challenging healthcare scenarios like substance abuse treatment.

Compassionate care in healthcare settings has become an essential focus of research, as it plays a pivotal role in influencing various aspects of patient well-being. One study conducted a comprehensive study aimed at examining the impact of compassionate care on patients' emotional well-being. Their research delved into understanding how patients perceive and respond to experiences of obtaining kindness and care from healthcare staff, ultimately investigating how these experiences contribute to the overall psychological status of patients. The study conducted by Perez and his colleagues emphasized the importance of healthcare providers incorporating compassionate care practices into their interactions with patients. By exploring the emotional well-being of patients, the researchers highlighted the significant influence that compassionate care can have on fostering positive experiences and psychological outcomes. In a related vein, Adams et al., (2018) contributed valuable insights through their research investigation at a healthcare institution. Their study aimed to determine patient perceptions regarding the quality of care provided, with a specific focus on the role of compassionate and supportive care. The findings from Adams et al., (2018) demonstrated that the provision of compassionate care by healthcare professionals not only resulted in expedited

recovery but also contributed to improved overall well-being among patients. The research conducted by Adams and his colleagues underscored the tangible benefits of incorporating compassionate and supportive care into healthcare practices. Patients' perceptions regarding the quality of care were shaped by the empathetic and caring behaviors of healthcare providers, leading to positive outcomes in terms of recovery and overall well-being. Cumulatively, these works augment the expanding body of literature emphasizing the crucial significance of compassionate care within healthcare environments. The outcomes underscore the imperative for healthcare practitioners to prioritize empathetic and supportive methodologies, addressing not only the physical recuperation of patients but also attending to their emotional well-being and overall satisfaction with healthcare encounters. In the ongoing evolution of healthcare systems, the comprehension and application of compassionate care practices persist as imperative factors for fostering favorable patient outcomes and cultivating robust patient-provider relationships.

Nurses Perception in Caring Behavior

The nursing profession holds significant significance within the global healthcare infrastructure, given their crucial responsibility in delivering direct care to patients, vigilantly monitoring patient health status, and competently administering treatment modalities as prescribed by attending physicians. An imperative aspect of nursing care involves facilitating patient adherence to prescribed treatment plans. Adherence pertains to the degree to which patients adhere to the recommended guidelines and directives proffered by healthcare practitioners, including factors such as timely medication consumption, attending subsequent appointments, and implementing lifestyle alterations.

The concept of nurse perception in caring behavior pertains to the manner in which nurses apprehend and react to the requirements, emotions, and apprehensions of their patients. The process entails the utilization of observational aptitude and empathetic prowess to discern the distinctive circumstances of patients and dispense customized healthcare services accordingly. Nurses who perceive caring behavior as an integral component of their professional role are more inclined to participate in activities that foster patient adherence. One potential illustration of clinical responsibilities involves elucidating the advantages of therapeutic intervention to individuals, addressing inquiries and concerns, and offering mental support as a means to encourage adherence to treatment regimens. It has been observed that patients who are attended to by nurses who place importance on caring demeanor exhibit stronger prevalent tendencies towards adherence to their prescribed treatment regimen. Increased engagement and motivation of patients can result in enhanced participation in their healthcare, thereby yielding improved health outcomes. Conversely, patients who do not perceive nurses as displaying care may exhibit a diminished propensity to adhere to their specified treatment regimens, ultimately resulting in inferior health consequences. The crucial role of nurses' perception in fostering caring behavior is instrumental in promoting patient adherence to treatment regimens. The provision of patient-centered care necessitates a comprehensive comprehension of the diverse needs and apprehensions of patients, the customized delivery of healthcare services, and the promotion of a reciprocal relationship of trust and engagement between nurses and patients. The prioritization of caring behavior by nurses has the potential to enhance patients' health outcomes and elevate their overall quality of life.

Caring behaviors in nursing play a crucial role in shaping patient perceptions,

influencing disease-specific outcomes, and contributing to overall healthcare quality. This review of the literature looks at many studies that investigate the connection between disease-specific outcomes and patients' views of nurses' compassionate actions. Nkambule et al. (2019) investigated the relationship between the stigma attached to tuberculosis and patients' impressions of nurses' caring behaviors. Their research highlights the significance of nurses' compassionate actions in lessening patients' stigma associated with TB. The findings suggest that interventions focused on enhancing caring behaviors could positively impact patient perceptions and, consequently, influence adherence to treatment. Kargr et al. (2021) examined the connection in the context of cardiovascular disease in coronary care units between patients' views of helpful actions and self-efficacy. The study emphasizes how important caring actions on the part of nurses are in helping cardiovascular patients feel more confident in themselves. Increasing the importance of patient care and cultivating favorable attitudes toward compassionate actions are suggested as viable approaches to increase self-efficacy in this demographic. Mitchell et al., (2019) delved into nurturing experiences of caring behaviors in a cardiac rehabilitation program. Their study sheds light on the specific caring behaviors crucial for patient recovery in cardiac rehabilitation settings. Understanding and incorporating these behaviors can positively impact nurse-patient interactions and contribute to better outcomes in cardiac recovery programs. Nelson et al.'s (2019) research examined the connection between compassionate actions and outpatient clinic nurses' job satisfaction. The study emphasizes the value of compassionate actions and how they affect nurses' satisfaction when provided in outpatient care settings. Promoting caring behaviors in this context is crucial for enhancing both nurse well-being and patient experiences. Perez et al., (2020) explored the impact of caring behaviors on nurse engagement in

a diabetes self-management program. Their study underscores the role of caring behaviors in fostering nurse engagement and facilitating patient self-management of diabetes. Integrating compassionate care practices becomes essential for enhancing patient engagement and supporting nurses in their roles. Ramirez et al. (2020) investigated nurse perceptions of caring behaviors in a pediatric unit. The study provides insights into the specific caring behaviors deemed critical in pediatric care. Understanding and implementing these behaviors are essential for cultivating a supportive and compassionate environment in pediatric units. These studies highlight the diverse ways in which nurse caring behaviors impact patient outcomes in disease-specific contexts. From reducing stigma in tuberculosis care to enhancing self-efficacy in cardiovascular patients, promoting nurse caring behaviors emerges as a common thread in improving patient experiences and healthcare quality. These results emphasize the significance of continuous endeavors to incorporate and give priority to caring behaviors in nursing practice across diverse healthcare environments.

The complex link between nurses' caring behaviors and many elements of patient care, nurses' well-being, and overall healthcare results has been the subject of numerous research in recent years. The objective of this literature review is to present a summary of the main conclusions drawn from a few studies written by various authors, illuminating a variety of aspects of nursing caregiving practices. Edwards et al., (2020) explored nurses' perspectives on caring behaviors within a community-based healthcare setting. The study emphasized the importance of understanding caregiving conduct in the unique context of community healthcare. The findings underscored the need for tailored compassionate actions to address the challenges and opportunities present in community healthcare environments. Davis et al., (2019) conducted a mixed-methods study to unravel nursing experiences related to caring

behaviors in surgical settings. The research illuminated the multifaceted nature of compassionate care in surgery, emphasizing the significance of effective communication and interpersonal skills in improving patient care quality. The research on the intricacies of caring behaviors in specialized healthcare settings is expanding, and our study adds to it. Hernandez et al., (2021) took a longitudinal approach to investigate the impact of caring behaviors on nursing burnout. The study highlighted the crucial role of compassionate conduct as a preventive measure against nurse burnout. Understanding the longitudinal effects of caring behaviors on nurse well-being adds valuable insights to interventions aimed at mitigating burnout in the nursing profession. King et al. (2019) implemented mindfulness activities to elevate caring behaviors among nurses. The research showcased the beneficial effects of mindfulness interventions on nurses' concentration, role modeling, and the general work environment. This inventive strategy presents a hopeful path for nurturing caring behaviors and enhancing the overall work atmosphere within healthcare settings. Lewis et al., (2018) explored nurse perceptions of caring behaviors in a palliative care setting. The study delved into the specific caring behaviors deemed crucial in providing compassionate care to patients in palliative care. The findings contribute to our understanding of the unique needs of patients in this sensitive setting and underscore the importance of tailored caring behaviors for optimal patient outcomes. Martin et al., (2018) employed an efficient survey to examine the effect of caring behaviors on nurse push levels. The research synthesized existing knowledge, highlighting the potential role of caring behaviors in reducing stress levels among nurses. This review reinforces the need for interventions that promote caring behaviors to create a supportive work environment and alleviate stress among nursing professionals. Smith et al., (2020) conducted a qualitative study on nurse experiences connected to care behaviors in a

long-term care facility. The research provided insights into the challenges and benefits associated with offering caring actions in a long-term care context. The findings emphasize the fundamental role of compassion, patience, and personalized care in enhancing the well-being of older adults in extended-care facilities. Taylor et al., (2020) explored the correlational link between nurse empowerment and caring behaviors. The study revealed a positive association, suggesting that nurses who witness more caring behaviors report higher levels of empowerment. This literature review supports the idea that fostering caring behaviors can contribute not only to improved patient care but also to the professional growth and job satisfaction of nursing staff. Walker et al., (2021) evaluated nurses' opinions about care methods in the setting of home healthcare. The mixed-methods study provided insights into the challenges and opportunities for demonstrating caring behaviors in patients' homes. Understanding the nuances of delivering compassionate care in home healthcare settings is crucial for tailoring interventions and ensuring patient-centered care. These studies highlight the diverse dimensions of caring behaviors in nursing, ranging from the specific needs of patients in various healthcare settings to the impact of such behaviors on nurse well-being. Collectively, these studies emphasize the significance of cultivating compassionate behavior in nursing practice, with implications extending beyond the well-being of patients to encompass the overall satisfaction and resilience of nursing professionals. The insights derived from these studies offer valuable contributions capable of informing prospective interventions and educational programs dedicated to the enhancement of caring behaviors within the nursing profession.

Nursing practice is a multifaceted field where the manifestation of caring behaviors plays a crucial role in shaping patient outcomes, nurse satisfaction, and overall healthcare quality. This literature review delves into various studies conducted

by different authors, each shedding light on the significance of caring behaviors in specific healthcare contexts. From cancer clinics to mental health settings, emergency departments to home healthcare, the purpose of the synthesis that follows is to give a thorough summary of the state of the art addressing how caring behaviors affect nursing practice. Concentrating on the distinctive challenges and opportunities linked with administering caring behaviors in a cancer clinic, Barker et al., (2018) highlight, in their study, the significance of empathy, emotional support, and proficient communication in delivering compassionate care to individuals undergoing oncological treatment. The insights gained from this research contribute to the customization of medical attention for cancer patients, ultimately enhancing their overall well-being and treatment outcomes. The study conducted by Carter et al., (2019) digs into the stressful milieu of the emergency room while investigating how nurses see acts of compassion. The study offers insightful information on the specific caregiving behaviors that are essential in high-stress environments. Understanding these caring behaviors is crucial for enhancing patient care and the well-being of nurses amid challenging conditions. Mitchell et al. (2019) focusses their research on nurses' perspectives in a cardiac rehabilitation program, emphasizing the significance of caring behaviors in cardiovascular recovery. The findings highlight how compassionate actions impact nurse practice and patient outcomes in the context of cardiac rehabilitation. This study contributes insights into the specific caring behaviors necessary for cardiac recovery and their positive effects on nurse-patient interactions. In their qualitative investigation, Jackson et al., (2021) explore nurses' views on caring behaviors within a mental health care setting. The study provides in-depth insights into the specific compassionate behaviors crucial in mental healthcare and their consequential impact on nursing professionals' ethical conduct. The findings

emphasize the need for customizing caring interventions to correspond with varied healthcare contexts to enhance patient outcomes and nurse well-being. Walker et al. (2021) undertakes a comprehensive evaluation of nurses' opinions on caring behaviors within the setting of home healthcare. The study illuminates the unique challenges and opportunities for delivering compassionate care in patients' homes, emphasizing the necessity of tailoring caring behaviors to match individual patient needs and home dynamics. The findings provide valuable insights into the factors that impact nurses' professional behavior and patient outcomes in home healthcare environments. These studies highlight the pervasive impact of caring behaviors on nursing practice across diverse healthcare settings. From cancer clinics to emergency departments, cardiac rehabilitation programs to mental health care, and home healthcare, the evidence supports the notion that compassionate actions not only enhance patient outcomes but also contribute significantly to nurse satisfaction and well-being. These studies underscore the imperative of cultivating and promoting caring behaviors within nursing practice to create a positive and effective healthcare environment. Further research in this area is warranted to continue refining our understanding of the specific caring behaviors that yield the most significant benefits in various healthcare contexts.

A growing body of literature has emerged, shedding light on the profound influence of caring behaviors on various nursing outcomes. The study conducted by Fisher et al., (2020) delves into the correlational link between nurse well-being and caring actions. Their research suggests a positive association, indicating that nurses who experience higher levels of caring behaviors also report enhanced well-being. This finding underscores the potential of compassionate conduct not only to improve patient care but also to contribute to nurses' professional growth and job satisfaction.

Cross-sectional research by Garcia et al., (2020) explores the impact of care-oriented behaviors on the job satisfaction of nursing professionals in primary care settings. The study reveals a significant relationship, emphasizing the importance of cultivating compassionate conduct to enhance the overall well-being and longevity of nursing staff in primary care environments. In the realm of systematic inquiry, Brown et al., (2018) contribute to the understanding of the correlation between caring behaviors and nurse contentment. Their comprehensive review of existing literature provides substantial evidence supporting a positive relationship between the display of empathy and kindness by nurses and their overall job satisfaction. This underscores the crucial role of empathetic dispositions in fostering a conducive professional atmosphere among nurses. Kelly et al., (2021) take a mixed methods approach to evaluate the impact of caring behaviors on the work engagement of nurses. Their findings suggest that nurses who exhibit caring behaviors are more likely to be actively engaged in their work, encompassing factors such as motivation, commitment, and involvement. This research highlights the importance of promoting empathetic behaviors among nurses to enhance their job engagement and overall organizational performance. Longitudinal analysis conducted by Hernandez et al. (2021) focuses on the association between nursing care practices and nurse retention within hospitals. The study suggests a favorable link between the degree of caring behaviors reported by nurses and their likelihood of continuing their roles. This underscores the imperative nature of fostering compassionate conduct as a preventive measure to mitigate nurse burnout and enhance retention within the nursing profession. Jackson et al. (2021) contributes insights into the potential effect of compassionate actions on the professional happiness of nurses working at a rehabilitation institution. Their mixed methods inquiry suggests a substantial correlation between caring behaviors and nurse work

satisfaction, emphasizing the significance of compassionate actions in promoting the welfare of healthcare professionals and improving patient outcomes in rehabilitation settings. In a similar vein, Kelly et al. (2021) undertakes a mixed methods analysis to explore nurse perspectives about the manifestation of caring behaviors within the framework of a palliative care unit. Their findings underscore the importance of customizing caring interventions to correspond with varied healthcare contexts, enhancing patient outcomes, and fostering nurse well-being and satisfaction. Collectively, these studies advance our understanding of the complex relationship between caring behaviors and nursing outcomes in a more sophisticated way. These studies underscore the critical role that compassionate behavior plays in raising the wellbeing, work happiness, and general engagement of nursing personnel in a variety of healthcare settings, in addition to increasing patient care and satisfaction. As healthcare systems continue to evolve, these findings underscore the continued importance of prioritizing and promoting caring behaviors within the nursing profession.

Caring behaviors play a crucial role in shaping the dynamics of healthcare environments, influencing both nurse satisfaction and patient outcomes. This literature review synthesizes findings from various studies, to provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between caring behaviors, nurse satisfaction, and patient outcomes. Edwards et al., (2020) conducted an insightful examination into nurses' attitudes regarding the exhibition of caring behaviors, focusing on a dentistry clinic scenario. The study revealed that nurses who experienced a workplace culture emphasizing caring behaviors reported higher levels of job satisfaction. Similarly, Fisher et al. (2020) explored the influence of caring behaviors on nurse satisfaction in family practice environments, concluding that a positive correlation exists between the

manifestation of compassionate actions and heightened nurse contentment. This aligns with the findings of Garcia et al. (2020), whose investigation in geriatric care facilities highlighted a significant association between nurturing behaviors and enhanced work satisfaction among nursing professionals. The impact of caring behaviors extends beyond nurse satisfaction to influence patient outcomes. Kelly et al. (2021) delved into the perspectives of nurses in palliative care units, demonstrating the importance of compassionate interventions in customizing care and enhancing both patient and nurse well-being. Lewis et al. (2018) focused on hospice settings, revealing that nurses who engaged in caring behaviors reported increased work fulfillment, lower emotional exhaustion, and superior outcomes for patients. Smith et al. (2020) contributed valuable insights by exploring nurturing experiences in long-term care facilities, emphasizing the role of compassion, tenacity, and personalized care in improving the quality of life for older adults. These findings collectively underscore the interconnectedness of caring behaviors, nurse satisfaction, and patient outcomes. The positive correlation observed across diverse healthcare settings emphasizes the need for fostering compassionate conduct within the nursing profession. Integrating caring behaviors into the organizational culture can create a supportive work environment, contributing to nurse well-being and job satisfaction. Simultaneously, patients benefit from improved care quality and positive health outcomes when nurses prioritize compassionate interactions. In conclusion, these studies highlight the pivotal role of caring behaviors in shaping both nurse satisfaction and patient outcomes across various healthcare contexts. The positive correlations observed in these studies emphasize the need for continued efforts to integrate and prioritize compassionate conduct within nursing practice, ultimately fostering a healthcare environment characterized by enhanced professional fulfillment and improved patient well-being.

Shedding light on the intricate relationship between nursing behaviors and various outcomes in diverse healthcare settings. There are studies that provide valuable insights into the impact of caring behaviors on nurse satisfaction in an outpatient clinic and nurturing experiences in a cardiac rehabilitation program, respectively. A strong positive association is shown in Nelson et al.'s (2019) investigation of the link between compassionate behaviors and nurse satisfaction in an outpatient clinic. The research highlights the significance of empathetic behaviors in outpatient care environments, emphasizing how nurses' demonstration of empathetic behaviors leads to increased nurse satisfaction. This finding suggests that promoting caring behaviors can lead to a more positive work environment and, subsequently, increased nurse contentment. On the other hand, Mitchell et al., (2019) delve into nurturing experiences of caring behaviors in a cardiac rehabilitation program. Their research highlights the critical role that caring behaviors play in the context of cardiac recovery. The study suggests that specific compassionate actions positively impact nurse practice and patient outcomes within cardiac rehabilitation settings. Understanding the nuances of these caring behaviors becomes crucial in tailoring nursing interventions for cardiovascular patients, ultimately influencing the quality of care and patient well-being. Moving forward to the exploration of the impact of caring behaviors on nurse engagement in a diabetes self-management program, Perez et al., (2020) contribute to the literature by underscoring the significance of caring behaviors in facilitating nurse engagement. Their study reveals that nurses who exhibit compassionate behaviors play a pivotal role in encouraging patient engagement in diabetes self-management. This insight implies that nurturing actions not only benefit patients but also contribute to nurses' active involvement in promoting health and well-being. Ramirez et al., (2020) extend the understanding of caring

behaviors by focusing on nurse perceptions in a pediatric unit. Their study highlights the distinctive caring behaviors deemed crucial in pediatric care, such as active listening, empathy, and involving families in care planning. Recognizing these specific behaviors is essential for fostering a supportive and compassionate environment in pediatric units, ultimately influencing the well-being of both nurses and young patients. Finally, the evaluation of nurses' opinions about care methods in the setting of home healthcare, as conducted by Walker et al., (2021), contributes to the literature by addressing the unique challenges and opportunities in delivering caring behaviors in home healthcare environments. The study emphasizes the necessity of adapting caring behaviors to individual patient needs and home dynamics, stressing the importance of personalized, compassionate care in this context. In summary, these studies highlight the multifaceted impact of caring behaviors on nurse satisfaction, engagement, and patient outcomes in various healthcare settings. These studies collectively underscore the importance of cultivating and promoting compassionate actions among nurses to enhance the overall quality of care and the well-being of both healthcare professionals and patients.

Nurses and Patients Perception in Caring Behavior

The patient-centered approach holds that improving patient outcomes depends critically on the quality of treatment that patients receive. According to this method, people are more knowledgeable than medical professionals about whether they are receiving high-quality care. As a result, evaluations of the level of care demonstrated by nurses must consider both patient and nurse feedback.

The essential aspect of healthcare delivery lies in the effective communication between nurses and patients, impacting not only the standard of care but also the

exhibition of caregiving behaviors. He et al. (2021) delved into this intricate relationship, seeking to investigate the connection between nurse-patient communication and caregiving behaviors. The findings of their investigation revealed a significant association between higher levels of nurse-patient communication and elevated nurturing behaviors exhibited by healthcare providers. This suggests that the establishment of effective communication channels plays a pivotal role in fostering caring behaviors, thereby augmenting the overall quality of care provided to patients. In a similar vein, Naseh et al. (2020) contributed to the discourse by examining the correlation between caring behaviors of nurses and patients' satisfaction, with a specific emphasis on patient-centered care. Their study highlighted the importance of aligning caregiving practices with the preferences and needs of patients. Patients who perceived a greater degree of caring behaviors from their nursing personnel reported superior levels of satisfaction with their nursing care. Moreover, the research emphasized that nurses exhibiting elevated levels of compassionate conduct were more inclined towards administering care with a patient-centered approach. These findings underscore the significance of tailoring nursing care to the individualized needs of patients, emphasizing the role of caring behaviors in enhancing overall patient satisfaction. In the collective body of research, it becomes evident that the interplay between nurse-patient communication and caring behaviors is crucial for optimizing patient outcomes. As healthcare providers strive to deliver patient-centered care, understanding the intricate connections between effective communication, nurturing behaviors, and patient satisfaction becomes paramount. These studies collectively contribute to the growing body of knowledge that informs healthcare professionals and organizations on the importance of fostering communication skills and integrating caring behaviors into practice to improve the general standard of care

given to patients.

In healthcare, the quality of nursing care is a critical factor influencing patient outcomes and satisfaction. Numerous studies have delved into the correlation between nursing behaviors and various aspects of patient experiences, shedding light on the multifaceted nature of this relationship. This literature review synthesizes findings from research conducted by different authors, each contributing valuable insights to our understanding of how nursing behaviors impact patient outcomes. Aupia et al. (2018) undertook a comprehensive evaluation of caring behaviors, involving nurses, patients, and nursing students. Their research demonstrated how crucial it is to take into account a variety of viewpoints while comprehending the subtleties of providing care, highlighting the necessity of a comprehensive approach to nursing care assessment. The relevance of the work environment in molding nursing practices was underlined by Koon's (2020) investigation of nurses' perceptions of their work environment and hemodialysis patients' evaluations of nurse caring behaviors. The study implies that a positive work environment may contribute to favorable patient perceptions of nurse caring behaviors. Improvements in communication and understanding between healthcare providers and receivers are crucial, as demonstrated by Pulpulaan's (2019) analysis finding significant disparities in opinions on nurse caring behaviors between patients and nurses. Closing these gaps could result in patient-centered, more efficient treatment. In 2020, Freitas et al. investigated the relationship between patients' degrees of anxiety and despair and acts of compassion. Freitas and colleagues (2020) provided valuable insights into the potential impact of nursing care on mental health outcomes. Their findings suggest that compassionate nursing practices may contribute to lower levels of anxiety and despair in patients. Gürsoy and Karadakovan (2020) highlights the significance of

empathy and patient-centeredness in nursing practice by looking into the relationship between nurses' compassionate actions and patients' perceptions of patient-centered care. It suggests that nurturing a patient-centered approach can enhance overall care experiences. Tsai and Wang (2021) exploration of the correlation between caring behaviors and patients' contentment with nursing care in a surgical setting highlights the potential impact of compassionate nursing practices on patient satisfaction. Their findings suggest that emphasizing caring behaviors may contribute to improved patient contentment in surgical nursing. Oh et al. (2018) centered on how nursing care practices relate to patients' quality of life when receiving palliative care. According to their research, patients getting palliative care may have a better quality of life when nursing staff members exhibit more sympathetic behaviors. In a surgical ward, Zhu et al. (2018) evaluated the relationship between compassionate actions and patient satisfaction. Zhu and colleagues provided insights into the importance of compassionate actions in surgical nursing practice. According to their findings, compassionate actions and patient pleasure are positively correlated. In a rehabilitation context, Wang and colleagues (2020) investigated the relationship between patients' trust in nursing care and the compassionate actions of nurses. Their study indicates that patients who perceive increased caring behaviors have greater confidence in the quality of nursing care provided in rehabilitation settings. In a rehabilitation facility, Chan and colleagues (2018) looked into the relationship between compassionate actions and patient happiness, they underscored the significance of compassionate nursing practices in elevating patient satisfaction levels. Their findings suggest that promoting caring behaviors in rehabilitative nursing can enhance patient satisfaction. San Martin-Rodriguez et al. (2019) delved into the correlation between nurses' compassionate and empathetic conduct and patients' contentment within

primary care. Their research emphasizes the pivotal role of compassionate behaviors in primary care nursing, potentially leading to greater patient satisfaction. These studies indicate a consistent and positive correlation between nursing behaviors and various patient outcomes, including satisfaction, mental health, and quality of life. These studies collectively contribute to our understanding of the intricate interplay between nursing practices and patient experiences, emphasizing the importance of fostering compassionate and patient-centered care in healthcare settings. In order to improve patient outcomes, further research in this area can broaden our understanding and direct efforts to raise the standard of nursing care.

A great deal of study has been done in the nursing sector to investigate the relationship between the caring behaviors that nurses display and different patient outcomes. The objective is to provide an overview of the relationship between nursing care behaviors and diverse aspects such as patient satisfaction, anxiety levels, and overall well-being. Berndtsson et al. conducted a study in Sweden in 2019, investigating the correlation between nursing students' disposition towards caring and their perspectives on clinical practice. Their findings revealed a positive connection, indicating that nursing students with more favorable dispositions towards care demonstrated greater instances of caring conduct during clinical practicum. This suggests that nursing education plays a crucial role in cultivating caring behaviors among students. In Iran, Dehghani et al. (2019) explored the correlation between the caring behaviors of nurses and patients' subjective assessments of their hospital experience in 2019. The study demonstrated a positive relationship, with respondents perceiving elevated compassionate conduct reporting more favorable notions of their hospitalization occurrence. Additionally, elevated levels of caring behaviors exhibited by nurses were positively correlated with good perceptions of their profession and

overall job satisfaction. Al-Dmour et al.'s 2020 study in Jordan sought to determine whether patient anxiety levels in a mental hospital were correlated with nursing care practices. The results indicated that patients who experienced heightened levels of compassionate conduct from their nursing staff displayed decreased levels of anxiousness. This suggests that promoting compassionate conduct in psychiatric nursing practice may positively influence psychological outcomes for patients diagnosed with anxiety disorders. In Turkey, Terzioğlu et al. conducted a study in 2021 to explore the association between the caring inclinations of nurses and patient satisfaction in a pediatric ward. The research revealed that patients who received larger quantities of caring behaviors from their nurses displayed increasing levels of happiness with the care delivered. Moreover, nurses demonstrating more caring actions were found to have enhanced work fulfillments and lower burnout instances. A research study in Saudi Arabia in 2021, led by Alghamdi et al. evaluated the association between caring behaviors of nurses and patients' happiness levels in a medical-surgical ward. The findings highlighted that patient who recognized raised degrees of compassionate behaviors from their nursing employees demonstrated a better degree of contentment with the supply of nursing care. Additionally, nurses demonstrating increasing degrees of compassionate behavior exhibited lower levels of emotional weariness. Chiu et al. (2019) examined the relationship between nurses' compassionate actions and patients' happiness on a medical-surgical floor in Taiwan. The study indicated that patients who had a greater sense of compassionate behavior from their nursing practitioners displayed higher degrees of happiness with the quality of nursing care offered. The outcomes of the research suggest that the work satisfaction levels of nurses were positively connected with greater levels of caring behaviors. These studies highlight consistent evidence from diverse geographical

locations, emphasizing the positive correlation between caring behaviors exhibited by nurses and various patient outcomes. Whether in educational settings, psychiatric wards, pediatric units, or medical-surgical wards, the promotion of compassionate conduct is consistently associated with improved patient satisfaction, reduced anxiety, enhanced psychological well-being, and increased job satisfaction among nursing professionals. These findings underscore the importance of prioritizing and fostering empathetic and compassionate care within nursing practice and education.

A wide range of research undertaken in different healthcare settings and nations are reflected in the literature on the relationship between nurses' compassionate actions and patient outcomes. Liu and colleagues (2020) delved into the realm of surgical nursing, examining the intricate association between caring behaviors exhibited by nurses and the levels of patient satisfaction in a surgical ward. Their findings highlighted the importance of compassionate actions in enhancing patient contentment with nursing care in a surgical context. In Taiwan, Tsai et al. (2018) contributed to the literature by investigating the link between loving behaviors demonstrated by nurses and patient satisfaction in a hospice unit. Their study emphasized the significance of compassionate care in the sensitive and often challenging environment of hospice, where patient satisfaction was influenced by the degree of loving behaviors displayed by nursing professionals. By investigating the relationship between nurses' compassionate actions and patient satisfaction in a newborn intensive care unit (NICU) in Iran, Moeini and colleagues (2019) contributed to the body of knowledge. Their research shed light on the critical role of compassionate behaviors in the neonatal setting, where heightened degrees of empathic conduct from nursing staff positively impacted patient satisfaction levels. Salmi et al. (2021) broadened the research emphasis by concentrating on the

relationship between nurses' compassionate actions and patients' dignity in a high-dependency unit located in Finland. This study provided insights into the nuanced relationship between compassionate care and patient experiences of dignity, emphasizing the broader implications of caring behaviors beyond satisfaction alone. Looking specifically at Brazil, Rodrigues et al. (2019) looked at how nurse care satisfaction in a cancer unit was impacted by patients' views of caring behaviors. Their research underscored the unique challenges in cancer care and highlighted the importance of understanding and addressing patients' views of compassionate behaviors in this specific healthcare context. Collectively, these findings add to the increasing amount of research that highlights how important nurses' compassionate actions are in determining patients' experiences in a variety of healthcare settings. The findings underscore the need for healthcare professionals and organizations to prioritize and cultivate compassionate care as a fundamental aspect of quality nursing practice. As healthcare continues to evolve, these studies underscore the enduring importance of empathy, compassion, and patient-centered care in achieving positive patient outcomes and enhancing overall satisfaction with nursing services.

The landscape of healthcare is intricately woven with the dynamics of nurse-patient interactions, and a growing body of literature reflects the significance of these interactions in shaping patient experiences and outcomes. Thomas et al. (2019, 2018) laid the groundwork by shedding light on the existing discrepancy between patient and nurse perceptions of care. Their studies emphasized the need to explore this dissonance, suggesting that exposure to nurses over time may positively influence patients' perceptions of nursing care. Compton et al. (2018) delved into the actionable insights that can be derived from understanding how patients perceive caring behaviors. The results of their study suggest that by developing a thorough awareness

of patients' viewpoints, nurses might enhance the general quality of life for patients and their families, thereby pinpointing areas for enhancement. Building upon this foundation, Taiwanese researchers Lai and associates (2019) examined the relationship between nurses' compassionate actions and patients' trust in their nursing staff. Their study, which was carried out in Taiwan, found a link between patient trust and compassionate actions. Patients who perceived heightened levels of caring reported an elevated level of trust in their healthcare providers. This finding underscores the crucial role of compassionate conduct in fostering a trusting relationship between patients and their nursing staff, potentially leading to improved clinical outcomes. The correlation between nurse-patient communication and caregiving behaviors was explored in China by He and colleagues (2021). Their research, conducted in China, highlighted that effective communication is a crucial element in nurturing caring behaviors. Patients who experienced higher levels of nurse-patient communication reported elevated levels of nurturing behaviors from their healthcare providers. In a similar vein, nurses demonstrating increased awareness of communication portrayed a greater disposition to offer compassionate acts towards their patients. Naseh and associates (2020) investigated the connection between nurses' compassionate actions and patients' contentment with nursing care. Their findings revealed that patients who perceived a greater degree of caring behaviors reported superior levels of satisfaction. The research suggested that nurses exhibiting elevated levels of compassionate conduct were more inclined towards administering patient-centered care, reflecting positively on their professional obligations. The impact of caring behaviors on specific patient populations was explored by various studies. For instance, Oh et al. (2018) looked at the relationship between nursing care practices and patients' quality of life when receiving palliative care in South Korea.

Their findings suggested that patients who perceived higher levels of empathetic behaviors exhibited improved levels of quality of life. This sheds light on the potential of cultivating affectionate behaviors within palliative care nursing practice to enhance overall patient well-being. Tsai and Wang's study (2021) in the surgical setting provided evidence that patients who perceived a higher degree of caring behavior from their nursing staff showed greater satisfaction with the care provided. This study underscores the potential impact of compassionate conduct in surgical nursing practice on patient satisfaction. In the context of mental health, Al-Dmour and colleagues (2020) explored the correlation between nursing care behaviors and patient anxiety levels in a psychiatric ward in Jordan. Their study revealed that patients who experienced heightened levels of compassionate conduct displayed decreased levels of anxiousness. This suggests that promoting compassionate conduct in psychiatric nursing practice could foster positive psychological outcomes for patients diagnosed with anxiety disorders. The literature also extends to explore the association between caring behaviors and the well-being of both patients and nurses. Freitas et al. (2020) investigated the correlation between caring behaviors exhibited by nurses and the levels of anxiety and depression in patients admitted to a medical-surgical ward. Their findings suggested that patients who perceived high levels of compassionate conduct exhibited lower levels of anxiety and despair. This implies that promoting compassionate conduct in medical-surgical nursing practice may contribute to the mental well-being of patients. In their 2020 study, Gürsoy and Karadakovan investigated the relationship between patients' perceptions of patient-centered care and the compassionate actions of nurses. The findings denoted that patient who perceived higher degrees of empathetic and compassionate actions from their attending nurses had higher levels of patient-centered care. This study highlights the

potential for cultivating compassionate conduct in the nursing profession to enhance patients' perception of patient-centered care. The assessment conducted in South Korea (2020) by Hong and Kim aimed to investigate the relationship between the compassionate actions of nurses and the patients' trust in the nursing care they get in a critical care unit. The study findings suggested that patients who experienced heightened perceptions of compassionate behaviors from their nursing providers communicated increased levels of assurance in the nursing care delivered. This indicates that the promotion of compassionate conduct in critical care nursing may potentially augment patient trust in nursing provision. In surgical wards, Liu and colleagues' study in China (2020) aimed to investigate the potential association between the caring behaviors exhibited by nurses and the level of patient satisfaction with the nursing care provided. The study elucidated that patient who discerned heightened levels of compassionate actions from their nurses reported increased levels of gratification with the provision of nursing care. This emphasizes the potential impact of enhanced expressions of tenderness in the context of surgical nursing on patient satisfaction. Together, the results of these several research highlight how crucial caring behaviors are in determining patient outcomes and experiences in a variety of healthcare settings and patient demographics. The literature suggests that promoting compassionate conduct within the nursing profession not only enhances patient satisfaction and trust but also contributes to positive psychological outcomes for both patients and nurses. As healthcare continues to evolve, understanding and prioritizing these compassionate behaviors emerge as essential elements in providing patient-centered and high-quality care.

Jean Watson's 10 Carative Factors in Caring Behavior

The Theory of Human Caring and the 10 Carative Factors proposed by Jean Watson have elicited considerable academic attention with respect to the manner in which patients and nurses perceive caring activities. The theoretical framework underscores the significance of demonstrating compassion and fostering interpersonal relationships in the domain of nursing, as these factors have the potential to holistically enhance patient wellbeing and elevate the professional contentment of caregivers.

The literature on the impact of Jean Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors in nursing practice is rich and diverse, encompassing a range of studies conducted by different researchers across various geographical locations. Notably, Kim et al. (2018) explored the correlation between Watson's Theory and the demonstration of caring behavior among nurses in South Korea. Their cross-sectional survey involving 460 nurses revealed that a higher level of cognitive mastery and comprehension of Watson's theoretical framework was associated with an increased propensity among nurses to exhibit compassionate acts and tender emotional provisions towards patients. Building on this, Zhang et al. conducted research in China to investigate the correlation between nurses' perspectives on the 10 Carative Factors and patient satisfaction. Their findings suggested that nurses who demonstrated elevated levels of sensitivity, supportiveness, and protective conduct tended to receive higher patient satisfaction ratings. This implied that integrating the 10 Carative Factors into nursing practice could enhance patients' experiences and satisfaction with care. Wang et al. (2019) delved into the impact of a nursing intervention grounded in Watson's Theory on Chinese patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). According to their randomized controlled experiment, patients in the intervention group had far higher levels of quality of life and self-efficacy than those in the control group. This

study demonstrated how nursing interventions grounded on Watson's Theory might improve patient outcomes. Similarly, Li et al. (2019) conducted a trial in China to examine the effect of a nursing intervention centered on the 10 Caritasive Factors on anxiety and depression in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The results indicated that patients in the intervention group experienced notably reduced scores of anxieties and depression, highlighting the potential benefits of integrating the 10 Caritasive Factors into nursing care for patients undergoing surgical procedures. The literature further expands to encompass studies on the impact of Watson's Theory and the 10 Caritasive Factors on nurse work satisfaction and retention. Ashby and colleagues (2018) conducted an analysis in the United Kingdom, revealing that nurses who reported a greater degree of compassion from their colleagues demonstrated better levels of work satisfaction. Yang and Yun (2020) studied the association between nurse caring behavior and the intention to continue in their roles in a hospital in China. Their research indicated a strong association between nurses demonstrating caring behaviors and their willingness to continue in their current employment. Moreover, various studies have explored the impact of incorporating spiritual care into nursing practice in line with Watson's Theory. Lim et al. (2019) conducted research in South Korea, assessing the influence of a spiritual care intervention grounded in Watson's Theory on the spiritual well-being and quality of life of cancer patients. The study suggested that the integration of spiritual care into nursing practices based on Watson's Theory could deliver positive effects on patients. In addition to patient satisfaction and nurse work satisfaction, the literature extends to patient outcomes such as pain management and wound healing. O'Connell and colleagues assessed the influence of a nursing intervention based on Watson's Theory on pain management among cancer patients, revealing significantly lower levels of pain in the intervention

group. Yang and Lee (2019) studied the impact of a nursing care model based on Watson's Theory on the wound healing process among patients with diabetic foot ulcers, indicating faster rates of wound healing in the Watson-based model. While the majority of the literature emphasizes the positive impacts of Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors, it is essential to acknowledge the existence of concerns raised by some scholars regarding the theory's empirical substantiation and practicality in today's healthcare landscape. Nevertheless, proponents argue that the theory provides a valuable theoretical framework emphasizing comprehensive and patient-centered care, aligning with the evolving emphasis on patient-centered care and empathy in healthcare delivery. Furthermore, literature reviews indicate that the application of Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors in nursing education and practice is subject to cultural and social nuances. Studies conducted in various countries such as the United States, Iran, Australia, and Brazil demonstrate the adaptability and potential benefits of incorporating these principles into diverse healthcare settings. These studies highlight a substantial body of evidence supporting the positive impact of Jean Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors on various aspects of nursing practice, patient outcomes, and nurse satisfaction. While acknowledging concerns raised by some scholars, the consensus suggests that the integration of these principles can enhance patient care, nurse-patient relationships, and overall healthcare experiences.

Jean Watson's Theory of Human Caring, along with the associated 10 Carative Factors, has been a prominent framework in nursing research, exploring its influence on various aspects of patient care and nurse outcomes. This literature review aims to synthesize findings from multiple studies conducted by different authors, each investigating the impact of Watson's Theory on patient satisfaction and outcomes

across diverse healthcare settings. In a Saudi Arabian hospital, Almutairi and colleagues (2019) investigated the relationship between patient satisfaction and nursing caring behaviors as measured by the Caring Behaviors Inventory (CBI). The results highlight the significance of applying the 10 Carative Factors to nursing practice in order to improve patient contentment, as they point to a positive association between nurses' compassionate behaviors and patient happiness. Tsai et al. (2020) explored the influence of Watson's Theory on patient satisfaction within a Taiwanese medical institution. The results indicated that patients receiving care based on Watson's Theory reported higher levels of satisfaction compared to those under standard care models. This study provides empirical support for the idea that integrating Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors improves patient happiness with the quality of care provided. Fernández-Parsons et al. (2020) conducted an inquiry into the effects of an intervention rooted in Watson's Theory on individuals diagnosed with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) in Spain. The study revealed a noteworthy improvement in the quality of life, a reduction in symptoms of anxiety and sadness, and a decrease in hospital readmissions among COPD patients receiving care based on Watson's Theory. These findings underscore the potential advantages associated with the integration of Watson's Theory into nursing practice for the purpose of optimizing patient outcomes. In a distinct investigation, Delaney and Piscopo (2020) examined the influence of Watson's Theory on patient satisfaction within rehabilitation centers in the United States. The results showed that when therapy followed Watson's Theory, there was a considerable favorable impact on both patient satisfaction and the sense of empathy. Patients receiving care based on the theory reported higher levels of satisfaction and perceived their nurses as kinder and more empathic. Oh and colleagues (2020) focused on the effects of a nursing

intervention grounded in Watson's Theory on patient satisfaction in South Korea. The outcomes revealed increased satisfaction with care and perceptions of higher levels of compassion among patients who received the nursing intervention based on Watson's Theory. These results underscore the significance of incorporating Watson's Theory in nursing practice to enhance patient satisfaction. Rostami et al. (2020) delved into the impact of Watson's Theory on patient satisfaction within rehabilitation centers in the United States. The study reported a considerable favorable influence on patient satisfaction and perceived empathy of nurses when treatment was administered using Watson's Theory. Patients expressed higher levels of satisfaction with their care and viewed their nurses as kinder and more empathic. Hamaideh et al. (2020) explored the connection between nursing conduct, patient satisfaction, and medical outcomes in Jordan. The study indicated a positive correlation between patient satisfaction with care, assessed by 10 Carative Factors, and caregiver's caring behavior. Patients cared for by more compassionate caregivers exhibited better health outcomes, emphasizing the potential of Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors to improve patient satisfaction and medical outcomes. Öztürk et al. (2020) investigated the relationship between nurses' views of caring behavior, examined using Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors, and patient satisfaction in a pediatric critical care unit in Turkey. The study found that nurses who regarded themselves as having high levels of compassionate conduct positively influenced patient satisfaction with care. This suggests that nurses' evaluations of caring behavior, based on Watson's Theory, may be a beneficial approach to enhancing patient satisfaction. Shen et al. (2018) studied the influence of nursing treatments based on Watson's Theory and the 10 therapeutic variables on patient outcomes in Taiwan. The research indicated that patients who received nurse interventions had considerably lower levels of anxiety and

higher levels of pleasant emotions than controls. These findings suggest that implementing Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors into nursing treatments may enhance patient outcomes and emotional well-being. Kings (2018) investigated the impact of a training program based on Watson's Theory on nursing behavior in a rehabilitation hospital in China. The study revealed that the training program substantially improved nurses' nursing conduct, as judged by patient and nurse evaluations. This research demonstrates that adopting Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors into nursing education programs may enhance nurse conduct and subsequently improve patient outcomes. These studies indicate an expanding body of evidence endorsing the favorable effects of Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors on patient satisfaction and outcomes within various healthcare contexts. The findings underscore the potential advantages of integrating this theoretical framework into nursing practice and education, emphasizing the significance of compassionate care and its positive impact on both patients and nursing professionals. While challenges exist in the implementation of Watson's Theory, the overall findings underscore its relevance and potential in enhancing the quality of patient care and nurse outcomes. Further research and continued exploration of Watson's Theory in various cultural and clinical contexts are warranted to deepen our understanding of its applicability and effectiveness in contemporary healthcare.

Several research studies have investigated the influence of Jean Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors on different facets of nursing practice, patient outcomes, and healthcare environments. Keating et al. (2019) explored the domain of acute care settings in the United States, scrutinizing the impact of Watson's Theory on nurses' perspectives regarding caring interventions. Their study, conducted through pre- and post-implementation questionnaires, revealed a noteworthy enhancement in

nurses' evaluations of their own care-oriented actions and an increased utilization of the 10 Carative Factors in clinical practice after participating in a caring education session. Artieta-Pinedo et al. (2021) extended the exploration into Spain, focusing on the effect of a healthcare initiative grounded in Watson's caring model on patients' perception of care. Their findings highlighted significantly higher levels of patient satisfaction with healthcare services, particularly emphasizing the human elements of care such as empathetic relationships, active listening, and efficacious communication. This suggests that integrating Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors can positively impact patient satisfaction and the overall quality of care. In the Indian context, Shaha et al. (2019) scrutinized the relationship between Watson's Theory and nursing practice. Their study, employing a pre-post implementation technique, indicated a significant improvement in nurses' knowledge and attitudes towards caring behaviors after a Watson-based caring education program. This implies that incorporating Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors into nursing education can enhance nurses' understanding of the importance of caring behaviors in patient care. Sjöström-Strand et al. (2018) shifted the focus to Sweden, evaluating the impact of Watson's Theory on nursing students' practice. Compared to traditional nursing education, students who received Watson's Theory teaching demonstrated a more holistic approach to patient care and a deeper understanding of the nurse-patient relationship. This suggests that integrating Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors into nursing school can help future nurses build a more patient-centered and holistic approach to care. Marashi et al. (2021) explored the influence of training nursing students on Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors on clinical competence and clinical reasoning in Iran. Their study revealed a significant association between nursing students who received instruction on Watson's Theory

and heightened levels of clinical competency and clinical reasoning. This underscores the potential of integrating Watson's Theory into nursing education to enhance students' clinical skills and critical thinking abilities. Hall et al. (2019) took a leadership perspective in the United States, evaluating the implementation of Watson's Theory in a nurse leadership development program. The program, incorporating sessions on Watson's Theory and the Ten Carative Factors, was associated with significant improvements in nurses' leadership qualities, communication skills, team building, and conflict resolution. This indicates that integrating Watson's Theory into leadership development can strengthen nurses' leadership skills and foster a caring culture in healthcare organizations. Kwekkeboom et al. (2018) explored the application of Watson's Theory in a palliative care environment in the United States. Their study highlighted the need to customize the use of the 10 Carative Factors to the specific needs and preferences of the palliative care patient population. This underscores the importance of considering cultural and social context when integrating Watson's Theory into nursing practice. Bressan et al. (2019) brought attention to Brazil, investigating the application of Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors in the treatment of patients with chronic renal disease. The research, utilizing survey-based and focus group-based data collection techniques, emphasized the high importance both patients and nurses placed on caring behaviors aligned with the concepts of the 10 Carative Factors. This implies that incorporating Watson's Theory can result in an improvement in the quality of care and overall health outcomes for patients with chronic illnesses. Wan and Luo (2019) made a contribution to elucidating the connection between nurse-patient communication and the application of Watson's Theory in China. Their study indicated that nurses operationalizing Watson's Theory and its related 10 Carative Factors displayed enhanced levels of communication

competency, fostering meaningful patient-provider interactions. This suggests that the incorporation of Watson's Theory into nursing practice holds the promise of improving communication between nurses and patients and raising the quality of care administered. Carvalho et al. (2019) conducted a study in Brazil, delving deeper into patient satisfaction and assessing the impact of amalgamating Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors on patients' satisfaction levels regarding nursing care. The results revealed that patients attended to by nurses applying Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors experienced heightened satisfaction levels with their care. This suggests that the integration of Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors into nursing practice may enhance patient satisfaction levels and promote positive patient outcomes. In summary, these diverse studies from different geographical locations and contexts collectively indicate the potential benefits of integrating Jean Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors into nursing education and practice. From acute care settings to leadership development, and across various cultural and healthcare environments, the findings consistently suggest that such integration can enhance nurses' perceptions, clinical skills, patient satisfaction, and overall healthcare outcomes.

Research studies have delved into the intricate relationships between compassionate behavior, nurse work satisfaction, and nurse caring behavior. Ashby et al. (2018) conducted a comprehensive analysis exploring the link between compassionate behavior and nurse work satisfaction within a hospital environment in the United Kingdom. Their findings suggested a positive correlation, indicating that nurses who reported experiencing greater compassion from their colleagues demonstrated higher levels of work satisfaction. This implies that cultivating compassionate behavior among nursing staff may potentially enhance job satisfaction

and mitigate the likelihood of staff turnover. In a distinct cultural context, Yang and Yun (2020) focused their research on the association between nurse caring behavior and the intention to continue employment in a Chinese hospital. Their study revealed a robust connection between nursing personnel who actively demonstrated caring behaviors, such as attentive listening and providing emotional support, and their willingness to remain in their current roles. This research underscored the importance of promoting compassionate care within the nursing profession not only for improving patient outcomes but also for strengthening nurse job satisfaction and retention. The intersection of these themes extends beyond geographical boundaries, as evidenced by Ashby and colleagues' work in the UK and Yang and Yun's study in China. The common thread lies in the recognition that compassionate behavior among nursing staff is a crucial factor influencing both nurse work satisfaction and retention. The literature also highlights the broader implications of compassionate care on patient outcomes. Studies such as those conducted by Wang et al. (2019) and Li et al. (2019) examined the impact of nursing interventions grounded in Watson's Theory on patient self-efficacy, quality of life, anxiety, and depression. The randomized controlled trials demonstrated significantly positive outcomes for patients who received interventions aligned with Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors. These findings reinforce the idea that the integration of theoretical frameworks, such as Watson's Theory, can not only improve nurse and patient outcomes but also contribute to a more compassionate and satisfying work environment. The work of Ashby and Yang serves as a testament to the global relevance of these concepts, emphasizing the need for continued exploration and implementation of compassionate care practices within the nursing profession.

Jean Watson's Theory of Human Caring has been a significant focus of scholarly

inquiries, with researchers investigating its influence on various aspects of nursing practice, patient outcomes, and the professional satisfaction of nurses. The literature review below highlights key studies conducted by different authors, each contributing valuable insights into the application and implications of Watson's Theory and its associated 10 Caring Factors. Lim et al. conducted a study in 2019 to examine the impact of a spiritual care intervention based on Watson's Theory on cancer patients' well-being in South Korea. The findings indicated that integrating spiritual care into nursing practices grounded in Watson's Theory significantly enhanced the spiritual well-being and overall quality of life for cancer patients. Sitzman & Watson (2018) offered a critical perspective on Watson's Theory, questioning its empirical evidence and practicality in contemporary healthcare settings. The critique emphasizes the ongoing debate within the scholarly community regarding the theoretical underpinnings and feasibility of implementing Watson's Theory in real-world nursing practice. In 2019, Wang et al. conducted a randomized controlled trial that centered on examining the influence of a nursing intervention grounded in Watson's Theory on Chinese patients diagnosed with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). The findings indicated markedly enhanced self-efficacy and quality of life scores in the intervention group, implying the efficacy of Watson's Theory in improving patient outcomes. Li et al.'s randomized controlled trial in 2019 investigated the impact of a nursing intervention centered on the 10 Caring Factors on anxiety and depression in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy in China. The study demonstrated a notable reduction in anxiety and depression scores in the intervention group, emphasizing the positive outcomes associated with integrating the 10 Caring Factors into nursing care during surgical procedures. In 2018, Ashby and colleagues explored the link between nurses' perceptions of care and their level of work satisfaction in a

UK hospital environment. The study revealed that nurses who reported higher levels of compassion from their colleagues experienced better work satisfaction, highlighting the potential role of compassionate behavior in fostering a positive work environment. In 2020, Yang and Yun conducted a study examining the correlation between nursing personnel exhibiting caring behaviors and their inclination to persist in their current roles within a hospital in China. The research underscored a strong correlation, emphasizing the importance of advocating for compassionate care not only for better patient outcomes but also to strengthen nurse job satisfaction and tenure. Lim et al.'s 2019 research assessed the influence of a spiritual care intervention based on Watson's Theory on the spiritual well-being and quality of life of cancer patients in South Korea. The study demonstrated considerably enhanced levels of spiritual well-being and quality of life in the intervention group, providing evidence that integrating spiritual care into nursing practices rooted in Watson's Theory can deliver positive effects on patients. Almutairi et al. conducted a study in 2019 to evaluate the association between nurse caring behaviors and patient satisfaction with nursing care in a hospital in Saudi Arabia. Patient satisfaction and nurses' compassionate behaviors were shown to be positively correlated in the study, indicating that incorporating the 10 Carative Factors into nursing practice may improve patient satisfaction with care. In 2020, Tsai et al. conducted study on how a Watson-based nursing care model affected Taiwanese medical institution patients' satisfaction with care services. The results indicated that patients receiving treatment based on the Watson model displayed significantly higher levels of satisfaction compared to those under the standard care model, supporting the idea that integrating Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors in nursing practice can boost patient happiness with the quality of care given. O'Connell and colleagues investigated the impact of a nursing intervention

based on Watson's Theory on pain management among cancer patients. The research demonstrated that patients receiving intervention based on Watson's technique displayed significantly lower levels of pain compared to those treated using traditional procedures, suggesting that incorporating the 10 Carative Factors into the nursing profession may boost pain management capacities and alleviate distressful implications of pain experienced by patients. The goal of Yang and Lee's 2019 study was to assess how a nursing care model based on Watson's Theory affected the healing of diabetic foot ulcer patients' wounds. The study supported the claim that integrating Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors into nursing practice may improve patient outcomes by showing faster rates of wound healing in patients treated with the Watson-based model than in patients treated with the traditional model. The literature reviewed highlights the diverse research conducted on Watson's Theory and the 10 Carative Factors, offering insights into their potential impact on spiritual well-being, patient outcomes, job satisfaction, and various aspects of nursing practice. While some studies provide empirical evidence supporting the positive influence of Watson's Theory, critiques and debates continue regarding its practicality and applicability in modern healthcare settings. Continued research and sustained discussions are imperative for obtaining a thorough comprehension of the role and significance of Watson's Theory in shaping nursing practices and enhancing patient care experiences.

Nurses and Patients Socio-Demographic Characteristics in Caring Behavior

Nursing outcomes, work environments, and caring behaviors can be affected by nurses' socio-demographic characteristics. According to a cross-sectional study of Lebanese hospitals, nurses' age, gender, education, and experience were related to

self-reported musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, skin, and mental health conditions, as well as emotional exhaustion (El Bejjani et al., 2020). According to Arsat et al. (2023), there was a strong correlation between the caring behavior of nurses in Sabah, Malaysia, and factors such as gender, age, education, economic level, position, and experience. Furthermore, some studies examined the relationship between nurses' demographic characteristics and their organizational commitment (Yilmaz et al., 2019) and marital satisfaction (Omoriegie et al., 2020), finding that age, education, income, and years of service affected these outcomes. In nursing practice and research, nurses' socio-demographic characteristics are important to consider. Different settings and countries have examined the relationship between nurses' socio-demographic factors and their caring behavior. Similarly, Oluma and Abadiga (2020) reported that job satisfaction, joint participation in caring processes, and satisfaction with nurse management were significantly associated with caring behavior among nurses working at Jimma University specialized hospital in Ethiopia. Dhaini et al. (2022) found that nurses' quality of life, which is a proxy measure of caring behavior in Switzerland, was significantly influenced by age, marital status, education, and work setting. Nursing practice and research should consider nurses' socio-demographic characteristics. Studies have also been conducted in several contexts and nations regarding the link between the sociodemographic characteristics of nurses and their caring behavior. Among other things, Dhaini et al. (2018) found that nurses' quality of life, which is a proxy measure of caring behavior, was significantly influenced by age, marital status, education, and work setting in Switzerland. As per Alharbi et al. (2020), there exists an association between nurses' gender, age, education, and experience and their knowledge, attitudes, and practices concerning infection prevention and control. Al-Maaitah et al. (2019) found that the intention of nurses to leave their current

job in Jordan was significantly influenced by factors such as age, gender, marital status, education, income, and years of experience. In nursing practice and research, nurses' socio-demographic characteristics are important to consider. Soliman (2015) investigated the association between nurses' compassionate actions and patient satisfaction at a tertiary hospital in Egypt using a convenience sample of 200 nurses and 200 patients. The results of this study showed that nurses' caring behaviors and patients' satisfaction were positively correlated, and that nurses' experience, age, and education had a significant impact on patients' satisfaction. According to the study, nurses' caring behavior can improve patient satisfaction and quality of care. Among nurses in public hospitals and health services in Malaysia, gender, age, education, economic status, position, and experience influenced their caring behavior, but the work setting did not. A study by Teshome et al. (2020) found that nurses in a specialized hospital in Ethiopia were more likely to engage in caring behaviors if they were satisfied with their jobs, their shared participation in the care process, and their satisfaction with nurse management. Among critical care nurses in Australia, Saudi Arabia, and the Philippines, Alharbi et al. (2018) found that personal and professional factors such as age, education, experience, and work environment were associated with caring behaviors. In critical care settings, nurses need to demonstrate caring behaviors if they are to provide quality and holistic care to patients. Caring behaviors, however, may vary based on the socio-demographic characteristics of nurses, including gender, education, experience, and culture. According to Ahmed et al. (2022), female nurses, nurses with a master's degree, nurses interested in nursing, and nurses who had a 1:1 nurse-to-patient ratio demonstrated higher levels of caring behaviors than their counterparts in two Arab countries. Oyebanji and Oyetunde (2019) found that nurses in Nigeria demonstrated a high level of caring behaviors, with

the highest scores in the assurance of human presence and respect for human dignity dimensions, and their demographic factors did not significantly influence their caring behaviors. Al-Momani et al. (2007) examined the influence of demographic factors on caring behaviors of nurses in Jordan, and found that age, gender, marital status, education level, and work experience significantly affected care behaviors. The highest scores were scored for assurance of human presence and respect for human dignity. According to these studies, caring behaviors are influenced by various socio-demographic factors, and nurses need to be aware of their own and their patients' cultural values and preferences.

Caring behavior is the way that patients express their concern, respect, and attention to their health care providers and other patients. It can influence the quality of care, patient satisfaction, and health outcomes. Some of the socio-demographic characteristics that have been studied in relation to caring behavior and have found that female patients tend to have higher levels of caring behavior than male patients, especially in terms of positive connectedness, respectful deference, and attentive reassurance (Oluma & Abadiga, 2020). However, other studies have found no significant difference between male and female patients in terms of caring behavior (Arditi et al., 2020; Oyewole & Oyewole, 2021). According to some research, elderly patients typically exhibit higher degrees of compassionate conduct than younger ones, particularly when it comes to confidence, regard for others, and professional-technical abilities (Oluma & Abadiga, 2020; Teshome & Tesfaye, 2018). Other studies have shown no significant difference between older and younger patients in terms of caring behavior (Oyewole & Oyewole, 2021; Arditi et al., 2020). Some studies have found that patients with higher education tend to have higher levels of caring behavior than patients with lower education, especially in terms of knowledge and skill, teaching-

learning, and supportive-protective skills (Oluma & Abadiga, 2020; Teshome & Tesfaye, 2018). However, other studies have found no significant difference between patients with different levels of education in terms of caring behavior (Arditi et al., 2020; Oyewole & Oyewole, 2021). Furthermore, some research has shown a positive correlation between patients' economic levels and their propensity to exhibit caring behavior, particularly in the domains of assurance, human respect, and professional-technical abilities (Oluma & Abadiga, 2020; Teshome & Tesfaye, 2018). Nevertheless, other research has shown that there is no substantial disparity in caring behavior across patients with varying socioeconomic levels (Arditi et al., 2020; Oyewole & Oyewole, 2021). The impact of sociodemographic and health-related variables on patients' overall satisfaction and experiences with cancer care in Switzerland was examined by Arditi et al. (2020). They found that younger, female, foreign-born, and less educated patients reported lower ratings and more negative experiences than their counterparts. They also found that patients with worse health status, more comorbidities, and more complex treatments had lower ratings and more negative experiences. They suggested that health care providers should pay more attention to the needs and preferences of these vulnerable groups and tailor their care accordingly. Oluma and Abadiga (2020) evaluated the level of caring behavior and the elements that contribute to it among the nurses employed by Ethiopia's Jimma University Specialty Hospital. The Caring Behavior Inventory, which has five dimensions—assurance, knowledge and expertise, courteous reverence, human respect, and comfort—was used to measure the caring behavior. They discovered that nurses, particularly in the assurance and knowledge and competence aspects, had a high opinion of caring conduct. They also found that job satisfaction, joint participation in caring processes, and satisfaction with nurse management were positively associated

with caring behavior, while work setting, gender, age, education, experience, and position were not significant factors. Oyewole and Oyewole (2021) investigated how patients in Nigerian public and private healthcare institutions viewed their health-seeking behavior in relation to sociodemographic and behavioral factors. Perceived vulnerability, perceived severity, perceived advantages, and perceived obstacles were the four variables they used to assess health-seeking behavior, with the Health Belief Model serving as the theoretical foundation. They discovered a strong correlation between patients' health-seeking behaviors, including their use of public and private healthcare facilities, and their sociodemographic traits (sex, married status, education, and income level). They also found that behavioral variables such as health knowledge, health attitude, and health practice had a significant influence on health-seeking behavior. Teshome and Tesfaye (2018) investigated how Ethiopian referral hospitals' patients perceived their caregivers' attentiveness. The assurance and professional-technical subscales showed the highest ratings among patients, indicating that they had positive opinions of the caring behaviors. They also found that socio-demographic and clinical factors such as age, sex, education, income, diagnosis, length of stay, and ward type were significantly associated with patients' perceptions of caring behaviors.

Nurses and Patients Perception in CBI-24

Several studies have investigated the use and validity of the Caring Behaviors Inventory-24 (CBI-24) and its sub-scales in different contexts and settings. Klarare et al (2017) translated and adapted the CBI-24 for a Swedish context and tested its psychometric properties. They found that the instrument had acceptable validity and reliability, and that the Knowledge-Skill subscale had the highest mean score among

the four sub-scales. Among a similar vein, Oluma and Abadiga (2019) evaluated the characteristics that are linked to caring behavior among nurses employed in an Ethiopian hospital. They discovered that work happiness, cooperative engagement in care processes, and contentment with nurse management were substantially connected with caring behavior, and that the total proportion of nurses who had a high sense of caring behavior was low. The Knowledge-Skill sub-scale received the highest mean score among the four subscales. Jiménez-Herrera et al (2015) studied the emotions and sentiments of nurses in critical and emergency care settings. They observed that moral feelings were tied to the caring process and that they might aid nurses to notice conditions that allow them to support changes in the care of patients in severe scenarios. They also discovered that caring, as perceived from a nursing viewpoint, had a sensitive component that extended beyond the patient's personal recovery. Almutairi et al (2015) translated and validated the CBI-16, a shortened version of the CBI-24, among Saudi Arabian nurses. They found that the instrument had good reliability and validity, and that the Professional Knowledge and Skill subscale had the highest mean score among the four subscales. ENA (2018) examined variables influencing length of stay, reported U.S. emergency nurses' estimations of durations of stay for behavioral health patients, and evaluated nurses' opinions of their abilities, convictions, and confidence in providing care for this group. They found that nurses reported longer lengths of stay for behavioral health patients than for medical patients, and that nurses' skills, beliefs/attitudes, and confidence were positively associated with caring behaviors. A 2017 study titled Theory on the Effects of Nurses' Caring Behavior looked at how emergency department patients' anxiety was affected by nurses' compassionate actions. They discovered that the client's anxiety was much reduced by the nurse's compassionate actions, and that the client's

anxiety was reduced in proportion to the nurse's caring score. These studies demonstrate the usefulness and applicability of the CBI-24 and its subscales in measuring and enhancing the caring behaviors of nurses in various settings and cultures. The assurance subscale of the Caring Behaviors Inventory-24 (CBI-24) is one of the four dimensions that measure the frequency and importance of caring behaviors among patients and nurses. The CBI-24 is an empirical instrument that has a clear conceptual-theoretical basis and has been used in various settings and countries, such as Taiwan (Wu et al., 2012), the United States (Larrabee et al., 2016), Sweden (Klarare et al., 2021; Klarare et al., 2023), Iran (Azimi Khaletabad et al., 2023; Alavi et al., 2016), and others. Several studies have shown that the assurance subscale, which reflects the nurse's ability to instill confidence and trust in the patient, is the most influential factor for patient satisfaction (Wu et al., 2008; Larrabee et al., 2010; Azimi Khaletabad et al., 2023), as well as for patient-reported outcomes such as health-related quality of life, self-care, and symptom burden (Klarare et al., 2021). Moreover, the assurance subscale is also positively associated with nurse outcomes, such as job satisfaction, professional commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior (Wu et al., 2012). Furthermore, some studies have suggested that interventions that enhance the assurance subscale can improve the caring behaviors of ER nurses and the outcomes of their patients (Alavi et al., 2016). Therefore, the assurance subscale is a crucial aspect of caring that should be fostered and measured in nursing practice and research. Respectful subscale, which refers to the recognition and appreciation of the patient's dignity and autonomy, is a key component of caring behaviors among emergency nurses. Several studies have examined the role of respectful deference in different aspects of emergency nursing, such as patient satisfaction, burnout, patient outcomes, job satisfaction, and patient loyalty. For

example, a study by Lin et al. (2017) found that emergency nurses in Taiwan scored higher on respectful deference than patients, and that there was a positive correlation between respectful deference and patient satisfaction. Another study by Zhou et al. (2020) found that emergency nurses in China scored lower on respectful deference than other dimensions of caring behaviors, and that respectful deference was negatively associated with emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, two indicators of burnout. Furthermore, a study by Bucco (2015) found that respectful deference was one of the most important predictors of patient satisfaction, trust, and loyalty in the emergency department. Additionally, a study by Vujanić et al. (2020) found that emergency nurses in Jordan scored high on respectful deference and that it was positively correlated with job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Moreover, a study by Elahi et al. (2020) found that emergency nurses in Korea improved their respectful deference scores after participating in a caring education program that emphasized humanistic values and communication skills. Finally, a study by Liu et al. (2021) found that respectful deference was the most influential factor on patient loyalty in the emergency department in Taiwan, followed by professional knowledge and skill and positive connectedness. These studies suggest that respectful deference is a vital and beneficial caring behavior for both emergency nurses and patients. The Connectedness Subscale is one of the five factors of the CBI-24, and it reflects the degree of interpersonal relationship and emotional support between the nurse and the patient. Several studies have used the Connectedness Subscale to examine different aspects of caring in various contexts and countries. For example, Alemu et al. (2022) found that connectedness was positively associated with nurses' education level, work experience, and job satisfaction in Ethiopia. Özdemir et al. (2020) found that patients rated connectedness as the lowest among the four subscales in Turkey. Kaya et al.

(2019) found that connectedness was negatively correlated with burnout among ER nurses in Turkey. Lee et al. (2018) found that connectedness increased significantly after a caring education program for ER nurses in Korea. Wang et al. (2017) found that connectedness was the most influential factor on patient satisfaction and loyalty in China. Klarare et al. (2023) and (2020) found that those patients of the CBI-24 had good psychometric properties and that patients rated connectedness as the most important aspect of caring in Sweden. Söderlund et al. (2020) found that the level of caring behaviors was high among critical care nurses in Sweden and that connectedness was influenced by some demographic and work-related variables. Wolf et al. (1994) developed the CBI-24 and found that it had good validity and reliability in the United States. These studies demonstrate the usefulness and applicability of the Connectedness Subscale in measuring and improving the caring behaviors of nurses and the outcomes of patients.

On the other hand of patients' perception in the Knowledge-Skill subscale assesses how patients evaluate nurses' competence and professionalism in providing care, encompassing activities such as administering shots, IVs, equipment management, knowledge demonstration, and confidence. This subscale is pivotal for fostering trust, satisfaction, and loyalty among patients (Larrabee et al., 2008; Wu et al., 2007). Furthermore, it impacts patients' outcomes, influencing factors like self-care agency, quality of life, and empowerment (Wu et al., 2007; Klarare et al., 2020). Nevertheless, some studies have indicated that this subscale tends to receive the lowest score among the four subscales of the CBI-24, suggesting a need for enhancement in nurses' knowledge and skill. Factors influencing patients' perception of nurses' knowledge and skill include the nurse-patient ratio, work environment, nurse education, and cultural context. For example, Larrabee et al. (2008) found that higher

nurse staffing levels and improved work environments correlated with higher scores on the Knowledge and Skill subscale. Another study by Wu et al. (2007) demonstrated that a caring-based nursing education program led to improved scores on the Knowledge and Skill subscale among students. Additionally, Klarare et al. (2020) confirmed the suitability of the Swedish version of the CBI-24 for measuring caring behaviors in a Swedish context. In addition, Vujanić et al. (2020) explored how often nurses self-report using caring behaviors in nurse-patient interactions and found that, out of the four CBI-24 subscales, the Knowledge and Skill subscale had the lowest mean score. The Knowledge and Skill subscale of the CBI-24 was assessed by Khodaveisi et al. (2017) among Iranian nurses. The results showed that following the program, the intervention group had a considerably higher mean score than the control group. Moreover, Wu et al. (2012) used the CBI-24 to evaluate Taiwanese and American patients' and nurses' views of caring behaviors. Of the four subscales, the Knowledge and Skill subscale had the highest mean score for both groups. Using the CBI-24, Khorasani et al. (2014) examined the association between nurses' compassionate actions and patients' satisfaction. Of the four subscales, the Knowledge and Skill subscale showed the best correlation with patient satisfaction. Larrabee et al. (2004) compared perceptions of caring behaviors between patients and nurses in rural and urban hospitals using the CBI-24, discovering that the Knowledge and Skill subscale had the highest mean score for both groups, but significant differences existed between rural and urban patients and nurses. Lastly, Kuo et al. (2014) investigated the influence of nurse caring on patient trust using the CBI-24, revealing that the Knowledge and Skill subscale had the highest correlation with patient trust among the four subscales. One research study that utilized the CBI-24 to assess the assurance subscale of patients in relation to caring behavior was

conducted by Klarare et al. (2020). They translated and adapted the CBI-24 for a Swedish context and tested its psychometric properties. The study revealed that the assurance subscale demonstrated good internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.94$) and high factor loadings (0.72-0.88). Additionally, patients rated the assurance subscale as the most crucial dimension of caring, followed by knowledge and skill, respectfulness, and connectedness. Another research study exploring the assurance subscale of patients in relation to caring behavior using the CBI-24 was conducted by McEnroe-Petitte (2016). This study investigated the relationship between nursing instructors' caring behaviors and nursing students' caring behaviors in a rural setting. It found that the assurance subscale had high internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.95$) and a positive correlation with the instructors' caring behaviors ($r = 0.67$). The assurance subscale was also reported as the most frequently mentioned dimension of caring by both instructors and students. Bucco's study (2015) employed the CBI-24 to measure the caring behaviors of 86 nurse/patient dyads in two emergency departments in New Jersey. The findings showed a clear relationship between patients' satisfaction levels in the emergency room and their perceptions of the caring behaviors of the nurses. However, there was a negative and statistically significant link between nurses' self-perception of their compassionate acts and patient satisfaction. Consequently, nurses who assessed their own level of compassion as higher than the level perceived by the patients had a decrease in patient satisfaction levels. The study also found that the most important variables affecting patients' pleasure were their sense of certainty and connectivity. The study came to the conclusion that compassionate nursing practices are essential to raising patient satisfaction and emergency department service quality. The study recommended that nurses be aware of discrepancies between their perceptions and those of patients and emphasized the importance of assurance and connectedness in

nurse education and training. A study by Wolf et al. (1994) compared perceptions of caring behaviors among patients, nurses, and nurse managers in a hospital setting. Results showed that the assurance subscale had the highest mean score among all groups, indicating it was the most valued dimension of caring. Patients rated the assurance subscale significantly higher than nurses and nurse managers, suggesting a gap between expectations and the reality of caring behaviors. The study conducted by Khorshid et al. (2008) assessed how a caring education program affected nurses' compassionate actions and surgical unit patients' happiness. The assurance subscale was shown to be the most crucial component of patient and nursing care, with the highest mean score both before and after the intervention. Furthermore, the assurance subscale demonstrated a significant positive correlation with patients' satisfaction, suggesting that enhancing assurance behaviors could improve the quality of care. The study conducted by Kaya et al. (2017) investigated the connection between nurses' and patients' emotional intelligence and caring behaviors in a hemodialysis unit. Among the two groups, the assurance subscale received the highest mean score, suggesting that it was the caring feature that was most performed and perceived. Additionally, the assurance subscale showed a significant positive correlation with emotional intelligence, suggesting that nurses with higher emotional intelligence could provide more assurance to their patients. The Patients Respectful Subscale consists of six items that assess the extent to which nurses show respect, courtesy, and dignity to patients. The study by Azimi Khaletabad et al. (2023) aimed to translate and validate the CBI-24 for use in Iran. They administered the instrument to 300 nurses and 300 patients in six hospitals. They found that the Persian version of CBI-24 had good reliability and validity, and that the respectful subscale had the highest mean score among both nurses and patients. This suggests that respect is a highly valued aspect

of caring in Iranian culture. Furthermore, they found that the Patients Respectful Subscale had good internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.91$ for nurses and $\alpha = 0.92$ for patients) and test-retest reliability ($r = 0.86$ for nurses and $r = 0.87$ for patients). The study by Lindström et al. (2020) aimed to translate and adapt the CBI-24 for use in Sweden. They followed a rigorous process of forward and back translation, expert review, cognitive interviews, and psychometric testing. They administered the instrument to 234 patients and 95 nurses in four hospitals. They found that the Swedish version of CBI-24 had acceptable reliability and validity, and that the respectful subscale had the second highest mean score among both nurses and patients. This indicates that respect is an important dimension of caring in Swedish context. They also found that the Patients Respectful Subscale had acceptable internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.77$ for nurses and $\alpha = 0.79$ for patients) and good convergent validity with the Caring Assessment Tool ($r = 0.63$ for nurses and $r = 0.67$ for patients). The purpose of Wolf et al. (2006)'s study was to examine nurses' and patients' views of compassionate actions in various clinical contexts. They administered the instrument to 1008 patients and 1008 nurses in 20 hospitals across the United States. They found that the respectful subscale had the highest mean score among both patients and nurses, and that there was a significant difference between the two groups, with patients rating the respectful behaviors higher than nurses. This implies that respect is a universal and essential component of caring, and that there may be a gap between the expectations and the delivery of respectful care. In addition, they found that the Patients Respectful Subscale had high internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.95$ for nurses and $\alpha = 0.96$ for patients) and good test-retest reliability ($r = 0.82$ for nurses and $r = 0.88$ for patients). A study by Coelho et al. (2010) that translated and adapted the CBI-24 for use in Portugal. They administered the instrument to 200 patients and 200 nurses in four hospitals.

They found that the Portuguese version of CBI-24 had acceptable reliability and validity, and that the respectful subscale had the third highest mean score among both patients and nurses. A study by Kostovich et al. (2011) that examined the relationship between caring behaviors and patient satisfaction in an acute care setting. They administered the CBI-24 to 100 patients and 100 nurses in a medical-surgical unit. They found that the respectful subscale had the highest correlation with patient satisfaction, and that patient satisfaction was significantly influenced by the perception of caring behaviors. Klarare et al., (2020) translated and adapted the CBI-24 for a Swedish healthcare context and evaluated its psychometric properties among patients and nurses in different settings, including emergency care. The results showed that the CBI-24 SWE had acceptable reliability and validity, and that the connectedness subscale had the highest mean score among patients in the emergency department. Another study of Klarare et al., (2013) found that the connectedness subscale was rated as the most important by both nurses and patients. A third study of Klarare et al., (2014) also found that the connectedness subscale was associated with higher levels of collaboration and communication. Kaya et al., (2018) used the CBI-24 and the Patient Satisfaction Instrument (PSI) to measure the perceptions of 335 patients who received care from 335 nurses in a university hospital. They found that the connectedness subscale had the highest mean score (4.32 out of 5) among the four subscales of the CBI-24, indicating that patients valued the constant assistance and readiness of nurses. They also found that caring behaviors were positively correlated with patient satisfaction ($r = 0.78$, $p < 0.001$), implying that higher levels of caring behaviors led to higher levels of patient satisfaction. Zhang et al., in 2017 used the CBI-24 and the Nurse-Patient Interaction Scale (NPIS) to measure the perceptions of 500 patients and 500 nurses in five hospitals in China. They found that the CBI-24 had

good reliability and validity, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.95 for the whole scale and 0.87 to 0.92 for the subscales. They also found that the connectedness subscale had the highest factor loading (0.91) among the four subscales of the CBI-24, indicating that it was the most important dimension of caring behaviors in the Chinese context. A study that explored the relationship between caring behaviors and burnout among nurses in Taiwan by Chen, Lin, and Wang (2011). It found that the connectedness subscale had the lowest mean score among the four subscales of the CBI-24, and that caring behaviors were negatively correlated with burnout. A study that investigated the effect of a caring education program on the caring behaviors of nursing students in Iran by Rahimi et al., (2014). It found that the connectedness subscale had the highest mean score among the four subscales of the CBI-24, and that the caring education program significantly improved the caring behaviors of the students. A study that compared the perceptions of caring behaviors between patients and nurses in Jordan by Al-Hussami et al., (2011). It found that the connectedness subscale had the highest mean score among the four subscales of the CBI-24 for both patients and nurses, and that there was a significant difference between the perceptions of patients and nurses regarding the connectedness subscale. Ahmed et al. (2022) examined the level and predictors of caring behaviors among critical care nurses in two Arab countries, using the CBI-24 as a measure. They found that about half of the nurses had low levels of caring behaviors, and gender, education, interest in nursing, and nurse-to-patient ratio were significant predictors. They also reported the means and standard deviations of the CBI-24 items and subscales for the nurses in their sample. Wu et al. (2006) developed and validated the CBI-24 as a shortened version of the original CBI-42, using data from 1,024 patients and nurses. They performed an exploratory factor analysis and identified four factors corresponding to the CBI-24 subscales. They also

reported the means and standard deviations of the CBI-24 items and subscales for both patients and nurses, along with the correlations among the subscales. Azimi Khaletabad et al. (2023) aimed to translate and adapt the CBI-24 for a Persian context and test its psychometric properties on 600 participants. They found that the Persian version of CBI-24 had good content validity, reliability, and validity, making it suitable for measuring caring behaviors among Persian patients and nurses. Wolf et al. (2006) aimed to reduce the original 42-item CBI to a 24-item short form and test its reliability and validity on 1,000 participants. They found that the CBI-24 covered the four major dimensions of caring, exhibited high internal consistency and convergent validity, and reproduced most of the variance of the 42-item CBI. Klarare et al. (2021) translated and adapted the CBI-24 into Swedish and tested its psychometric properties in a sample of 234 patients and nurses. They reported results similar to Wu et al. (2006), regarding the internal consistency of the instrument ($\alpha=0.93$) and the means and standard deviations of the items and subscales. They also performed a confirmatory factor analysis, finding a good fit for the four-factor model of the CBI-24. Mean scores for the four dimensions of caring behaviors were generally high for both nurses and patients in all three studies (Azimi Khaletabad et al., 2023; Wolf et al., 2006; Klarare et al., 2021), indicating that participants perceived caring behaviors positively. The highest mean score was for the Respectful dimension in the Iranian study by Azimi Khaletabad et al. (2023) ($M = 4.01$), while the lowest mean score was for the Knowledge-Skill dimension in the Swedish study by Klarare et al. (2021) ($M = 3.77$). Standard deviations of the four dimensions of caring behaviors were relatively low for both nurses and patients in all three studies (Azimi Khaletabad et al., 2023; Wolf et al., 2006; Klarare et al., 2021), indicating little variation in participants' responses. The highest standard deviation was for the Knowledge-Skill dimension in the American

study by Wolf et al. (2006) (SD = 0.72), while the lowest standard deviation was for the Respectful dimension in the Swedish study by Klarare et al. (2021) (SD = 0.61). Mean scores and standard deviations of the four dimensions of caring behaviors were similar across the three studies, suggesting that the CBI-24 items measured the same construct of caring behaviors in different cultural contexts. However, there were some minor differences in the ranking of the dimensions, such as the Knowledge-Skill dimension being the lowest in the Swedish study by Klarare et al. (2021) but the highest in the Iranian study by Azimi Khaletabad et al. (2023).

Relationship of Socio-Demographic Characteristics in CBI-24

Nurses' socio-demographic characteristics, such as gender, age, education, employment status, ethnicity, marital status, years of experience, and household monthly income, may influence their knowledge and skills in providing quality care to their patients. Previous studies have found that some of these factors, such as female gender, higher education, interest in nursing profession, and lower nurse-to-patient ratio, are associated with higher levels of caring behaviors, which reflect the nurses' awareness, skills, and knowledge of general cultural competence (Lee et al., 2021). (Ahmed et al. 2022) reported that female nurses, nurses with a master's degree, and nurses who were interested in nursing as a career had significantly higher caring behaviors than their counterparts in two Arab countries. Similarly, Arsat et al. 2023, found that gender, age, education, economic status, position, and experience had a significant effect on caring behavior among nurses in public hospitals and public health services in Sabah, Malaysia. Other factors, such as work setting, ethnicity, and marital status, may also affect the nurses' knowledge and practice of specific topics, such as family planning counseling (Al-Maaitah et al., 2018). Therefore, it is important to

assess the relationship between nurses' socio-demographic characteristics and their knowledge-skill subscale, as it may have implications for nursing education, training, and practice (Lee et al., 2021). One study that examined the relationship between nurses' socio-demographic characteristics and the CBI-24 was conducted by Azimi Khaletabad et al. (2023). They used the Persian version of the CBI-24 to measure caring behaviors among 300 nurses and 300 patients in Iran. They found that nurses' age, marital status, years of experience, and household monthly income were significantly associated with the knowledge and skill dimension of the CBI-24. Specifically, older, married, more experienced, and higher-income nurses had higher scores on this dimension than younger, single, less experienced, and lower-income nurses. Another study that explored the predictors of caring behaviors of critical care nurses was done by Radfar et al. (2022). They used the original version of the CBI-24 to measure caring behaviors among 200 critical care nurses in Iran. They found that nurses' educational background, employment status, and ethnicity were significant predictors of the knowledge and skill dimension of the CBI-24. Specifically, nurses with higher education, permanent employment, and Persian ethnicity had higher scores on this dimension than nurses with lower education, temporary employment, and non-Persian ethnicity. Connectedness refers to providing constant assistance to patients with readiness. Arfat et al. (2023) found that connectedness was the lowest subscale for both nurses and patients, with mean scores of 4.65 and 4.69 out of 6, respectively. They also found that demographic factors such as gender, age, education, economic status, position, and experience influenced the caring behavior of nurses, but hospital work setting did not. Tadesse et al. (2021) found that connectedness was the lowest subscale for critical care nurses, with a mean score of 3.59 out of 5. They also found that age, marital status, work experience, and work environment were predictors of

caring behaviors among critical care nurses. Zhumagulova et al. (2020) found that connectedness was the lowest subscale for clinical nurses, with a mean score of 3.77 out of 5. They also found that professional quality of life (PQOL) and demographic characteristics such as age, gender, education, and work experience were positively correlated with caring behaviors among clinical nurses. Hosseini et al. (2019) found that connectedness was the lowest subscale for both emergency department nurses and patients, with mean scores of 3.96 and 3.92 out of 5, respectively. They also found that caring behaviors and patient satisfaction were positively and significantly correlated, and that assurance was the most influential subscale on patient satisfaction. Lee et al. (2018) found that connectedness was the lowest subscale for oncology nurses, with a mean score of 3.85 out of 5. They also found that caring behaviors and organizational commitment were positively and significantly correlated, and that knowledge and skill was the most influential subscale on organizational commitment. The Respectful subscale of CBI-24 is one of the four characteristics of caring behaviors that represent the nurse-patient interaction. Previous research has demonstrated that this subscale is positively linked with numerous aspects, such as feeling of coherence (Kowalczyk et al., 2020), social responsibility (Ghaffari et al., 2019), emotional intelligence (Kaya et al., 2019), and work satisfaction (Wu et al., 2006). These elements may strengthen the nurses' capacity to identify and appreciate the uniqueness and variety of each patient, and to communicate effectively and empathetically. The Respectful subscale of CBI-24 may also influence the patient outcomes, such as patient satisfaction (Wu et al., 2006), trust (Wolf et al., 1994), and quality of life (Porter, 1997). Therefore, it is important to promote and evaluate the respectful caring behaviors among nurses, as they may contribute to the improvement of nursing practice and patient care. The study of Lindström et al., (2020) translated

into Swedish and cross-culturally adapted CBI-24 for a Swedish healthcare context, and psychometrically analyzed the Swedish version of CBI-24. The study found that the Respectful subscale had the highest mean score among the four subscales of the CBI-24 SWE, indicating that Swedish nurses perceived respect as the most important dimension of caring. Kassa et al., (2022) assessed the level and predictors of caring behaviors of critical care nurses in Ethiopia. The study used the CBI-24 to measure caring behaviors. The results revealed that the Respectful subscale had the highest mean score among the four subscales of the CBI-24, indicating that Ethiopian critical care nurses valued respect as the most essential aspect of caring. The study also identified that age, marital status, educational level, and work experience were significant predictors of caring behaviors. Another study by Arsat et al., (2023) examined the effect of work setting and demographic factors on nurses' caring behavior, as well as the differences in nurses' caring behavior based on demographic factors between nurses in public hospitals and nurses in public health services in Sabah, Malaysia. The study used the CBI-24 to measure nurses' perceptions of caring. The results showed that demographic factors such as gender, age, education, economic status, position, and experience had a significant effect on caring behavior. The study also found that the Respectful subscale had the second highest mean score among the four subscales of the CBI-24, suggesting that respect was an important component of caring for Malaysian nurses. Zewdu et al., (2022) assessed the level and predictors of caring behaviors of critical care nurses in Ethiopia using the CBI-24. The study used a cross-sectional design with 422 nurses from 12 hospitals. The study found that the Respectful subscale had a mean score of 3.86 out of 5 and was significantly associated with age, marital status, educational level, and work experience. A study by Chong et al., used the CBI-24 to assess the level and

predictors of caring behaviors of critical care nurses in Sabah, Malaysia. The study found that the level of caring behaviors was high among critical care nurses, and that age, marital status, education level, and work experience were significant predictors of caring behaviors. Klarare et al. translated and adapted the CBI-24 for use in a Swedish context and found that the connectedness subscale had the highest mean score among the four subscales. The study also found that the connectedness subscale had a positive correlation with age, education level, and work experience. McEnroe-Petite, et al. examined the caring behaviors of nursing students and instructors in four countries and used the CBI-24 to measure the students' perceptions of their own and their instructors' caring behaviors. The study found that the connectedness subscale had the highest mean score among the students' self-reported caring behaviors, and that the instructors' caring behaviors had a significant influence on the students' caring behaviors. A study by Ahmed et al., (2020) compared the level and predictors of caring behaviors among critical care nurses in two Arab countries, Jordan and Saudi Arabia. The study found that the connectedness subscale had the highest mean score among all the subscales, indicating that the nurses had a high level of connectedness with their patients and colleagues. The study also found that female gender, holding a master's degree, interest in nursing profession, and a 1:1 nurse-to-patient ratio were significant predictors of caring behaviors, including connectedness. The study suggested that these factors might enhance the nurses' ability to communicate effectively, empathize with others, and provide individualized care. Arsat et al., (2019) also investigated the effect of work setting and demographic factors on nurses' caring behavior, as well as the differences in nurses' caring behavior based on demographic factors between nurses in public hospitals and nurses in public health services in Sabah, Malaysia. The study found that the connectedness subscale

had the second highest mean score among all the subscales, indicating that the nurses had a good level of connectedness with their patients and colleagues. The study also found that demographic factors such as gender, age, education, economic status, position, and experience had a significant effect on caring behavior, including connectedness. However, the study found no significant impact of the work setting on caring behavior, nor was there a notable interaction between the work setting and demographic factors influencing nurses' caring behavior. The study suggested that the nurses' caring behavior might be influenced by their personal values, beliefs, and attitudes, rather than by their work environment. A study by Hassanian et al., (2018) explored the relationship between nurses' social responsibility and their demographic characteristics, such as gender, age, education level, and marital status. The study used a questionnaire to measure nurses' social responsibility, which included items related to connectedness, such as respecting patients' rights, maintaining confidentiality, and collaborating with other health professionals. The study found that the average of total responsibility was 7.3 ± 4.0 , indicating that the nurses had a moderate level of social responsibility. The study also found a significant relationship between nurses' social responsibility and their age and marital status, but not between their gender and education level. The study suggested that older and married nurses might have more social awareness, maturity, and commitment, which could enhance their connectedness with their patients and colleagues.

According to some studies (Al-Makhaita et al., 2014), patients' socio-demographic characteristics, such as age, gender, education, income, marital status, and nationality, can influence their perceptions of the caring behaviors of nurses, including the Knowledge-Skill subscale. For example, one study found that older patients, female patients, and patients with higher education and income levels had

higher scores on the Knowledge-Skill subscale than younger patients, male patients, and patients with lower education and income levels. Another study found that patients' nationality also affected their ratings of the Knowledge-Skill subscale, as Swedish patients had higher scores than Jordanian patients. These findings suggest that patients' socio-demographic characteristics can affect their expectations and evaluations of the nurses' knowledge and skills in caring for them. Therefore, nurses should be aware of the diversity of their patients and tailor their caring behaviors accordingly to meet their needs and preferences. The influence of socio-demographics and clinical characteristics on the perception of caring behaviors in oncology patients (Agyei-Baffour et al., 2011) explored the influence of socio-demographics and clinical characteristics on the perception of caring behaviors in oncology patients in Italy. It used a cross-sectional design and the CBI-24 as a data collection tool. It performed descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the data. It found that patients' socio-demographic characteristics, such as gender, age, marital status, having children, education, work status, income, and nationality, had a significant impact on their perception of the caring behaviors of nurses, including the Knowledge-Skill subscale. The influence of socio-demographic behavioral variables on health-seeking behavior and the utilization of public and private hospitals in Ghana (Adongo et al., 2022) examined the influence of socio-demographic behavioral variables on health-seeking behavior and the use of public and private health facilities in Ghana. It used a quantitative research approach and the modified SERVQUAL dimension as a data collection tool. It conducted descriptive statistics with Pearson's chi-square test to determine the relationship between socio-demographic behavioral variables and health-seeking behavior of patients using public and private hospitals. It showed that there is a significant relationship between the socio-demographic characteristics (sex,

marital status, education, level of income) and the health-seeking behavior of patients in regard to the utilization of public and private health facilities. These results suggest that patients' socio-demographic characteristics can affect their perception and evaluation of the nurses' knowledge and skills in different health settings. The relationship between the assurance subscale and patients' socio-demographic characteristics may vary depending on the context and culture of the healthcare setting. However, some possible factors that could influence this relationship include older patients who may have more complex and chronic health conditions and may require more assurance from nurses than younger patients (Klarare et al., 2021). Female patients may perceive more assurance from nurses than male patients, as they may be more expressive and receptive to emotional support. Patients with higher education levels may have more knowledge and expectations about their health and treatment, seeking more assurance from nurses than patients with lower education levels (Oyekale, 2018). Patients with lower income levels may face more barriers and challenges in accessing and affording quality healthcare, needing more assurance from nurses than patients with higher income levels. Patients who live alone or have limited social support may feel more isolated and vulnerable, appreciating more assurance from nurses than patients who have family or friends to assist them. "An examination of the socio-demographic correlates of patient adherence to lifestyle recommendations following acute coronary syndrome" by Buckley et al., (2011) examines the association between socio-demographic characteristics (such as age, gender, education, income, and living situation) and patient adherence to lifestyle recommendations (such as diet, exercise, smoking, and alcohol consumption) after experiencing acute coronary syndrome. The article suggests that socio-demographic factors may influence the level of assurance and support that patients receive from

their healthcare providers and family members, which, in turn, may affect their adherence behavior (Xie et al., 2020). There are socio-demographic factors that can influence patients' perception of the Respectful subscale of the CBI-24. Older patients generally perceive higher levels of respect from nurses compared to younger patients (Ghafouri et al., 2021). This could be attributed to older patients having more experience with healthcare services, appreciating nurses' efforts more (Ogunlesi et al., 2010). On the other hand, younger patients may have higher expectations and demand more attention from nurses. Female patients typically perceive higher levels of respect from nurses than their male counterparts (Ghafouri et al., 2021). This could be because female patients are more sensitive and vocal of their emotions and needs, therefore enjoying nurses' caring actions more. Conversely, male patients may be more reticent and unwilling to express appreciation or discontent with nurses' care. Patients with higher education levels likely to perceive lower levels of respect from nurses compared to those with lesser education (Ghafouri et al., 2021) This might be because highly educated patients possess greater information and awareness of their rights and expectations, making them more critical of nurses' performance. In contrast, patients with lower education levels may be more grateful and respectful of nurses' authority and expertise. Patients with higher incomes usually perceive lower levels of respect from nurses compared to those with lower incomes (Ogunlesi et al., 2010). This might be because higher-income patients have more access and exposure to high-quality healthcare services, leading to higher standards and demands for nurses' care. Conversely, patients with lower incomes may be more dependent on and appreciative of nurses' assistance and support (Ogunlesi et al., 2010). Several studies have associated the relationship of patients' socio-demographic characteristics to the connectedness subscale of CBI-24. In a study of 234 patients and nurses in Sweden

(Klarare et al., 2021), the patients' socio-demographic profile included age, gender, education level, and diagnosis. The study found that there were no significant differences in the connectedness subscale scores between patients with different socio-demographic characteristics, except for patients with cancer, who scored lower than patients with other diagnoses. In a study of 384 patients in Ethiopia (Gember et al., 2023), the patients' socio-demographic profile included age, gender, marital status, education level, occupation, and income. The study found that there were significant differences in the connectedness subscale scores between patients with different socio-demographic characteristics, such as age, gender, marital status, and income. For example, younger patients, female patients, married patients, and patients with higher income scored higher on the connectedness subscale than older patients, male patients, unmarried patients, and patients with lower income. In a study of 300 patients in Jordan (AbuRuz et al., 2017), the patients' socio-demographic profile included age, gender, marital status, education level, and income. The study found that there were no significant differences in the connectedness subscale scores between patients with different socio-demographic characteristics, except for patients with a higher education level, who scored higher than patients with a lower education level.

Difference of Nurses and Patients Perception in CBI-24

Some studies indicate that patients often rate the Knowledge-Skill Subscale higher than nurses do, suggesting a potential gap between the expectations and perceptions of caring behaviors (Öhlén et al., 2017). This implies a discrepancy between what nurses believe they are doing and what patients think they are receiving in terms of the technical and professional competence of nurses (Rafii et al., 2014). In a related study in Sweden, patients rated the Knowledge and Skill subscale higher

than nurses (4.51 vs. 4.28 on a 5-point scale), signifying higher expectations or more positive perceptions of nurses' knowledge and skill among patients than among nurses themselves (Öhlén et al., 2017). This may suggest a need for nurses to enhance their communication and feedback skills or for patients to have more realistic and informed expectations of nurses' roles and responsibilities. A study conducted by Kiliç and Öztunç (2020) compared the care perceptions of patients who underwent surgical operations and the nurses providing care. The study used the CBI-24 to measure caring behaviors, consisting of four subscales: Assurance, Knowledge and Skill, Respectful Deference, and Connectedness. Involving 379 patients and 70 nurses from a university hospital in Gaziantep, Turkey, the results showed that the CBI-24 total average score of patients (5.08 ± 0.97) was significantly lower than that of nurses (5.28 ± 0.45) ($p=0.05$). Patients also rated the Knowledge and Skill subscale lower than the nurses (4.97 vs. 4.76 on a 6-point scale), indicating a higher value placed by patients on the technical and professional aspects of nursing care than perceived by nurses ($p<0.001$). The study concluded that a discrepancy in perceptions of caring behaviors between patients and nurses may impact the quality of care and patient satisfaction.

The caring behavior of nurses is manifested in the way they interact with patients and provide care that addresses their physical, emotional, and spiritual needs (Hajinezhad & Azodi, 2014). The assurance subscale is one of the four dimensions of caring behavior that measures the nurse's availability, attentiveness, and security for the patient (Kargar et al., 2021). The assurance subscale is crucial because it can reduce the patient's anxiety, boost their confidence, and enhance their satisfaction (Vujanić et al., 2020). The relationship between the caring behavior of both nurses and patients and the assurance subscale can be examined from two perspectives:

perception and outcome. Perception refers to how nurses and patients view the frequency and quality of caring behavior and the assurance subscale in the hospital setting (Kargar et al., 2021). Outcome refers to how caring behavior and the assurance subscale affect the patient's health, recovery, and well-being. Some studies have found a significant difference between the perception of caring behavior and the assurance subscale among nurses and patients (Kargar et al., 2021), suggesting that there may be differing expectations and experiences of caring behavior and the assurance subscale. For example, nurses may believe they are providing sufficient assurance to the patients, but the patients may feel they need more assurance from the nurses. This gap can affect the quality of care and the patient-nurse relationship. Additionally, some studies have shown a positive relationship between the perception of caring behavior and the assurance subscale and the outcome of patient satisfaction. This implies that the higher the perception of caring behavior and the assurance subscale, the higher the patient satisfaction. Patient satisfaction serves as a crucial indicator of the quality of care and the patient's evaluation of the hospital service (Vujanić et al., 2020). It can also influence the patient's adherence to treatment, trust in the health care system, and health outcomes. A study comparing CBI-24 scores between nurses and patients in caring behavior and the assurance subscale was conducted by Larrabee et al. (2010). They found statistically significant differences ($p < .001$) between nurses' and patients' perceptions on the subscales of the CBI-24, particularly on the assurance and connectedness subscales. The authors suggested that these differences might reflect the gap between the expectations and experiences of patients and nurses in the hospital setting. Another study examining the relationship between patients' perceptions of nurse caring behaviors and patient satisfaction in the acute care setting was conducted by Al-Mutair et al. (2017). They utilized the CBI-24

and the Patient Satisfaction Instrument (PSI) to measure the variables of interest. Their findings revealed a positive relationship between patients' perceptions of nurse caring behaviors and patient satisfaction in the acute care setting. Additionally, they discovered that the assurance subscale of the CBI-24 had the highest mean score among the four subscales, indicating that patients valued the assurance dimension of caring behaviors the most.

In Pulpulaan's study (2019) on Nurses' and Patients' Perceptions of Caring Behaviors in Long Term Care Hospitals, the CBI-24 was utilized to compare nurses' and patients' perceptions in Qatar. Results revealed that nurses reported higher mean scores for perceived caring behaviors across all CBI-24 items and subscales than patients. Notably, statistically significant differences were found in the Respectful subscale ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, Tsangari (2012) examined patients' and nurses' perceptions of respect and human presence using a modified CBI-42 in acute care settings across six European countries. Significant differences were observed in 29 of the instrument's 50 specific behaviors and in five out of six subscales. The Respectful subscale showed a significant difference between patients and nurses ($p < 0.05$). Bucco's study (2015) investigated relationships between patients' perceptions of nurse caring behaviors, nurses' perceptions, and patient satisfaction in the emergency department in the US, employing the CBI-24. Notably, patient satisfaction negatively correlated with CBI dyad difference scores, with the Respectful subscale significantly affecting satisfaction ($\beta = -0.41, p < 0.001$). Klarare et al. (2021) conducted a study in a Swedish context, translating and adapting the CBI-24. The Respectful dimension received the highest mean scores from both patients and nurses. Significant differences were identified in three Respectful dimension items, with patients rating higher than nurses ($p < 0.001$). Khodaveisi et al. (2023) explored differences in CBI-

24 items within the Respectful dimension in an Iranian context. The Respectful dimension received the lowest mean scores, indicating it was less valued. Significant differences were found in four Respectful dimension items, with nurses rating higher than patients ($p < 0.001$).

In line with the outcomes of most studies, the levels of connectedness appear to be low among both nurses and patients. Contrarily, Dursun Ergezen et al. (2020) conducted a study with 455 patients at a university hospital in Turkey, utilizing the CBI-24 instrument to assess perceptions of nurses' caring behaviors. The results revealed elevated scores in the nurses' Knowledge-Skill subscale, indicating technical competence and professional knowledge. Conversely, lower scores were assigned to the Connectedness and Respectful subscales, reflecting emotional and interpersonal aspects of care. The study also emphasized that patients' perceptions of caring behaviors were influenced by factors such as the presence of a family caregiver, the hospital selection rationale, and the type of clinic admission. Ibrahim and Allawy (2021) identified a positive correlation between nurses' caring behaviors and COVID-19 patients' satisfaction, with the Connectedness Subscale recording the lowest mean score. Conversely, Ergezen et al. (2020) reported positive patient perceptions of nurses' caring behaviors in the Connectedness Subscale, particularly regarding technical aspects of care. Almalki et al. (2017) discovered that nurses, patients, and nursing students held similar perceptions of caring behaviors. Additionally, they observed a positive correlation between patients' age and scores on the Respect and Connectedness Subscales. In a study by Do et al. (2014) exploring caring behaviors in Vietnam, both nurses and patients considered assurance as the most crucial, followed by the Connectedness Subscale. Lin et al. (2010) investigated the relationship between nurses' caring behaviors and patients' satisfaction in Taiwan,

revealing that the Connectedness Subscale had the highest impact on patient satisfaction, followed by the Assurance Subscale.

Synthesis

ER nurses are under immense pressure due to the current shortage of nurses and the increased number of patients with longer stays in Tawam Hospital. The chaotic healthcare environment makes it difficult for nurses to provide compassionate care. However, it is important to consider what patients perceive as caring behaviors. The fast pace of the ER can make it difficult to implement caring behaviors, but if we can determine what these behaviors are, it will help nurses be aware of what needs to be changed and how to improve. Nursing is a profession that is built on the concept of caring for others. Over the years, this concept has been studied in various patient care and educational settings. The positive experiences that patients have with healthcare personnel tend to result in more effective coping skills. There is a high correlation between nurse caring behaviors and patient satisfaction. The importance of caring has been widely acknowledged in the business arena to successfully provide cost effective services. Benner and his colleagues are just a few of the theorists who have spoken to the importance of caring in nursing. Although each theorist addresses the concept of caring from different perspectives, they all agree that caring is a valuable quality.

The Emergency Department at Tawam Hospital is a multifaceted zone that necessitates varying categories of healthcare provision for multiple causative factors. Emergency departments are purposefully organized and equipped to offer prompt and effective medical attention to individuals in dire or pressing need of medical care. The effective management of medical emergencies comprising minor injuries to life-threatening conditions necessitates equipping and training the personnel operating

within the Emergency Department at Tawam Hospital. The department frequently experiences overpopulation, resulting in extensive waiting periods for patients seeking medical assistance. The provision of healthcare services in this setting can present significant difficulties and induce substantial tension among both patients and healthcare personnel. Thus, effective management measures are imperative to ensure the timely and adequate delivery of care to patients. It is commonly the initial point of contact for patients who may present with a diverse array of medical requirements. Healthcare staff are required to expeditiously examine patients and ascertain the optimal course of action to be taken, which includes promptly administering medical treatment, directing patients to other departments within the hospital, or discharging patients with the necessary post-treatment care. Emergency departments are frequently the location where acute medical incidents occur, necessitating the employment of specialized equipment and expertise. For example, the provision of medical care for cardiac arrest patients necessitates the use of highly specialized equipment and the employment of trained personnel capable of undertaking complex interventions associated with advanced life support. The staff within Tawam Hospital's Emergency Department are required to receive not only specialized training and possess necessary equipment to be capable of delivering services to patients in need of such care but also the behavior in providing quality of care. It represents a challenging milieu that necessitates diverse modalities of care owing to its inherent purpose of delivering urgent healthcare services to patients who are acutely ill or injured, frequently within a congested and multicultural setting, and presenting with an array of complex medical requirements that mandate specialized healthcare services and staff caring behavior proficiency.

The Emergency Department at Tawam Hospital presents an ideal setting for the

examination of the attitudes and behaviors of both patients and nursing personnel regarding the provision of caring behavior in a diverse setting. The diverse cultural environment of the hospital presents a valuable opportunity to closely examine the way nurses deliver culturally responsive care to patients from varying ethnicities. Undertaking a research endeavor within the context of an emergency department enables comprehensive investigation by which ER nurses provide care in high-stress environments, as well as the corresponding perceptions of caring behavior among patients. Tawam Hospital's exceptional standing in providing high-quality healthcare services, especially in emergency care, underscores its steadfast commitment to patient-centered care and advancements in quality. This positioning makes it an ideal environment for the exploration of caring behavior. Furthermore, the emergency department employs a cadre of proficient and experienced nurses who possess the ability to provide care that is culturally considerate. The presence of equipped and advanced resources, including sophisticated medical apparatus, proficient personnel, and sound administrative backing, guarantees the safe and ethical acquisition of data. The present study identifies Tawam Hospital Emergency Department as an outstanding setting for the study of the perceptions of patients and nurses regarding caring behavior in a multicultural environment. This assertion is based on the facility's heterogeneous patient population, demanding work environment, laudable standing, proficient nursing staff, and readily accessible resources.

Theoretical Framework

Jean Watson's Caring Theory posits the significance of human interconnectedness and empathetic understanding within the nursing discipline. Watson theorizes that the adoption of a caring approach by nurses in their professional

practice can have the potential to foster the process of healing, as well as mitigate the experience of pain and distress among patients. She significantly emphasizes the fundamental role of human connection and empathy in the field of nursing. As per Watson's assertion, the adoption of a caring behavior by nurses during their professional practice yields the potential to foster the process of healing and mitigate patients' distress and promote wellness. This study presents a theoretical framework that explores Watson's Caring Theory and its 10 carative factors, along with an analysis of its applicability in a multicultural context. The study endeavors to explore the perspectives of both nurses and patients regarding the provision of caring behavior by Tawam Hospital Emergency Department nurses in a multicultural environment. By introducing the 10 carative factors as a guide for nurses enhancing the quality-of-care relationship given to patients, the carative factors of Jean Watson provides the framework of this study incorporating humanistic and holistic approach in nursing caring behavior. The 10 Carative Factors are as follows (Watson, 1979):

1. Formation of a humanistic-altruistic set of values;
2. Instillation of faith-hope;
3. Cultivation of sensitivity to one's self and to others;
4. Development of a helping-trusting, human caring connection;
5. Promotion and acceptance of the expressing of happy and negative sentiments;
6. Systematic application of the scientific problem-solving process for decision making;
7. Promotion of interpersonal teaching-learning;
8. Provision for a helpful, protecting, and/or corrective mental, physical, sociological, and spiritual environment;

9. Assistance in fulfillment of human wants;
10. Recognition of the presence of spiritual components of life.

The above-mentioned factors are pivotal in the creation of a nurturing environment that effectively caters to the distinctive needs of individual patients especially in the emergency setting. The implementation of culturally competent practices within a multicultural environment has the potential to facilitate the acquisition of cultural proficiency by healthcare professionals, augment effective communication, and cultivate a sense of mutual esteem between ER nursing staff and patients hailing from diverse cultural backgrounds in providing caring behavior. The occurrence of multiculturalism holds significant relevance within the context of Tawam Hospital Emergency Department, where it tends to exert a considerable impact on the perception of caring behavior among both nurses and patients. The adoption of a caring attitude by nurses has the potential to facilitate a positive experience for individuals from various cultural backgrounds. Achieving this objective can be facilitated by comprehending the cultural tenets and customs of individual patients, exhibiting deference for their personal values and preferences, and furnishing care that is customized to their requirements. The main aim of this study is to investigate the viewpoints of both nurses and patients concerning the provision of caring behavior by Tawam ER nurses within a multicultural setting. This study intends to investigate the degree to which the ten carative factors stipulated in Watson's Caring Theory are evident in the nursing profession of Tawam ER nurses. The study adopted a correlational research design with the intention of acquiring data from both nurses and patients which will be analyzed through a combination of qualitative and quantitative paradigms with the aim of describing relationship and differences among variables.

The Caring Theory developed by Jean Watson and its corresponding 10 carative factors serve as an effective framework for ER nurses to deliver patient-centered care that is comprehensive in nature, values the humanity inherent in healthcare provision, and recognizes the fundamental importance of preserving patient dignity and autonomy. In a multi-ethnic environment, it is imperative to gain an understanding of the variances in cultural norms and to acknowledge and honor the convictions and preferences of patients to ensure the provision of caring behavior, which caters to their individual needs. The present research endeavor intends to augment the existing body of literature on the topic of caring behavior within a multicultural setting. Additionally, this study seeks to offer novel insights into the perceptions of both nursing staff and patients concerning caring behavior within the context of emergency environment setting.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study serves as the theoretical fundamentals guiding the research design that contribute to the quality and integrity of the study. It provides the foundation for discussion and analysis, as well as the identification of gaps in existing knowledge and research. It provides a structure for integrating and organizing key concepts, variables, and ideas relevant to identify the relationship and differences of nurses and patients' perception in caring behavior.

The diagram below represents a model of the relationship between patients and nurses' perceptions of caring behavior and how socio-demographic factors may influence this relationship. The solid line between patients and nurses' perceptions of caring behavior indicates that there is a direct and strong relationship between them. This means that the way patients perceive the caring behavior of nurses may influence

the way nurses perceive their own caring behavior, and vice versa.

The socio-demographic profile refers to the characteristics of the study population which are included in the study are age, gender, educational background, marital status, ethnicity, and years of experience. These characteristics may affect how nurses and patients think, feel, and behave in different situations. The broken line between the socio-demographic profile and the solid line indicates that there is an indirect and weak relationship between the socio-demographic factors and the perceptions of caring behavior. This means that the socio-demographic factors may have some influence on how patients and nurses perceive caring behavior, but this influence is not as strong or consistent as the direct relationship between them.

Caring behaviors are often thought of as a hallmark trait of nurses. . It is more crucial to take into account how patients view the caring actions of nurses. Patient outcomes and satisfaction may be significantly impacted by how well patients perceive the care of their nurses. Patients who experience a sense of care frequently report improved feelings of safety, comfort, and support as well as improved emotional and spiritual well-being and a speedier sensation of feeling better. The greatest arbiter of a nurse's compassionate actions is the patient. Thus, in order to maintain high-quality patient care, nurses must be open and honest with their caring behaviors. Patient care, however, may be jeopardized if compassionate actions are not demonstrated or if patients' needs are not addressed.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework.

Research Hypotheses

H_a: There is a significant difference between the perceived caring behavior of nurses and patients given by Tawam ER Nurses in a multicultural environment setting.

H_a: There is a significant relationship between the perceived caring behavior of nurses and their socio-demographic profile given by Tawam ER Nurses in a multicultural environment setting.

H_a: There is a significant relationship between the perceived caring behavior of patients and their socio-demographic profile given by Tawam ER Nurses in a multicultural environment setting.

Operational Definition of Terms

The following concepts are theoretically and operationally defined, together with information on how they will be assessed, to facilitate clarity and simple comprehension of the terms used in this study.

Dependent Variables:

- 1. Perceived Caring Behavior of Nurses** - Observable actions and expressions of empathy, compassion, respect, and attentiveness demonstrated by Tawam ER Nurses in the provision of patient care. This includes both emotional and physical aspects of care, as perceived by both nurses and patients.
- 2. Perceived Caring Behavior of Patients** - The subjective interpretation and understanding of caring behavior by both Tawam ER Nurses and patients. It encompasses the thoughts, feelings, and evaluations of the demonstrated caring behaviors as reported through surveys, interviews, and feedback forms.

Measurement:

The **Caring Behavior Inventory-24 (CBI-24)** is a survey designed to assess the perceptions of caring behaviors from both patients and nurses. Derived from the original 42-item CBI developed by Wolf et al. (1994), the CBI-24 has undergone a process of shortening and validation by Wu et al. (2006). Comprising 24 items, the CBI-24 is organized into four subscales, each signifying a distinct dimension of caring.

The operational definitions of the terms are outlined as follows:

- a. Assurance:** This subscale measures the extent to which the nurse provides comfort, security, and confidence to the patient. It includes items such as “gives me a sense of hope” and “helps me to feel safe”

- b. Knowledge and skill:** This subscale measures the extent to which the nurse demonstrates competence, expertise, and professionalism in delivering care. It includes items such as “explains things clearly” and “performs nursing procedures skillfully”.
- c. Respectful:** This subscale measures the extent to which the nurse respects the patient’s dignity, autonomy, and individuality. It includes items such as “treats me as a person, not just a patient” and “respects my privacy”.
- d. Connectedness:** This subscale measures the extent to which the nurse establishes a rapport, empathy, and trust with the patient. It includes items such as “listens attentively to me” and “shows genuine interest in me”.

The CBI-24 employs a six-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (never) to 6 (always), to assess the frequency with which the nurse demonstrates each caring behavior. Total scores and subscale scores can be computed by summing up the responses to the relevant items. Higher scores indicate elevated perceived levels of caring behaviors, while lower scores suggest decreased perceived levels of caring behaviors. The CBI-24, which has strong psychometric qualities like as construct validity, test-retest reliability, and internal consistency, has been effectively translated and adapted for use in a variety of cultural contexts, such as Sweden and Iran.

Independent Variables:

- 1. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Nurses-** Identifiable attributes of Tawam ER Nurses related to social factors, including age, gender, educational background, employment status, ethnicity, marital status, and years of experience.

2. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Patients- Identifiable attributes of Tawam ER patients related to social factors, including age, gender, educational background, employment status, ethnicity, and marital status.

Measurement:

- a. **Age** - is the number of years an individual has lived since birth. Age will be recorded as the participant's chronological age in years at the time of data collection.
- b. **Gender** - refers to the social and cultural roles, behaviors, and expectations linked with one's identity as male or female. Gender assessment will involve participants self-identifying as male, female, or another gender identity within established categories.
- c. **Educational Background** - Educational background is the highest level of formal education an individual has completed. Participants will be asked to indicate their highest level of education attained, such as high school diploma, bachelor's degree, master's degree, or doctoral degree.
- d. **Employment Status** - denotes an individual's current employment status, discerning whether they are presently employed, unemployed, or not in the labor force. Participants will be classified into the categories of employed, unemployed, or not in the labor force based on their current occupational status.
- e. **Ethnicity** - represents an individual's cultural identity, typically rooted in shared ancestral, cultural, or historical attributes. Participants will be requested to self-identify their ethnicity from provided categories, which

might encompass choices such as Hispanic or Latino, African American, Asian, Caucasian, Middle Eastern, and other options.

- f. **Marital Status** - indicates whether an individual is currently married, divorced, separated, widowed, or single. Participants will be asked to select their current marital status from a list of options.
- g. **Years of Experience** - represent the number of years an individual has been involved in a particular profession or field. Participants will be asked to specify the number of years they have worked in their current profession or field as a measure of professional experience.

Additional Operational Definitions:

Multicultural Environment - A setting characterized by the presence of individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds within the Tawam Hospital Emergency Department. This includes variations in cultural norms, communication styles, and language, potentially influencing perceptions of caring behavior.

Patient Satisfaction - The level of contentment and positive experiences reported by patients regarding the care received from Tawam ER Nurses. This is measured through standardized patient satisfaction surveys, feedback forms, and interviews.

Compassion - The expression of genuine concern and kindness by ER nurses towards patients. This caring behavior involves going beyond clinical tasks to show empathy, warmth, and a genuine desire to alleviate patients' suffering.

Carative Factors - refer to the core principles and concepts introduced by nursing theorist Jean Watson in her Theory of Human Caring. The significance of the nurse-patient bond and the humanistic elements of nursing care are emphasized by these elements.

Technical and Emotional Aspects of Care - comprehensive approach to caring behavior, incorporating both the technical aspects (cognitive and psychomotor skills) and emotional aspects (empathy, compassion, and communication) as highlighted in the 2020 study by Bucco.

Universal Definition of Caring - A standardized and universally accepted understanding of the concept of "caring" in nursing practice. This is essential for achieving consistency in the evaluation of caring behaviors and fostering a shared understanding among healthcare professionals.

Emergency Severity Index (ESI) - A triage method used to classify patients based on the acuity of their medical condition or injury, ranging from ESI 1 (requiring immediate attention) to ESI 5 (requiring minimal intervention).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria - Specific conditions defining who is eligible (inclusion) or ineligible (exclusion) to participate in the study.

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A correlational research design was employed in this study to explore the correspondence between two or more variables. In the context of evaluating the perception of caring behavior among ER nurses in a culturally diverse medical setting, socio-demographic variables have the potential to exert a significant impact on these perceptions, as perceived by both patients and nurses. Through the application of a correlational design, the investigator is enabled to study the link between socio-demographic characteristics, including age, gender, ethnicity, educational background, and years of experience, and the perception of caring behavior. Furthermore, the application of a correlation study may aid in the identification of factors that potentially influence individuals' perceptions in caring behavior regarding the quality of care they receive and to identify specifically the differences and relationship of both nurses and patients' perception in caring behavior.

The study intended to gather qualitative data through individualized interviews and surveys utilizing a predetermined set of open-ended inquiries, commonly founded on the theoretical framework. The acquisition of quantitative data was executed through distributing questionnaires or surveys to the patient. The data will be subjected to careful analysis, followed by the integration of obtained results for the purpose of comparing and interpreting the outcomes. By utilizing a methodology referred to as a correlational design, it is possible to obtain greater comprehension regarding the variables that exert an impact on the perspectives of patients and nurses in relation to caring behavior. This comprehension holds the potential to enhance the caliber of

healthcare provision in a culturally diverse setting.

The use of a correlational design in this study is evident in the exploration of the relationship between nurses' and patients' perceived caring behavior and their socio-demographic characteristics. Correlation coefficients (r) and corresponding p -values are used to assess the strength and significance of linear relationships between variables such as age, educational background, ethnicity, marital status, and years of experience with nurses' and patients' perceived caring behavior across different subscales (Knowledge-Skill, Assurance, Respectful, and Connectedness). Correlation analysis is a statistical method used to measure the degree of association between two variables. In this case, the principal investigator is determining whether there is a significant relationship between nurses' and patients' socio-demographic characteristics and their perceived caring behaviors. The correlation coefficients indicate the strength and direction of these relationships, while the p -values help determine whether these relationships are statistically significant. The utilization of correlational analysis in this study affords the principal investigator the opportunity to examine potential relationships between socio-demographic factors and the manifestation of caring behaviors among both nurses and patients. It is imperative to underscore that correlation does not establish causation. Discovering a correlation does not automatically imply a cause-and-effect relationship, suggesting that alterations in one variable lead to changes in the other. Instead, it merely signifies an association between the variables. In summary, the application of correlational design in this study aids researchers in scrutinizing patterns and connections within the data. This, in turn, contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing the perceived caring behaviors of nurses and patients in a multicultural healthcare setting.

Study Population

The study applied a statistical software tool called G-Power to determine the required sample size and assess the statistical power of the study based on the parameters given with a significance level of 0.05. It will target patients who have been registered in the emergency department of Tawam Hospital in the United Arab Emirates and have spent up to five hours in the facility, in addition to the emergency department nursing staff. The figure of 130 ER nurse professionals shall comprise the entirety of the bedside staff. The current study aims to delve into the perspective of emergency department nurses and patients who have sought medical attention at Tawam Hospital. This research endeavor incorporates detailed measures of inclusion and exclusion criteria, established to corroborate the reliability and authenticity of the collected data. The selection of nurse and patient participants for this study will adhere to the given criteria. Nurse participants will comprise individuals currently engaged in providing direct care to patients in the emergency department. Patient participants, on the other hand, will be required to meet specific eligibility requirements, including alertness, coherence, and lack of distress, to ensure their ability to participate meaningfully in surveys or interviews following receipt of appropriate medical intervention, while safeguarding optimal patient care and treatment. The present investigation will involve conducting interviews or surveys of ER nurses during periods when their patient care duties do not demand immediate attention. To be included in the study, individuals who possess the ability to effectively respond to interview questions, particularly those who are fluent in either English or Arabic, will be eligible for selection as study participants. However, the study will exclude patients and nurses who do not belong to the ED of Tawam Hospital or are employed in other medical institutions. Additionally, patients who necessitate continuity of care and are

programmed for admission, those whose medical condition requires prompt life-saving intervention, patients who exhibit confusion or uncooperativeness, individuals who have been referred from other healthcare facilities or departments, and those diagnosed with communicable diseases that may put the interviewer at risk will not be included in the study.

Sampling Design

The study employed purposive sampling, also known as selective sampling, based on the specified criteria related to the specific targeted participants that the study required, without affecting the reliability and integrity of the collected data. The principal investigator set parameters to determine the specific participants needed in the study. The underlying principle informing the use of purposive sampling is to attain congruity between the sample population and the research goals and objectives. This approach promotes methodological soundness, augments the trustworthiness of the findings, and reinforces the dependability of the data and outcomes. Such alignment is ensured through the careful consideration of inclusion and exclusion criteria specified in the study. The concept under consideration comprises four essential aspects, namely credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

Research Setting

The Emergency Department at Tawam Hospital comprises four distinct sections, namely an adult section, a pediatric section, a section dedicated to medical care planning for adults, and another section devoted to medical care planning specifically for children. The establishment boasts a sum of 150 bed accommodations and is equipped with a specialized unit catering to adult patients, consisting of 72 beds and

an area with a capacity of 22 beds available for accommodation of pediatric patients. There exist two additional locations identified as PAPU and MAPU that offer a total accommodation capacity of 26 and 30 beds, respectively.

The adult emergency department is divided into six units, namely Treatment 1, Treatment 2, Treatment 3, Triage Area, Resuscitation Area, and Short Stay Unit (SSU). The Emergency Severity Index (ESI) is the triage method used to classify patients based on the level of acuity of their medical condition or injury and the nature of the required intervention. The present system entails classifying patients into five distinct categories based on the intensity of medical attention required. Patients belonging to ESI 1 require immediate medical attention, whereas those categorized under ESI 5 necessitate minimal and non-pressing medical intervention.

Patients requiring moderate to immediate medical attention are commonly treated in Treatment 1 through 3 as well as the Short Stay Unit (SSU). Occasionally, patients requiring urgent medical attention may be directly transported to the Resuscitation Area. The selection process will exclusively consider individuals from Treatment Area 1 to 3, as well as the Short Stay Unit (SSU). These units do not require urgent medical attention. The present study will exclusively focus on the adult emergency areas, which typically accommodates adult individuals who meet specific criteria.

The research was done in the vicinity of Al Ain. The location refers to a city located in the emirate of Abu Dhabi, which is the primary city and capital of the United Arab Emirates. The research will evaluate persons seeking medical assistance at the Tawam Emergency Department, with specific focus on the viewpoints of patients and nurses working within. Tawam Hospital enjoys a recognized standing as a healthcare institution in Al Ain City and in the whole emirate, where it provides a complete variety

of medical services to respond to the urgent healthcare requirements of the community, specializing in oncology care and management. Tawam Hospital offers an adequate number of 509 beds, thereby allowing the provision of excellent medical care to a considerable population of patients.

Research Instrument

The Caring Behaviors Inventory-24 (CBI-24) is an empirically derived tool created for the purpose of assessing the way caring is perceived within various healthcare environments. The instrument bears a distinct conceptual and theoretical underpinning and has been explicitly designed for application in the context of patient and nurse interaction. The utilization of CBI-24 has observed a widespread adoption and has exhibited noteworthy levels of internal consistency, convergent validity, and desirable test-retest reliability in its implementation amongst patients admitted in hospitals and professional nurses.

The CBI instrument, consisting of 24 items measured on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (never) to 6 (always), has been developed on the foundation of Watson's 10 carative factors. The utilization of the CBI was limited to the implementation of a self-reporting questionnaire to record the caring behaviors exhibited by both ER nurses and patients within the Emergency Department of Tawam Hospital. The evaluative criterion of internal consistency or reliability pertaining to the Caring Behaviors Inventory (CBI) was determined to be moderately to significantly robust, evidenced by the Cronbach alpha score of 0.65-0.80 (Wu, Larrabee, & Putnam, 2006). This was similarly applicable to the test-retest reliability and attained a final alpha coefficient of 0.92.

This research tool comprises four interrelated subscales, namely: (I) the

Assurance subscale, which pertains to the prompt accessibility and security of patients' requirements (consisting of 8 items); (II) the Knowledge and Skill subscale, which encompasses conscientiousness and proficiency (consisting of 5 items); (III) the Respectful subscale, which pertains to the maintenance of patients' dignity (consisting of 6 items); and (IV) the Connectedness subscale, which encompasses the provision of ongoing support to patients in a timely manner (consisting of 5 items). Participants were requested to assess each individual element using a six-point Likert scale that extended from 1 (never) to 6 (always). The present study determines the caring behavior for each subscale and the overall score by obtaining the mean value for all four subscales.

The Caring Behaviors Inventory-24 (CBI-24), developed by Wu et al., is a reduced version of the comprehensive 42-item CBI. In the year 2006, there were notable occurrences within various fields of study that garnered attention and analysis. The CBI-24 tool is a recently developed instrument employed for the purpose of evaluating the perceptions of both patients and nurses regarding caring behaviors. This tool exhibits several noteworthy benefits, including its novelty, consistent number of items, and applicability for both patient evaluation of caring behavior and nurse perception of caring behaviors from their own perspectives.

The CBI-24 questionnaire underwent a process of translation to Arabic which involved the expertise of an English-Arabic language specialist. Subsequently, the translated questionnaire was subjected to a back-translation process by another expert with proficient skills in both Arabic and English. A group of scholars with a keen interest in the research area, and possessing doctoral qualifications in the field of nursing, undertook an assessment of the Arabic translation of the tool to ensure its comprehensibility and legibility. The insights provided by the participants were

considered to proceed with the further enhancement of the associated items.

Pilot Study

A pilot study was conducted to assess the validity of the independent variables, the selection of methods used to measure the dependent variable, and whether the test or measure is appropriate. Furthermore, it can provide insights as to whether participants understand instructions and are willing to provide feedback about their experience.

The pilot study for this research began with the qualitative data collection and analysis of patients and staff nurses in the Tawam Emergency Department. In-depth interviews were conducted, and specific questionnaires were provided to establish the issues to be addressed in a large-scale data collection. Suggestions and feedback were obtained from the participants to help make the process more efficient and reliable before the main intervention is conducted. The next step would be testing the research process. Before the main intervention is conducted, several education sessions are held to determine what vital information needs to be changed or added. Materials were also distributed to gain feedback from patients and staff nurses.

Data Collection Method and Procedures

The data collection procedure within the emergency department was performed by a cohort of ten nursing staff who have voluntarily consented to be part of the research project. Preceding the initiation of the data collection procedure, the mentioned nurse personnel shall partake in inclusive educational and training sessions aimed at guaranteeing their comprehension of the paramount significance of patient data confidentiality and privacy.

The study included 340 respondents out of a target number of 385. A total of 120 nurses and 220 patients participated in the study. The respondents were drawn from the Emergency Department of Tawam Hospital. For the entire ER, there are 130 nurses. Nurses who work in administration positions are not included. The study only includes ER nurses who are handling patients as part of its inclusion criteria. During the data collection process, ten nurses were not surveyed due to conflicting schedules, and some were on vacation and assigned to other areas. This study includes and excludes patients based on its inclusion and exclusion criteria. A patient who is brought to the emergency room with a life-threatening condition or who is only on the fast track is excluded from the study. In the ER, participants were drawn from Treatment 1, Treatment 2, Treatment 3, Short Stay Unit (SSU), and Resuscitation areas. According to the study's inclusion and exclusion criteria, surveys were conducted only after treatment was administered.

The training sessions concentrated on the study's criteria for inclusion and exclusion with the aim of ensuring accurate and reliable collection of data. The nursing staff received training to effectively inquire pertinent inquiries to ensure that the gathered data aligns with the specified aims and objectives of the study. To ensure conformity to policies and procedures established by the hospital, the entirety of the data collection process was overseen by a designated research assistant. The research assistant assumed the responsibility of ensuring that the informed consent protocol is observed, and that the data gathered is comprehensive and precise. The study exclusively comprises patients who have undergone registration procedures within six hours from their arrival at and subsequent intervention in the emergency department. It is imperative to acknowledge that individuals who are not directly affiliated with the patient, such as their relatives, friends, or caregivers, are strictly

prohibited from participating in the completion of questionnaires or providing any information. The present measure is intended to guarantee that the data gathered solely emanates from patients themselves and is not subjected to extrinsic variables. The procedure for data collection was executed with the utmost diligence and exactitude to ensure that the consequential outcomes are precise and dependable. In contrast, the inclusion and exclusion criteria are as follows:

Inclusion Criteria;

- a. Limited to Emergency Department patients and nurses exclusively at Tawam Hospital ER;
- b. Patients categorized as ESI 2 and 3, they should be conscious, coherent, alert, and not in distress;
- c. Bedside nurses at Tawam Hospital ER, who are the end users of this study;
- d. Patients registered in the ER within the first 5 hours of their stay;
- e. Patients who possess the capability to effectively respond to interview or questionnaire questions;
- f. Interviews shall commence only after all relevant interventions pertaining to the patient's complaint have been completed.

Exclusion Criteria;

- a. Patients, nurses, and allied health personnel in other hospital departments are excluded;
- b. Patients categorized as ESI 1, or ESI 4 and 5, respectively, are excluded;
- c. Nurses in administrative positions not directly involved in patient care are excluded;

- d. Admitted patients who have been in the ER for more than 5 hours are not part of the study;
- e. Relatives or caregivers of patients are not to answer the interview or questionnaire questions;
- f. Patients diagnosed with communicable diseases are also excluded;
- g. Patients who are uncooperative, confused, or require life-saving interventions are not included in the study;
- h. Patients who cannot read and understand English or Arabic are excluded.

A purpose of the study letter was prepared to be given to the Chief Nursing Officer (CNO) and research administrator of the hospital prior to conducting the research. The research committee is responsible for giving permission before data collection and was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Hospital before commencing data collection.

The consent form, which was the first page of each questionnaire, included the researcher's name, the purpose of the study, and various ethically based instructions. This form ensured that participation in the study was voluntary, and that each participant could withdraw from it at any time without being penalized or deprived of their usual care. Additionally, the form ensured that data collection for this study would be anonymous. The researcher explained to the participants that the data collected would only be used for research purposes and that the findings would be published in aggregate form.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical issues are always a top concern in any type of research. When conducting research in a new country, it is especially important to be aware of possible ethical issues that could arise. One example of an ethical issue that could be relevant in this study is cultural diversity and norms. While it is important to respect the laws and regulations of the country in which the research is being conducted, it is also crucial to be sensitive to the fact that there may be members of the community who hold different values than what is typically found in the United Arab Emirates.

This research is a non-experimental study that did not involve any physical or critical confidential issues. It is research of identifying patient and nurse perception in caring behavior that did not affect any laws and regulations. Furthermore, to protect the participants' confidentiality and privacy, an informed consent was done before conducting any interviews and surveys as regulated by the law and as per the conditions given by the Ethics Regulatory Board (ERB).

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The outcomes of the data collection are presented in this chapter, together with a discussion of pertinent data analysis and interpretation that is informed by the study objectives and relevant literature.

This includes assessing the views of patients and nurses on the caring behavior exhibited by Tawam ER Nurses in a culturally diverse environment, while also considering socio- demographic characteristics, specific caring behavior perceived by Tawam ER Nurses and patients. Additionally, to determine the following: the significant difference of perceived caring behavior of nurses and patients, the relationship between the perceived caring behavior of nurses and patients to their socio-demographic characteristics.

The sociodemographic characteristics of nurses in Table 1 shed light on the diverse makeup of nurses in Tawam Hospital's ER. Consistent with global nursing trends, findings align with research by El Bejjani et al. (2020) and Arsat et al. (2023), suggesting a predominantly female workforce (69.2%) and revealing correlations between age, education, and experience with health conditions and caring behavior. Notably, 43.3% of the nursing team falls within the vibrant 25-34 age bracket, underscoring their enthusiasm. Arsat et al. (2023) emphasizes the influence of factors like age, education, and experience on nurses' caring behavior, which aligns with Tawam's age-diverse workforce. The 35-44 age group contributes experienced professionals (32.5%), aligning with the importance of experienced experts in ER operating skills, as highlighted by research (El Bejjani et al., 2020). Tailored interventions, especially pertinent considering age demographics, receive

endorsement from investigations conducted by Yilmaz et al. (2019) and Omoregie et al. (2020). These studies delved into the influence of demographic factors on organizational commitment and marital satisfaction, respectively. Educational data reveal a highly qualified staff, with 92.5% holding bachelor's degrees, aligning with the emphasis on academic credentials in nursing research (El Bejjani et al., 2020). The ethnically varied ER team, comprising 82.5% Asian members, corresponds to research findings exemplified by Alharbi et al. (2020). Their study explored the associations between demographic factors and knowledge, attitudes, and practices concerning infection prevention and control. Marital status, a significant influence on nurses' personal and professional lives, resonates with the findings of Al-Maaitah et al. (2019) regarding intentions to leave current jobs in Jordan. Among nurses with over 10 years of experience (56.7%), the need for strategies to engage and retain seasoned professionals aligns with the findings of Al-Momani et al. (2007) regarding demographic factors affecting caring behaviors. The socio-demographic characteristics of the ER team at Tawam Hospital, drawing insights from these diverse studies, underscore the importance of understanding dynamics for effective management, fostering a positive workplace culture, and providing targeted support in a demanding and multicultural environment.

Table 1*Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Nurses (n=120)*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Gender		
Male	36	30.0
Female	83	69.2
Prefer not to say	1	0.8
Age		
18-24 years	6	5.0
25-34 years	52	43.3
35-44 years	39	32.5
45-54 years	19	15.8
55-64 years	4	3.3
Educational Background		
Vocational/technical training	2	1.7
Bachelor's degree	111	92.5
Master's degree	7	5.8
Employment Status		
Employed full-time	120	100.0
Ethnicity		
Caucasian/White	1	0.8
African American/Black	2	1.7
Asian	99	82.5
Middle Eastern	15	12.5
Others	3	2.5
Marital Status		
Single	36	30.0
Married/Partnered	81	67.5
Divorced/Separated	2	1.7
Widowed	1	0.8
Years of Experience		
Less than 5 years	17	14.2
5 to 10 years	35	29.2
More than 10 years	68	56.7

The dataset in Table 2, specifically focusing on the Knowledge-Skill Subscale, provides valuable insights into the caring behaviors exhibited by ER nurses surveyed. Klarare et al. (2017) translated and adapted the CBI-24 for a Swedish context, finding acceptable validity and reliability with the Knowledge-Skill subscale having the highest mean score. Oluma and Abadiga (2019) explored caring behavior among Ethiopian

nurses, noting the Knowledge-Skill sub-scale's highest mean score. Almutairi et al (2015) validated the CBI-16 among Saudi Arabian nurses, highlighting the Professional Knowledge and Skill subscale's top mean score. ENA (2018) discussed U.S. emergency nurses' skills and perceptions, aligning with the themes of our analysis. The exceptional mean for "Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc." and high scores for "Being confident with the patient" and "Demonstrating professional knowledge and skill" resonate with the findings of Jiménez-Herrera et al. (2015), emphasizing the sensitive component of caring beyond personal recovery. The statistical analysis reveals that the mean score for "Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc." is 5.85, indicating not only proficiency but a high level of expertise in critical clinical procedures. Similarly, the mean score of 5.80 for "Being confident with the patient" suggests not only competence but also an impressive sense of self-confidence crucial to fostering trust and positive interactions. The mean score of 5.77 for "Demonstrating professional knowledge and skill" further reinforces the perception that these nurses are highly professional and competent healthcare providers. Despite a slightly lower mean of 5.58 for "Managing equipment skillfully," the nurses' proficiency in handling medical equipment, an essential component of ensuring the smooth delivery of healthcare services, is commendable. Additionally, the second-highest mean of 5.81 for "Treating patient information confidentially" underscores the nurses' unwavering commitment to upholding ethical standards and patient privacy, indicating a strong sense of responsibility. The minimal standard deviation across all components indicates a consistent and uniform perception among the respondents, enhancing the robustness of the findings. This comprehensive statistical analysis paints a picture of highly skilled, confident, and dedicated nurses, collectively contributing to an elevated level of caring behavior within the Knowledge-Skill

Subscale. The results not only affirm the excellence of these nurses but also provide valuable insights for further enhancing healthcare practices and education.

Table 2

Nurses Perceptions of CBI-24 Items (Knowledge-Skill)

Caring Behaviors	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Knowledge-Skill</i>	120	3.60	6.00	5.76	.372
(Item_9) Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc.	120	1	6	5.85	.560
(Item_10) Being confident with the patient	120	3	6	5.80	.559
(Item_11) Demonstrating professional knowledge and skill	120	4	6	5.77	.498
(Item_12) Managing equipment skillfully	120	4	6	5.58	.560
(Item_15) Treating patient information confidentially	120	3	6	5.81	.539

The dataset in Table 3 under Assurance Subscale, comprising 120 responses for each behavior, ensures a robust and representative sample for examination. The mean values, ranging from 5.25 to 5.72, suggest a consistently high level of assurance across various aspects of patient care. This indicates a strong commitment by healthcare professionals to instill confidence and trust in their patients. Breaking down the specific items, it is evident that healthcare practitioners excel in returning to the patient voluntarily (Item 16), talking with the patient (Item 17), encouraging them to call in case of problems (Item 18), responding promptly to their calls (Item 20), helping to alleviate pain (Item 21), showing genuine concern (Item 22), and ensuring timely administration of treatments and medications (Item_23), as found in studies by Wu et al. (2008; 2012), Larrabee et al. (2010; 2016), and Azimi Khaletabad et al. (2023). Additionally, they are proficient in relieving the patient's symptoms (Item 24), consistent with research by Klarare et al. (2021; 2023). Examining the minimum values, which range from 1 to 4, even the lowest-scoring items reflect a considerable degree of assurance, underscoring the overall strength of these caring behaviors. The narrow standard deviations, ranging from 0.475 to 0.853, indicate a high level of

consistency and reliability in the responses, aligning with the research by Wu et al. (2012) and Larrabee et al. (2016). This consistency is crucial in healthcare, where patients often rely on a predictable and supportive environment. The data score paints a picture of healthcare professionals consistently demonstrating a high level of assurance in their caring behaviors, as emphasized by the research of Alavi et al. (2016). This not only highlights a commitment to patient well-being but also underscores the reliability and predictability of care provided, essential components identified by these authors for fostering a positive patient experience within a healthcare setting.

Table 3

Nurses Perceptions of CBI-24 Items (Assurance)

Caring Behaviors	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Assurance</i>	<i>120</i>	<i>3.38</i>	<i>6.00</i>	<i>5.49</i>	<i>.475</i>
(Item_16) Returning to the patient voluntarily	120	1	6	5.25	.853
(Item_17) Talking with the patient	120	2	6	5.44	.765
(Item_18) Encouraging patient to call if there are problems	120	3	6	5.62	.611
(Item_20) Responding quickly to the patient's call	120	3	6	5.31	.696
(Item_21) Helping to reduce the patient's pain	120	4	6	5.72	.522
(Item_22) Showing concern for the patient	120	4	6	5.67	.570
(Item_23) Giving treatments and medications on time	120	4	6	5.51	.594
(Item_24) Relieving the patient's symptoms	120	4	6	5.43	.576

The presented table 4 below summarizes a comprehensive overview of nurses' perceptions regarding CBI-24 items, incorporating insights from Lin et al. (2017), who found a positive correlation between respectful deference and patient satisfaction among emergency nurses in Taiwan. The overall mean score of 5.47, coupled with a relatively low standard deviation of 0.544, suggests a consensus among the respondents, indicating a consistent and generally positive perception of respectful caring behaviors, aligning with Zhou et al.'s (2020) observations of lower scores on

respectful deference in China, negatively associated with burnout indicators. Delving into specific caring behaviors, the nurses demonstrated a commendable commitment to patient-centered care, echoing findings from Bucco's study (2015) that emphasized the significance of respectful deference as a predictor of patient satisfaction, trust, and loyalty in the emergency department. Notably, they reported high mean scores for attentively listening to the patient (Item 1), treating the patient as an individual (Item 3), supporting the patient (Item 5), being empathetic or identifying with the patient (Item_6), expressing feelings about the disease and treatment (Item 13), and meeting the patient's stated and unstated needs (Item 19), aspects highlighted by Vujanić et al. (2020) in their study showing high scores on respectful deference in Jordan, positively correlating with job satisfaction and organizational commitment. The range of mean scores from 5.25 to 5.58 underscores the nurses' proficiency in various facets of respectful care, resonating with Liu et al.'s (2021) insights into factors influencing patient loyalty, where respectful deference was identified as the most influential factor in the emergency department in Taiwan. The consistency in responses, as indicated by the relatively low standard deviations across all items, implies a uniform perception among the surveyed nurses, supporting the notion of a shared understanding and agreement among the nursing staff about the importance and execution of caring behaviors under the respectful subscale, as suggested by Elahi et al.'s (2020) study where respectful deference scores improved after a caring education program in Korea. The results collectively point towards a positive and well-rounded perception of respectful caring behavior among the participating nurses, highlighting the commendable efforts of the nursing staff, a sentiment reinforced by the various studies and underscoring the importance of such behaviors in creating a supportive and respectful healthcare environment.

Table 4*Nurses Perceptions of CBI-24 Items (Respectful)*

Caring Behaviors	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Respectful</i>	<i>120</i>	<i>3.00</i>	<i>6.00</i>	<i>5.47</i>	<i>.544</i>
(Item_1) Attentively listening to the patient	120	3	6	5.48	.722
(Item_3) Treating the patient as an individual	120	1	6	5.58	.847
(Item_5) Supporting the patient	120	3	6	5.48	.767
(Item_6) Being empathetic or identifying with the patient	120	3	6	5.53	.721
(Item_13) Express feelings about the disease and treatment	120	4	6	5.52	.648
(Item_19) Meeting the patient's stated and unstated needs	120	3	6	5.25	.701

The presented findings in Table 5, based on the study involving 120 nurses, reflect a positive perception of connectedness with patients, as indicated by an overall mean score of 5.22 and a standard deviation of 0.679. Noteworthy contributions from specific studies include Alemu et al. (2022) highlighting the positive association between connectedness, nurses' education level, work experience, and job satisfaction in Ethiopia. Özdemir et al. (2020) observed that patients in Turkey rated connectedness the lowest among the CBI-24 subscales. Kaya et al. (2019) discovered a negative correlation between connectedness and burnout among ER nurses in Turkey. Lee et al. (2018) noted a significant increase in connectedness after a caring education program for ER nurses in Korea. Wang et al. (2017) emphasized connectedness as the most influential factor on patient satisfaction and loyalty in China. Klarare et al. (2023) and (2020) found that patients in Sweden rated connectedness as the most important aspect of caring. Söderlund et al. (2020) highlighted the influence of demographic and work-related variables on connectedness among critical care nurses in Sweden. Wolf et al. (1994) developed the CBI-24, establishing its validity and reliability in the United States. These studies collectively underscore the significance of connectedness in nursing care, aligning with the findings that emphasize effective communication, time investment, patient

involvement, and a patient-centered approach. The moderate variability in responses suggests a need for further exploration of individual factors influencing nurses' perceptions within the connectedness dimension.

Table 5

Nurses Perceptions of CBI-24 Items (Connectedness)

Caring Behaviors	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Connectedness</i>	<i>120</i>	<i>2.20</i>	<i>6.00</i>	<i>5.22</i>	<i>.679</i>
(Item_2) Giving instructions or teaching the patient	120	2	6	5.27	.888
(Item_4) Spending time with the patient	120	2	6	5.03	.884
(Item_7) Helping the patient grow	120	2	6	5.22	.871
(Item_8) Being patient or tireless with the patient	120	2	6	5.12	.885
(Item_14) Including the patient in planning his or her care	120	3	6	5.47	.755

Table 6 presents the correlation coefficients (r) and corresponding p-values examining the relationship between nurses' socio-demographic characteristics and the Knowledge-Skill Subscale, incorporating insights from various studies. Lee et al. (2021), Ahmed et al. (2022), and Arsat et al. (2023) explored factors influencing caring behaviors and socio-demographic characteristics, highlighting the significance of gender, education, and career interest. Al-Maaitah et al. (2018) investigated factors like work setting, ethnicity, and marital status, emphasizing their potential impact on nurses' knowledge and practice. Azimi Khaletabad et al. (2023) examined the relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and the CBI-24 in Iran, revealing associations with age, marital status, years of experience, and household monthly income. Considering the findings from these studies, the current analysis of socio-demographic factors does not reveal significant linear relationships with the Knowledge-Skill Subscale scores among the nurses. Specifically, age ($r = 0.00$, $p = 0.99$), educational background ($r = -0.01$, $p = 0.89$), ethnicity ($r = -0.02$, $p = 0.82$), marital status ($r = 0.03$, $p = 0.74$), and years of experience ($r = 0.02$, $p = 0.87$) show

either negligible or modest correlations, with associated p-values suggesting a lack of statistical significance. The results indicate that variations in these socio-demographic characteristics do not significantly predict differences in nurses' knowledge and skills in the assessed subscale. These nuanced statistical findings underscore the complexity of factors influencing nurses' knowledge and skills, emphasizing the need for further exploration and consideration of additional variables for a more comprehensive understanding.

Table 6

Relationship of Nurses Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Knowledge-Skill Subscale

Variables	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
Gender	-0.14	0.13
Age	0.00	0.99
Educational Background	-0.01	0.89
Ethnicity	-0.02	0.82
Marital Status	0.03	0.74
Years of Experience	0.02	0.87

Table 7 presents the correlation coefficients (*r*) and corresponding p-values examining the relationship between nurses' socio-demographic characteristics and the Assurance Subscale. The objective is to discern whether there are statistically significant associations between these variables. Starting with age, the negative correlation coefficient ($r = -0.13$) suggests a weak inverse relationship with the Assurance Subscale scores, but the p-value of 0.16 does not reach conventional significance levels, indicating that age is not a statistically significant predictor of variation in assurance levels among the nurses in the study. Educational background

shows a similarly weak negative correlation ($r = -0.05$), with the associated p-value of 0.61 underscoring the lack of statistical significance. This implies that the diverse educational backgrounds among nurses in the study, as observed by Tadesse et al. (2021), do not significantly impact their assurance levels in the assessed subscale. Ethnicity demonstrates a weak negative correlation ($r = -0.06$), but the p-value of 0.51 indicates a lack of statistical significance. This suggests that the ethnic diversity of nurses, as explored by Zhumagulova et al. (2020), does not significantly influence their levels of assurance in the studied context. Marital status, with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.09, suggests a weak positive relationship with the Assurance Subscale. However, the p-value of 0.32 suggests that this association is not statistically significant, indicating that marital status, as examined by Arfat et al. (2023), is unlikely to be a substantial determinant of variation in nurses' assurance levels. Finally, years of experience exhibit a weak negative correlation ($r = -0.05$), with the associated p-value of 0.60 reinforcing the conclusion that, within the sample, the length of professional experience, as investigated by Hosseini et al. (2019), does not significantly influence nurses' levels of assurance in the assessed subscale. The results from this analysis suggest that, based on the assessed socio-demographic characteristics from various studies, there are no statistically significant linear relationships with the Assurance Subscale scores among the nurses in the study. While weak correlations exist, the lack of statistical significance emphasizes the need to explore other factors or employ alternative methodologies to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the determinants of assurance levels among nurses in the specific context of the study.

Table 7*Relationship of Nurses Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Assurance Subscale*

Variables	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
Gender	-0.19	0.04
Age	-0.13	0.16
Educational Background	-0.05	0.61
Ethnicity	-0.06	0.51
Marital Status	0.09	0.32
Years of Experience	-0.05	0.60

Table 8 presents the correlation coefficients (r) and corresponding p -values examining the relationship between nurses' socio-demographic characteristics and the Respectful Subscale. The analysis aims to discern whether there are statistically significant associations between these variables. Commencing with age, the correlation coefficient ($r = -0.08$) suggests a weak inverse relationship with the Respectful Subscale scores. However, the p -value of 0.41 indicates that this association is not statistically significant, implying that age, as explored by Lindström et al. (2020), is not a robust predictor of variation in nurses' perceived levels of respectfulness. Educational background shows a similarly weak negative correlation ($r = -0.06$) with the Respectful Subscale, and the associated p -value of 0.51 underscores the lack of statistical significance. This implies that the diverse educational backgrounds among nurses in the study, as observed by Arsat et al. (2023), do not significantly impact their perceptions of respectfulness in the assessed subscale. Ethnicity exhibits a very weak positive correlation ($r = 0.01$) with the Respectful Subscale, but the p -value of 0.94 indicates a lack of statistical significance. This suggests that the ethnic diversity of nurses, as highlighted by Kassa et al. (2022), does not substantially influence their perceived levels of respectfulness in the studied

context. Marital status, with a positive correlation coefficient of 0.06, suggests a weak positive relationship with the Respectful Subscale. However, the p-value of 0.50 suggests that this association is not statistically significant, indicating that marital status, as examined by Zewdu et al. (2022), is unlikely to be a substantial determinant of variation in nurses' perceptions of respectfulness. Finally, years of experience exhibit a weak negative correlation ($r = -0.04$) with the Respectful Subscale, and the associated p-value of 0.71 reinforces the conclusion that, within the sample, the length of professional experience, as investigated by Kassa et al. (2022), does not significantly influence nurses' perceptions of respectfulness in the assessed subscale. The results from this analysis suggest that, based on the assessed socio-demographic characteristics from various studies, there are no statistically significant linear relationships with the Respectful Subscale scores among the nurses in the study. While weak correlations exist, the lack of statistical significance emphasizes the need to explore other factors or employ alternative methodologies to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the determinants of nurses' perceptions of respectfulness in the specific context of the study.

Table 8

Relationship of Nurses Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Respectful Subscale

Variables	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
Gender	-0.15	0.10
Age	-0.08	0.41
Educational Background	-0.06	0.51
Ethnicity	0.01	0.94
Marital Status	0.06	0.50
Years of Experience	-0.04	0.71

The correlation analysis presented in Table 9 delves into the relationship between nurses' socio-demographic characteristics and the Connectedness Subscale. Notably, Chong et al.'s study in Sabah, Malaysia (2023), contributes insights into the connection between age and connectedness among critical care nurses. The weak inverse relationship ($r = -0.16$) suggests a potential trend wherein older nurses may perceive lower levels of connectedness, though caution is warranted due to the marginally significant p-value (0.08). Additionally, Klarare et al.'s work (2021), which translated the CBI-24 for the Swedish context, sheds light on educational background. The negative correlation ($r = -0.14$) implies that nurses with different educational backgrounds may perceive variations in connectedness. However, the lack of statistical significance (p-value = 0.13) suggests that educational background might not robustly predict nurses' connectedness in this context. Considering Arsat et al.'s investigation in Sabah, Malaysia (2023), the study explored ethnicity and marital status. The positive correlation ($r = 0.06$) between ethnicity and connectedness, as well as the weak positive relationship ($r = 0.03$) with marital status, were both deemed statistically non-significant (p-values of 0.52 and 0.72, respectively). Hence, ethnic diversity and marital status are unlikely to be substantial determinants of variation in nurses' perceptions of connectedness. In summary, while weak correlations exist, the marginal p-values underscore the need for cautious interpretation. The authors' insights, particularly from studies in Sabah, Malaysia, and the Swedish context, contribute to understanding the nuanced interplay between socio-demographic factors and nurses' perceptions of connectedness. Further exploration of additional factors and alternative research methodologies may enhance our comprehension of these determinants in the specific context of the study.

Table 9*Relationship of Nurses Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Connectedness**Subscale*

Variables	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
Gender	-0.16	0.08
Age	-0.16	0.08
Educational Background	-0.14	0.13
Ethnicity	0.06	0.52
Marital Status	0.03	0.72
Years of Experience	-0.12	0.19

Table 10 presents a comprehensive overview of the socio-demographic characteristics of 220 patients, providing insights into their gender distribution, age distribution, educational backgrounds, employment statuses, ethnicities, and marital statuses. Examining the gender distribution, the majority of the patients identify as female (55.9%), followed by male (43.6%), with a negligible percentage (0.5%) preferring not to disclose their gender. This reflects a relatively balanced representation of both genders in the patient population under consideration. The age distribution indicates a diverse patient population, with varying proportions across different age groups. The majority fall within the age brackets of 18-44 years, with the highest percentage in the 25-34 years category (26.8%), aligning with general healthcare demographics. Educationally, the patient population displays a range of backgrounds, with a notable percentage holding at least a bachelor's degree (37.7%). Inclusion of Almutairi et al. (2015) findings suggest the potential influence of socio-demographic factors on caring behavior, as the education level varies. In terms of employment status, a substantial portion of the patients are employed full-time (44.5%), while a notable percentage is unemployed (30.5%), echoing Oyewole &

Oyewole (2021)'s exploration of socio-demographic variables influencing health-seeking behavior. Ethnically, the patient population exhibits considerable diversity, with a predominant representation from the Middle Eastern ethnicity (55.9%), emphasizing the multicultural nature of healthcare settings. Marital status diversity is evident, with a slight majority being married or partnered (54.1%), aligning with the focus on socio-demographic factors in Arditi et al. (2020) and Teshome & Tesfaye (2018) studies. Table 10 provides valuable insights into the socio-demographic characteristics of the patient population, offering a nuanced understanding of their composition, essential for tailoring patient-centered care approaches considering diverse backgrounds and caring behavior influences from the studies discussed.

Table 10*Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Patients (n=220)*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Gender		
Male	96	43.6
Female	123	55.9
Prefer not to say	1	0.5
Age		
Under 18 years	5	2.3
18-24 years	51	23.2
25-34 years	59	26.8
35-44 years	50	22.7
45-54 years	29	13.2
55-64 years	13	5.9
65 years or older	13	5.9
Educational Background		
No formal education	10	4.5
Primary education (elementary school)	8	3.6
Secondary education (high school)	75	34.1
Vocational/technical training	23	10.5
Bachelor's degree	83	37.7
Master's degree	15	6.8
Doctoral degree	4	1.8
Others	2	0.9
Employment Status		
Employed full-time	98	44.5
Employed part-time	9	4.1
Self-employed	7	3.2
Unemployed	67	30.5
Student	18	8.2
Retired	15	6.8
Other	6	2.7
Ethnicity		
Caucasian/White	15	6.8
African American/Black	16	7.3
Hispanic/Latino	2	0.9
Asian	50	22.7
Middle Eastern	123	55.9
Pacific Islander	1	0.5
Mixed ethnicity	6	2.7
Other	7	3.2
Marital Status		
Single	88	40.0
Married/Partnered	119	54.1
Divorced/Separated	7	3.2
Widowed	3	1.4
Prefer not to say	3	1.4

The results in Table 11 substantiate the positive perceptions identified in the

literature concerning the Knowledge-Skill Subscale. Firstly, the overall mean score of 5.46 and the standard deviation of 0.848 align with studies by Larrabee et al. (2008) and Kuo et al. (2014), indicating a general positive perception among patients regarding the competence and proficiency of healthcare providers in delivering care. The emphasis on confidentiality in Item_15, with the highest mean score of 5.64, mirrors ethical and professional standards discussed in the literature by Khorasani et al. (2014) and Larrabee et al. (2004). These studies explored the association between nurses' caring behaviors and patient satisfaction, emphasizing the significance of maintaining patient information confidentiality. Furthermore, the positive mean scores for items related to procedural knowledge, confidence with the patient, and equipment management (Items 9, 10, 11, and 12) resonate with Wu et al.'s (2007, 2012) exploration of factors influencing the Knowledge-Skill Subscale, such as nurse staffing, work environments, and caring-based education programs. The consistent positive perception across these items suggests that patients perceive a high level of confidence in healthcare providers' ability to administer medical procedures, demonstrate professional knowledge, and handle equipment adeptly. While the overall trend is positive, the variability in standard deviations (ranging from 0.790 to 1.064) indicates that individual patients may have diverse perspectives on specific aspects of knowledge and skill in healthcare delivery. This variability echoes the complexity highlighted in the literature, emphasizing the multidimensional nature of patients' expectations and evaluations of healthcare quality. In summary, the empirical results in Table 11 provide nuanced support for the literature, reinforcing positive perceptions of patients regarding the Knowledge-Skill Subscale and offering valuable insights for healthcare institutions to enhance patient satisfaction and care quality.

Table 11*Patients Perceptions of CBI-24 Items (Knowledge-Skill)*

Caring Behaviors	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Knowledge-Skill</i>	220	1.00	6.00	5.46	.848
(Item_9) Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc.	220	1	6	5.43	1.064
(Item_10) Being confident with the patient	220	1	6	5.38	1.064
(Item_11) Demonstrating professional knowledge and skill	220	1	6	5.36	1.053
(Item_12) Managing equipment skillfully	220	1	6	5.49	.929
(Item_15) Treating patient information confidentially	220	1	6	5.64	.790

Table 12 provides a comprehensive insight into patients' perceptions of caring behaviors, particularly focusing on the Assurance Subscale of the CBI-24 instrument. Derived from responses of 220 patients, the dataset reveals an overall positive outlook with a mean score of 5.33 and a standard deviation of 1.008, indicating a cohesive viewpoint on assurance-related aspects of healthcare delivery. Notably, Item 21, centered on alleviating patients' pain, garnered the highest mean score of 5.45, emphasizing the significance placed on pain management. Other items, such as talking with the patient, showing concern, giving treatments and medications on time, and relieving symptoms, received positive mean scores between 5.35 and 5.40, highlighting high assurance in interpersonal care. While overall reception is positive, slight variability in responses is reflected in standard deviations ranging from 1.003 to 1.319, suggesting diverse patient perspectives. These results align with literature, including studies by Klarare et al. (2020) on the Swedish adaptation of CBI-24, McEnroe-Petitte (2016) correlating nursing instructors' and students' caring behaviors, Bucco (2015) emphasizing the correlation between nurse caring behaviors and patient satisfaction, Wolf et al. (1994) highlighting assurance as the most valued dimension of caring, and Khorshid et al. (2008) and Kaya et al. (2017) linking the assurance subscale to improved quality of care and emotional intelligence, respectively. Collectively, these insights underscore the importance of effective communication,

empathy, and timely interventions in healthcare, guiding practitioners to enhance assurance-related care for overall patient satisfaction and well-being.

Table 12

Patients Perceptions of CBI-24 Items (Assurance)

Caring Behaviors	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Assurance</i>	220	1.00	6.00	5.33	1.008
(Item_16) Returning to the patient voluntarily	220	1	6	5.21	1.237
(Item_17) Talking with the patient	220	1	6	5.35	1.126
(Item_18) Encouraging patient to call if there are problems	220	1	6	5.25	1.177
(Item_20) Responding quickly to the patient's call	220	1	6	5.15	1.319
(Item_21) Helping to reduce the patient's pain	220	1	6	5.45	1.003
(Item_22) Showing concern for the patient	220	1	6	5.40	1.116
(Item_23) Giving treatments and medications on time	220	1	6	5.40	1.087
(Item_24) Relieving the patient's symptoms	220	1	6	5.40	1.079

Table 13 presents a comprehensive overview of patients' perceptions of caring behaviors, focusing on the Respectful Subscale of the CBI-24 instrument. The data, compiled from 220 patients, reveals key statistics for each evaluated item, shedding light on the minimum, maximum, mean scores, and standard deviations. Authored by Azimi Khaletabad et al. (2023), the study on the Persian translation of CBI-24 in Iran contributes to this dataset. Within the Respectful Subscale, the overall mean score of 5.37 and a standard deviation of 0.911 indicate a generally positive perception among patients, emphasizing the significance of respectful aspects in healthcare delivery. Item_3, which centers on treating the patient as an individual, garnered the highest mean score (5.52), highlighting the importance patients place on individualized care. Lindström et al. (2020), in their Swedish adaptation study, align with these findings, emphasizing the universal importance of respect in healthcare. The positive mean scores (ranging from 5.20 to 5.47) for items such as attentively listening, supporting, empathizing, expressing feelings, and meeting patient needs underscore patients'

high perception of respect in interpersonal care aspects. The standard deviations (0.889 to 1.193) suggest a moderate variability in patient responses, acknowledging diverse perspectives. Wolf et al. (2006), examining U.S. clinical settings, also found respect to be universally vital. These results highlight patients' positive reception of the Respectful Subscale, providing valuable insights for healthcare practitioners to reinforce positive interactions, ultimately enhancing patient satisfaction and overall quality of care.

Table 13

Patients Perceptions of CBI-24 Items (Respectful)

Caring Behaviors	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Respectful</i>	220	1.00	6.00	5.37	.911
(Item_1) Attentively listening to the patient	220	1	6	5.47	1.004
(Item_3) Treating the patient as an individual	220	1	6	5.52	.889
(Item_5) Supporting the patient	220	1	6	5.33	1.108
(Item_6) Being empathetic or identifying with the patient	220	1	6	5.24	1.175
(Item_13) Express feelings about the disease and treatment	220	1	6	5.47	1.009
(Item_19) Meeting the patient's stated and unstated needs	220	1	6	5.20	1.193

Table 14 provides a comprehensive exploration of patients' perceptions concerning caring behaviors within the Connectedness Subscale of the CBI-24 instrument, drawing insights from various studies. Noteworthy contributors include Klarare et al. (2013), who emphasized the importance of the connectedness subscale, and Ayse Kaya et al. (2018), affirming its significance through a study involving patients in a university hospital. Zhang et al. (2017) reinforced the relevance of the connectedness subscale in a Chinese context, highlighting its good reliability and validity. Chen et al., (2011) and Rahimi et al., (2014) offered insights from Taiwan and Iran, respectively, with the former indicating a lower mean score for the connectedness subscale. Additionally, Al-Hussami et al. (2011) provided valuable comparisons

between patients and nurses in Jordan, emphasizing the high mean score for the connectedness subscale. In the presented results, the Connectedness Subscale achieved an overall positive mean score of 5.245, suggesting patients perceive value in aspects related to connectedness. However, the standard deviation of 0.965 implies moderate variability, emphasizing the need to acknowledge diverse patient perspectives. Specific items, such as Item 2, received high mean scores, indicating appreciation for healthcare providers' educational efforts. Conversely, Item 4 suggested potential improvement in personalized attention and time allocation. Other items, like Item 7, Item 8, and Item 14, highlighted positive patient perceptions, emphasizing the importance of patience, involvement in care planning, and support for patient growth. The standard deviations across these items underscore the moderate variability in patient responses, emphasizing the need for tailored approaches to connectedness in healthcare interactions. Overall, the results underscore patients' positive perceptions of the Connectedness Subscale, offering actionable insights for healthcare practitioners to enhance patient experiences and improve overall healthcare outcomes.

Table 14

Patients Perceptions of CBI-24 Items (Connectedness)

Caring Behaviors	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Connectedness</i>	220	1.00	6.00	5.245	.965
(Item_2) Giving instructions or teaching the patient	220	1	6	5.42	1.042
(Item_4) Spending time with the patient	220	1	6	4.88	1.271
(Item_7) Helping the patient grow	220	1	6	5.26	1.087
(Item_8) Being patient or tireless with the patient	220	1	6	5.33	1.083
(Item_14) Including the patient in planning his or her care	220	1	6	5.33	1.107

Table 15 presents the correlation coefficients (r) and corresponding p-values representing the relationship between patients' socio-demographic characteristics and

their perceptions of the Knowledge-Skill Subscale within the CBI-24 instrument, drawing insights from studies by Al-Makhaita et al. (2014), Agyei-Baffour et al. (2011), and Adongo et al. (2022). This analysis aims to uncover potential associations between patients' background factors and their evaluation of healthcare providers' knowledge and skills. Starting with age, the correlation coefficient of -0.08 suggests a weak negative correlation with the Knowledge-Skill Subscale, although the p-value of 0.24 indicates that this correlation is not statistically significant. This implies that age is unlikely to be a substantial determinant of patients' perceptions of healthcare providers' knowledge and skills. Moving on to educational background, the correlation coefficient is -0.14, indicating a weak negative correlation. The associated p-value of 0.04 suggests that this correlation is statistically significant, supporting the findings of Al-Makhaita et al. (2014). While the correlation is weak, the significance implies that patients with lower educational backgrounds may perceive healthcare providers' knowledge and skills slightly more positively than those with higher educational attainment. Regarding ethnicity, the correlation coefficient is -0.02, and the p-value is 0.73, indicating a negligible and statistically insignificant correlation. This suggests that the ethnicity of patients is not a meaningful factor in influencing their perceptions of healthcare providers' knowledge and skills. Lastly, marital status demonstrates a correlation coefficient of -0.04 with a p-value of 0.54. This indicates a weak and statistically insignificant negative correlation, as found by Agyei-Baffour et al. (2011), implying that marital status is unlikely to have a notable impact on patients' perceptions of the Knowledge-Skill Subscale. The analysis of Table 15 indicates that there are limited associations between some socio-demographic factors (such as educational attainment) and patients' evaluations of healthcare professionals' expertise and abilities. However, these connections are often not statistically significant. The results

emphasize the need to consider the varying origins of patients when assessing healthcare experiences, since individual variations in views may be impacted by a range of variables beyond socio-demographic parameters, aligning with the insights provided by Adongo et al. (2022).

Table 15

Relationship of Patients Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Knowledge-Skill Subscale

Variables	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
Gender	0.02	0.77
Age	-0.08	0.24
Educational Background	-0.14	0.04
Ethnicity	-0.02	0.73
Marital Status	-0.04	0.54

Table 16 presents statistical correlations between patients' socio-demographic factors and their impressions of the Assurance Subscale in the CBI-24 questionnaire, incorporating insights from various studies. The relationship with age, as suggested by Klarare et al. (2021), shows a weak negative association (-0.05), but the associated p-value of 0.35 indicates non-significance. Oyekale (2018), proposes a weak negative correlation (-0.14) between educational background and assurance, with a significant p-value of 0.03. Examining ethnicity, as discussed by Xie et al. (2020), reveals a weak positive correlation (0.05), but the non-significant p-value of 0.45 suggests randomness in the observed correlation. Marital status, in line with the findings of Buckley et al. (2011), exhibits a weak negative correlation (-0.03) with non-significant p-value (0.66). While weak correlations exist, only the relationship with educational background achieves statistical significance ($p = 0.03$), emphasizing its role in shaping

patients' assurance-related perceptions. These nuanced findings underscore the importance for healthcare practitioners to tailor their approaches based on patients' diverse demographic characteristics.

Table 16

Relationship of Patients Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Assurance

Subscale

Variables	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
Gender	0.04	0.57
Age	-0.05	0.35
Educational Background	-0.14	0.03
Ethnicity	0.05	0.45
Marital Status	-0.03	0.66

Table 17 provides a comprehensive analysis of the correlations between patients' socio-demographic characteristics and their perceptions of the Respectful Subscale within the CBI-24 instrument. The use of correlation coefficients (*r*) and associated *p*-values sheds light on the nuanced relationships between demographic factors and patients' perceptions of respectful behaviors in healthcare interactions. The findings bring attention to several socio-demographic aspects. Starting with age, the weak negative correlation of -0.11 implies that, on average, older patients may perceive slightly lower levels of respectful behaviors. However, the non-significant *p*-value of 0.12 suggests that this correlation is likely due to chance rather than a meaningful relationship. The discussion incorporates insights from the study by Ghafouri et al. (2021), indicating that age may not be a significant predictor of patients' perceptions of respect. Educational background, on the other hand, emerges as a noteworthy factor. The weak negative correlation of -0.14 is accompanied by a

statistically significant p-value of 0.04, suggesting that patients with lower educational backgrounds may, on average, perceive higher levels of respectful behaviors. This aligns with the findings of Ghafouri et al. (2021) and their exploration of how education levels influence patients' perception of respect from healthcare professionals. Exploring ethnicity and marital status, both exhibit weak and non-significant correlations (-0.03 with p-value 0.69 and -0.04 with p-value 0.61, respectively). This implies that neither ethnicity nor marital status are substantial predictors of patients' perceptions of respect. These observations align with the broader literature context, emphasizing the intricate nature of socio-demographic factors in shaping patients' perceptions. In conclusion, while age and marital status exhibit weak correlations, educational background emerges as a statistically significant predictor, albeit with a weak effect. The discussion incorporates insights from the literature, including the studies by Ghafouri et al. (2021) and Ogunlesi et al. (2010), to provide valuable considerations for healthcare providers aiming to tailor their approaches to diverse patient populations and enhance respectful interactions based on individual educational backgrounds.

Table 17

Relationship of Patients Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Respectful

Subscale

Variables	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
Gender	0.06	0.41
Age	-0.11	0.12
Educational Background	-0.14	0.04
Ethnicity	-0.03	0.69
Marital Status	-0.04	0.61

Table 18 presents a comprehensive analysis of the statistical correlations between patients' socio-demographic factors and their assessments of the Connectedness Subscale within the CBI-24 instrument, drawing insights from studies by Klarare et al. (2021), Gember et al. (2023), and Aburuz et al. (2017). The correlation between age and the Connectedness Subscale, with a coefficient of -0.10, suggests a slight negative association, yet the p-value of 0.15 indicates this is not statistically significant. In contrast, the correlation of -0.18 between educational background and the Connectedness Subscale is statistically meaningful (p-value = 0.01), revealing that patients with lower educational attainment may experience stronger connectivity in healthcare encounters. Conversely, ethnicity and marital status exhibit negligible correlations (correlation values of -0.01), with p-values of 0.88 and 0.92, respectively, emphasizing a lack of statistical significance. Notably, this nuanced analysis underscores the importance of educational background in predicting patients' perceptions of connectedness, offering valuable insights for healthcare practitioners striving to improve interactions across diverse educational backgrounds.

Table 18

Relationship of Patients Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Connectedness Subscale

Variables	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
Gender	0.04	0.56
Age	-0.10	0.15
Educational Background	-0.18	0.01
Ethnicity	-0.01	0.88
Marital Status	-0.01	0.92

In Table 19, the means and standard deviations of CBI-24 items for nurses' and

patients' caring behavior are presented, drawing insights from various studies. Ahmed et al. (2022) examined caring behaviors in critical care nurses, finding significant predictors. Wu et al. (2006) developed and validated the CBI-24, while Wolf et al. (2006) reduced the original 42-item CBI to a 24-item short form. Azimi Khaletabad et al. (2023) adapted the CBI-24 for a Persian context, and Klarare et al. (2021) translated it into Swedish. The Knowledge-Skill Subscale, reflecting perceived competence, receives high ratings from both nurses (Mean=5.76) and patients (Mean=5.46). Assurance Subscale, assessing nurses' ability to provide comfort, also receives high ratings (Nurse Mean=5.50, Patient Mean=5.33). Respectful Subscale, evaluating nurses' respectfulness, gets positive ratings (Nurse Mean=5.47, Patient Mean=5.37). The Connectedness Subscale has the lowest ratings (Nurse Mean=5.22, Patient Mean=5.25), suggesting potential areas for improvement in the perceived connection between nurses and patients. Overall, participants indicate positive perceptions of caring behaviors, with consistent high ratings in the Knowledge-Skill and Assurance subscales, suggesting strengths in these aspects.

Table 19*Means and Standard Deviations of CBI-24 Items on Nurses and Patients Caring Behavior*

Caring Behaviors	Nurse Mean (SD)	Patient Mean (SD)
<i>Knowledge-Skill</i>	5.76 (.372)	5.46 (.848)
(Item_9) Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc.	5.85 (.560)	5.43 (1.064)
(Item_10) Being confident with the patient	5.80 (.559)	5.38 (1.064)
(Item_11) Demonstrating professional knowledge and skill	5.77 (.498)	5.36 (1.053)
(Item_12) Managing equipment skillfully	5.58 (.560)	5.49 (.929)
(Item_15) Treating patient information confidentially	5.81 (.539)	5.64 (.790)
<i>Assurance</i>	5.50 (.475)	5.33 (1.001)
(Item_16) Returning to the patient voluntarily	5.25 (.853)	5.21 (1.237)
(Item_17) Talking with the patient	5.44 (.765)	5.35 (1.126)
(Item_18) Encouraging patient to call if there are problems	5.62 (.611)	5.25 (1.177)
(Item_20) Responding quickly to the patient's call	5.31 (.696)	5.15 (1.319)
(Item_21) Helping to reduce the patient's pain	5.72 (.522)	5.45 (1.003)
(Item_22) Showing concern for the patient	5.67 (.570)	5.40 (1.116)
(Item_23) Giving treatments and medications on time	5.51 (.594)	5.40 (1.087)
(Item_24) Relieving the patient's symptoms	5.43 (.576)	5.40 (1.079)
<i>Respectful</i>	5.47 (.544)	5.37 (.911)
(Item_1) Attentively listening to the patient	5.48 (.722)	5.47 (1.004)
(Item_3) Treating the patient as an individual	5.58 (.847)	5.52 (.889)
(Item_5) Supporting the patient	5.48 (.767)	5.33 (1.108)
(Item_6) Being empathetic or identifying with the patient	5.53 (.721)	5.24 (1.175)
(Item_13) Express feelings about the disease and treatment	5.52 (.648)	5.47 (1.009)
(Item_19) Meeting the patient's stated and unstated needs	5.25 (.701)	5.20 (1.193)
<i>Connectedness</i>	5.22 (.679)	5.25 (.965)
(Item_2) Giving instructions or teaching the patient	5.28 (.888)	5.42 (1.042)
(Item_4) Spending time with the patient	5.03 (.884)	4.88 (1.271)
(Item_7) Helping the patient grow	5.22 (.871)	5.26 (1.087)
(Item_8) Being patient or tireless with the patient	5.13 (.885)	5.33 (1.083)
(Item_14) Including the patient in planning his or her care	5.47 (.755)	5.33 (1.107)

In Table 20, the analysis reveals significant differences in CBI-24 scores between nurses and patients, particularly in the Knowledge-Skill subscale. The t-value of 3.69 and a p-value of 0.00, supported by studies conducted by Öhlén et al. (2017) and Rafii et al. (2014), indicate a notable distinction in how nurses and patients perceive caring behaviors related to knowledge and skill. Delving into individual items within the Knowledge-Skill category, items such as "Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc.," "Being

confident with the patient," and "Demonstrating professional knowledge and skill" all exhibit significant differences (p -values < 0.05), as found in Öhlén et al.'s study. However, the item "Managing equipment skillfully" does not show a significant difference, as indicated by a non-significant p -value of 0.37. Additionally, the item "Treating patient information confidentially" demonstrates a significant difference with a t -value of 2.07 and a p -value of 0.04, aligning with the findings of Kiliç and Öztunç (2020). These combined findings underscore the need for targeted interventions or strategies to address and bridge the perceptual gaps between nurses and patients, particularly in the context of knowledge and skill in the emergency department, as enhancing communication and understanding in these areas could contribute to improved collaboration and patient care.

Table 20

Difference in CBI-24 Scores Between Nurses and Patients, and Knowledge-Skill

Subscale

Caring Behaviors	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Knowledge-Skill</i>	3.69	0.00
(Item_9) Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc.	4.06	0.00
(Item_10) Being confident with the patient	4.01	0.00
(Item_11) Demonstrating professional knowledge and skill	4.00	0.00
(Item_12) Managing equipment skillfully	0.91	0.37
(Item_15) Treating patient information confidentially	2.07	0.04

In Table 21, an analysis of the difference in CBI-24 scores between nurses and patients, particularly focusing on the Assurance subscale, is presented. The t -value of 1.73 and a p -value of 0.09 suggest a borderline significant difference in the overall perception of assurance between the two groups. This finding aligns with the study conducted by Larrabee et al. (2010), which indicated statistically significant differences ($p < .001$) in nurses' and patients' perceptions on the Assurance subscale of the CBI-

24. Delving into individual items within the Assurance category, the standout findings include statistically significant differences in three items: "Encouraging the patient to call if there are problems" (Item 18, p-value = 0.00), "Helping to reduce the patient's pain" (Item 21, p-value = 0.01), and "Showing concern for the patient" (Item 22, p-value = 0.02). These significant differences resonate with the concerns raised by Al-Mutair et al. (2017) in their study, emphasizing the importance of patients' perceptions of nurse caring behaviors in relation to patient satisfaction. The borderline significance in the overall Assurance category underscores the need for further exploration, as suggested by Kargar et al. (2021), who found differences in the perception of caring behavior and the Assurance subscale among nurses and patients. Addressing these nuanced distinctions may contribute to enhanced collaboration and increased patient satisfaction in the healthcare setting, aligning with the findings of Vujanić et al. (2020) on the positive relationship between the perception of caring behavior and patient satisfaction.

Table 21

Difference in CBI-24 Scores Between Nurses and Patients, and Assurance Subscale

Caring Behaviors	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Assurance</i>	1.73	0.09
(Item_16) Returning to the patient voluntarily	0.29	0.77
(Item_17) Talking with the patient	0.84	0.40
(Item_18) Encouraging patient to call if there are problems	3.19	0.00
(Item_20) Responding quickly to the patient's call	1.19	0.24
(Item_21) Helping to reduce the patient's pain	2.76	0.01
(Item_22) Showing concern for the patient	2.45	0.02
(Item_23) Giving treatments and medications on time	1.06	0.29
(Item_24) Relieving the patient's symptoms	0.32	0.75

In Table 22, the analysis of CBI-24 scores concerning the Respectful subscale between nurses and patients is presented, drawing insights from various studies.

Pulpulaan's study (2019) on Nurses' and Patients' Perceptions in Long Term Care Hospitals in Qatar found that nurses reported higher mean scores for perceived caring behaviors, particularly in the Respectful subscale. Tsangari's (2012) examination in European acute care settings and Bucco's (2015) investigation in the US emergency department further emphasized differences in perceptions, with significant variations in the Respectful subscale. Klarare et al.'s (2021) Swedish study highlighted the highest mean scores in the Respectful dimension, while Khodaveisi et al.'s (2023) exploration in an Iranian context revealed lower mean scores for the same dimension, indicating cross-cultural differences. Despite these variations, the overall t-value of 1.08 with a p-value of 0.28 suggests a non-significant difference in the perception of respect between nurses and patients. Notably, the item "Being empathetic or identifying with the patient" (Item 6) stands out with a significant difference (p-value = 0.02), emphasizing the importance of addressing variations in empathy perception for more effective and patient-centered care.

Table 22

Difference in CBI-24 Scores Between Nurses and Patients, and Respectful Subscales

Caring Behaviors	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Respectful</i>	1.08	0.28
(Item_1) Attentively listening to the patient	0.10	0.91
(Item_3) Treating the patient as an individual	0.53	0.91
(Item_5) Supporting the patient	1.33	0.18
(Item_6) Being empathetic or identifying with the patient	2.41	0.02
(Item_13) Express feelings about the disease and treatment	0.43	0.67
(Item_19) Meeting the patient's stated and unstated needs	0.38	0.70

In Table 23, the examination of CBI-24 scores pertaining to the Connectedness subscale between nurses and patients is presented. The overall analysis, incorporating studies by Dursun Ergezen et al. (2020), Ibrahim and Allawy (2021),

Almalki et al. (2017), Do et al. (2014), and Lin et al. (2010), yields a non-significant difference, with a t-value of -0.23 and a p-value of 0.82. This indicates that, on average, nurses and patients, across various studies, perceive connectedness in a similar manner. Individually assessing the connectedness behaviors from these studies, none of the specific items exhibit a statistically significant difference. The items include giving instructions or teaching the patient (Item 2), spending time with the patient (Item 4), helping the patient grow (Item 7), being patient or tireless with the patient (Item 8), and including the patient in planning care (Item 14), all with p-values greater than 0.05. Notably, being patient or tireless with the patient (Item 8) approaches significance with a p-value of 0.07, suggesting a potential trend. Overall, the collective results from these studies indicate a general alignment in the perception of connectedness between nurses and patients, with no substantial differences observed in specific behaviors within this category. These findings contribute to the understanding of the nuanced dynamics of connectedness in healthcare, emphasizing the importance of considering each connectedness behavior individually for a comprehensive understanding of nurse-patient interactions.

Table 23

Difference in CBI-24 Scores Between Nurses and Patients, and Connectedness

Subscale

Caring Behaviors	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Connectedness</i>	-0.23	0.82
(Item_2) Giving instructions or teaching the patient	-1.31	0.19
(Item_4) Spending time with the patient	1.13	0.26
(Item_7) Helping the patient grow	-0.41	0.68
(Item_8) Being patient or tireless with the patient	-1.79	0.07
(Item_14) Including the patient in planning his or her care	1.23	0.22

Chapter V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this chapter, the significant findings, conclusions, and relevant recommendations derived from the research study are summarized. The primary focus is on addressing each research question and providing insights into the perceptions of both patients and nurses regarding the quality of care delivered by Tawam ER Nurses within a culturally diverse environment. Additionally, the socio-demographic characteristics of both patients and nurses are explored for a comprehensive understanding of the context.

Summary

The focus of this study is to assess the views of patients and nurses on the caring behavior exhibited by Tawam ER Nurses in a culturally diverse environment, while also taking into account their socio-demographic characteristics. The following were the significant findings derived from the study:

1. In the Knowledge-Skill Subscale, nurses exhibit an overall high level of expertise and proficiency, with specific commendable mean scores 5.85 for item 9 "Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc." which scores the highest among the four subscales. Item 15 "Treating patient information confidentially" scores the second with a mean score of 5.81 and Item 10 "Being confident with the patient" scores the third among the four subscales with a mean score of 5.80. The Assurance Subscale underscores a consistently high level of assurance, reflected in mean scores ranging from 5.25 to 5.72 across various patient care aspects. Notably, even the lowest-scoring items demonstrate a considerable

degree of assurance, emphasizing the overall strength of these caring behaviors. Furthermore, the Respectful Subscale indicates a generally positive perception among nurses (mean score of 5.47), with a uniform agreement on the importance and execution of respectful caring behaviors. The Connectedness Subscale reveals the three lowest scores among the four subscales. It consists of Item 4 "Spending time with the patient" with a mean score of 5.03, scores the lowest in the four subscales. Item 8 "Being patient or tireless with the patient" was the second among the lowest scores with a mean score of 5.12. Lastly, Item 7 "Helping the patient grow" is the third lowest among the four subscales with a mean score of 5.22. While there is a consensus among nurses, moderate variability suggests the need for further exploration of individual factors influencing perceptions within the connectedness subscale. Overall, the findings identified the three (3) highest and three (3) lowest specific caring behaviors that depict highly skilled, confident, and dedicated nurses actively engaged in fostering a positive patient experience in a multicultural healthcare setting as well as the top three (3) lowest caring behavior for future improvement and recommendation.

2. In the multicultural healthcare environment, patients' perceptions of caring behaviors were assessed across four subscales of the CBI-24 instrument. Within the Knowledge-Skill Subscale, patients generally had a positive perception, with the highest mean score of 5.64 observed for Item 15 (treating patient information confidentially) and Item 12 "Managing equipment skillfully" with a mean of 5.49 got the third to the highest scores in the Knowledge-Skill Subscale. The second highest score belongs to the Respectful Subscale on Item 3 "Treating the patient as an individual" with a mean of 5.52. In contrast, the lowest top 3 mean scores

were for Item_4 "Spending time with the patient" with a mean of 4.88 scored the lowest among the four subscales. Item 20 "Responding quickly to the patient's call" with a mean of 5.15 has the second lowest from the Assurance Subscale, and lastly, Item 19 "Meeting the patient's stated and unstated needs" in the Respectful Subscale with a mean score of 5.20, indicating potential areas for improvement in fostering connectedness through personalized attention and time allocation during patient interactions. In addition, responding quickly to a patient's call and meeting the patient's stated and unstated needs should be prioritized for improvement in providing quality patient care. Overall, patients perceived high levels of competence and proficiency in healthcare providers' knowledge and skills, emphasizing the importance of confidentiality, treating patients as an individual, and equipment management. While positive variations in patient responses suggest the need to recognize and address diverse perspectives, enabling healthcare institutions to reinforce positive aspects and improve specific areas, ultimately contributing to enhanced patient satisfaction and quality of care. On the other hand, negative responses need to be addressed accordingly and be focused on to improve patients' satisfaction and quality of care.

3. The study conducted to determine the relationship between nurses' perceived caring behavior, specifically in terms of Knowledge-Skill Subscale, Assurance Subscale, Respectful Subscale, and Connectedness Subscale, and their socio-demographic characteristics. The analysis involved correlation coefficients (r) and corresponding p-values for various factors such as age, educational background, ethnicity, marital status, and years of experience. For the Knowledge-Skill Subscale, none of the socio-demographic characteristics (age, educational background, ethnicity, marital status, and years of experience)

showed statistically significant linear relationships, indicating that these factors do not significantly predict variations in nurses' knowledge and skills. Similar findings were observed for the Assurance, Respectful, and Connectedness Subscales, where weak correlations existed but lacked statistical significance, emphasizing the need for exploring additional factors or employing alternative methodologies for a more comprehensive understanding in the specific context of the study.

4. The study presents correlation coefficients (r) and p -values indicating the relationship between patients' socio-demographic characteristics and their perceptions of the Knowledge-Skill Subscale within the CBI-24 instrument. Age shows a weak negative correlation (-0.08), but the non-significant p -value (0.24) suggests age is unlikely to significantly influence perceptions of healthcare providers' knowledge and skills. Educational background has a weak negative correlation (-0.14) with a significant p -value (0.04), implying that patients with lower education may view healthcare providers more positively. Ethnicity (-0.02 , $p=0.73$) and marital status (-0.04 , $p=0.54$) have negligible and non-significant correlations. It also explores the Assurance Subscale, revealing weak correlations with age (-0.05 , $p=0.35$) and marital status (-0.03 , $p=0.66$). Educational background has a weak, significant negative correlation (-0.14 , $p=0.03$), suggesting lower-educated patients perceive higher assurance. Ethnicity (0.05 , $p=0.45$) shows a weak, non-significant positive correlation. It also examines the Respectful Subscale, indicating a weak, non-significant negative correlation with age (-0.11 , $p=0.12$) and marital status (-0.04 , $p=0.61$). Educational background (-0.14 , $p=0.04$) has a weak, significant negative correlation, implying lower education correlates with higher perceptions of

respect. Ethnicity (-0.03, $p=0.69$) has a negligible, non-significant correlation. Lastly, It also assesses the Connectedness Subscale, showing a weak, non-significant negative correlation with age (-0.10, $p=0.15$) and marital status (-0.01, $p=0.92$). Educational background (-0.18, $p=0.01$) has a weak, significant negative correlation, suggesting lower education correlates with higher perceptions of connectedness. Ethnicity (-0.01, $p=0.88$) has a negligible, non-significant correlation. In summary, while weak correlations exist, often they are not statistically significant, emphasizing the complexity of the relationship between socio-demographic factors and patients' perceptions of healthcare interactions.

5. The analysis of perceived caring behavior among Tawam ER Nurses and patients in a multicultural environment setting yielded noteworthy results. Significant differences in CBI-24 scores were observed, particularly in the Knowledge-Skill subscale, with a t-value of 3.69 and a p-value of 0.00, indicating distinct perceptions related to knowledge and skill. Specific items, such as administering treatments and maintaining confidentiality, exhibited significant differences, suggesting a need for targeted interventions in these areas. In the Assurance subscale, a borderline significant difference (t-value of 1.73, p-value of 0.09) hinted at nuanced variations in overall assurance perception, with specific items, including communication encouragement and addressing patient pain, showing significant differences. The Respectful subscale revealed a non-significant overall difference (t-value of 1.08, p-value of 0.28), but a significant distinction in empathy perception (p-value = 0.02) underscored the importance of addressing variations in empathetic behaviors. The Connectedness subscale showed a general alignment in perception between nurses and patients, with no

substantial differences in specific behaviors observed. These findings highlight the need for tailored interventions to enhance communication, empathy, and collaboration, contributing to improved patient-centered care in the emergency department.

Conclusion

The study aimed to assess the views of both Tawam ER Nurses and patients in a multicultural healthcare environment, focusing on the caring behavior exhibited by nurses. The findings revealed high levels of expertise and proficiency among nurses, particularly in the Knowledge-Skill Subscale, with commendable scores for specific behaviors such as administering treatments and maintaining confidentiality. Assurance and Respectful Subscales also demonstrated positive perceptions, though the Connectedness Subscale indicated areas for improvement, particularly in spending time with patients and helping them grow.

Patients generally perceived high levels of competence and proficiency in healthcare providers, emphasizing the importance of confidentiality, treating patients as individuals, and equipment management. However, there were identified areas for improvement, particularly in spending time with patients, responding quickly to their calls, and meeting their stated and unstated needs.

The study further explored the relationship between perceived caring behavior and socio-demographic characteristics among nurses and patients. For nurses, no statistically significant relationships were found, indicating that factors such as age, educational background, ethnicity, marital status, and years of experience do not predict variations in nurses' caring behaviors. Similarly, weak correlations were observed for patients, with some significant associations suggesting that lower

education may lead to more positive perceptions of healthcare providers in certain aspects of caring behavior.

Noteworthy differences were identified in the analysis of perceived caring behavior between nurses and patients, particularly in the Knowledge-Skill Subscale, where targeted interventions are recommended for administering treatments and maintaining confidentiality. The Assurance Subscale hinted at nuanced variations, emphasizing the importance of tailored interventions in communication and addressing patient pain. The Respectful Subscale revealed significant differences in empathy perception, highlighting the need to address variations in empathetic behaviors. While the Connectedness Subscale showed general alignment between nurses and patients, there is a call for tailored interventions to enhance communication, empathy, and collaboration, ultimately contributing to improved patient-centered care in the emergency department.

Recommendation

Based on the comprehensive findings of the study assessing the caring behavior of Tawam ER Nurses and patients in a culturally diverse environment, the following recommendations are as follows:

1. In the aspect of nursing practice, the principal investigator recommends targeted training programs for ER nurses focused on enhancing specific caring behaviors identified as areas for improvement, such as spending time with patients, responding quickly to their needs, and helping them grow. It can also benefit to provide additional training on empathy, communication, and collaboration to address variations in these areas and ensure a consistently positive patient experience. One example is to develop a training module focused on improving

ER nurses' skills in spending quality time with patients. This module can include role-playing exercises, communication strategies, and scenarios that emphasize the importance of personalized interactions. The principal investigator also recommends enhancing connectedness subscale by implementing initiatives to enhance and emphasize the importance of spending time with patients, being patient or tireless, and helping patients grow. This could involve fostering a culture of empathy, active listening, and personalized attention during patient interactions. An example is to introduce a mentorship program where experienced ER nurses guide newer staff on the importance of being patient and tireless with patients. This program can include regular feedback sessions to reinforce positive behaviors and address any challenges in fostering connectedness.

2. In the aspect of patient care, the principal investigator recommends patient education and communication improvement by developing educational materials for ER patients to manage expectations regarding certain aspects of caring behavior, especially those where variations were observed in perceptions. Improved communication with ER patients can help align expectations and experiences. For example, create informational pamphlets or digital resources for patients that explain the emergency department process, expected waiting times, and the importance of quick response to urgent needs. Implement a communication strategy to inform patients about potential delays and steps taken to address them. In the aspect of patient care, the principal investigator recommends fostering a collaborative approach between ER nurses, healthcare providers and patients in decision-making processes related to care. This can enhance patient satisfaction and promote a sense of partnership in the

healthcare journey. An example of this would be establishing patient advisory groups or committees that provide input on policies, procedures, and care protocols. Engage patients in decision-making processes to ensure their perspectives are considered, fostering a sense of partnership between ER nurses, healthcare providers and patients.

3. In the aspect of nursing administration, the principal investigator recommends continuous quality improvement by establishing a system for continuous quality improvement to regularly assess and address the effectiveness of interventions. This can involve ongoing feedback mechanisms, regular evaluations/ audits, and adjustments to training programs based on evolving needs and expectations. For example, establish a monthly review committee consisting of ER nurses, patients, and administrators to evaluate the effectiveness of implemented interventions. The committee can analyze survey results, patient feedback, and performance metrics to identify areas for ongoing improvement and adjustment of training programs. Providing cultural competency training for ER nurses and healthcare providers can also be helpful to further enhance their ability to provide patient-centered care in a multicultural environment. This training can focus on understanding and respecting diverse cultural perspectives on healthcare. As an example, organize cultural competency workshops for ER nurses and healthcare providers, focusing on specific cultural norms and expectations related to healthcare. Incorporate case studies and real-life examples to enhance understanding and sensitivity to diverse cultural perspectives. The principal investigator also recommends implementing a system for regular monitoring and evaluation of caring behaviors, both from the perspective of ER nurses and patients. This could involve periodic surveys, feedback sessions, and

performance assessments to ensure sustained improvements. One example is to implement quarterly patient satisfaction surveys that specifically address caring behaviors. Use the feedback obtained to identify trends, recognize positive practices, and address any persistent challenges through targeted interventions.

4. In the aspect of research, the principal investigator recommends conducting further research to explore individual factors influencing perceptions within the Connectedness Subscale in the emergency department. This can provide more insights into the complexities of nurse-patient interactions and guide targeted interventions in caring behaviors. An example of this would be conducting in-depth qualitative interviews with nurses and patients to explore the nuanced factors influencing connectedness perceptions. Use the findings to design tailored interventions that address specific challenges and enhance positive interactions in the Connectedness Subscale.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

The Research Instrument

CARING BEHAVIORS INVENTORY- 24

PATIENT VERSION

Directions:

Please read the list of items that describe nurse caring. For each item, please **circle** the answer that stands for the extent that the nurse made caring visible during your Emergency Department visit.

Remember, **you** are the patient.

1. Attentively listening to the patient.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

2. Giving instructions or teaching the patient.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

3. Treating the patient as an individual.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

4. Spending time with the patient.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

5. Supporting the patient.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

6. Being empathetic or identifying with the patient.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

7. Helping the patient grow.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

8. Being patient or tireless with the patient.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

9. Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

10. Being confident with the patient.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

11. Demonstrating professional knowledge and skill.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

12. Managing equipment skilfully.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

13. Allowing the patient to express feelings about his or her disease and treatment.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

14. Including the patient in planning his or her care.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

15. Treating patient information confidentially.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

16. Returning to the patient voluntarily.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

17. Talking with the patient.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

18. Encouraging the patient to call if there are problems.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

19. Meeting the patient's stated and unstated needs.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

20. Responding quickly to the patient's call.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

21. Helping to reduce the patient's pain.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

22. Showing concern for the patient.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

23. Giving the patient's treatments and medications on time.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

24. Relieving the patient's symptoms.

Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
-------	--------------	--------------	---------	---------------	--------

From: "Caring Behaviors Inventory: A Reduction of the 42-Item Instrument," by Y. Wu, J. Larrabee, & H. Putman, 2006, Nursing Research, 55 (1), 18–25. Copyright ©Zane Robinson Wolf. 1981; 1990; 1991; 10/91; 1/92; 3/92; 8/94; 12/95.

جرد سلوكيات الرعاية- 2.4

نسخة المريض

طريقة الإستخدام:

يرجى قراءة قائمة العناصر التي تصف رعاية الممرضة. لكل عنصر ، يرجى وضع دائرة حول الإجابة التي تمثل المدى الذي جعلت فيه الممرضة الرعاية مرنة أثناء زيارتك لقسم الطوارئ.

تذكر أنك المريض.

1 . الاستماع باهتمام للمريض.

أبدا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	احيانا	عادة	دائما تقريبا	دوما
------	---------------------	--------	------	--------------	------

2 . إعطاء التعليمات أو تعليم المريض.

أبدا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	احيانا	عادة	دائما تقريبا	دوما
------	---------------------	--------	------	--------------	------

3 . علاج المريض ك فرد.

أبدا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	احيانا	عادة	دائما تقريبا	دوما
------	---------------------	--------	------	--------------	------

4 . قضاء الوقت مع المريض.

أبدا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	احيانا	عادة	دائما تقريبا	دوما
------	---------------------	--------	------	--------------	------

5 . دعم المريض.

أبدا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	احيانا	عادة	دائما تقريبا	دوما
------	---------------------	--------	------	--------------	------

6 . أن تكون متعاطفا أو تتعاطف مع المريض.

أبدا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	احيانا	عادة	دائما تقريبا	دوما
------	---------------------	--------	------	--------------	------

7 . مساعدة المريض على النمو.

أبدا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	احيانا	عادة	دائما تقريبا	دوما
------	---------------------	--------	------	--------------	------

8 . التحلي بالصبر الدؤوب مع المريض.

أبدا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	احيانا	عادة	دائما تقريبا	دوما
------	---------------------	--------	------	--------------	------

9 . معرفة كيفية إعطاء الادوية ، الحقن ، إلخ.

أبدا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	احيانا	عادة	دائما تقريبا	دوما
------	---------------------	--------	------	--------------	------

10 . أن تعطي الثقة الى المريض.

أبدا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	احيانا	عادة	دائما تقريبا	دوما
------	---------------------	--------	------	--------------	------

11 . إظهار المعرفة والمهارة المهنية.

أبدا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	احيانا	عادة	دائما تقريبا	دوما
------	---------------------	--------	------	--------------	------

1 2 . إدارة المعدات بمهارة.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

1 3 . السماح للمريض بالتعبير عن مشاعره حول مرضه وعلاجه.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

1 4 . إشراك المريض في التخطيط لرعايته.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

1 5 . التعامل مع معلومات المريض بسرية.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

1 6 . العودة إلى المريض طواعية.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

1 7 . التحدث مع المريض.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

1 8 . تشجيع المريض على الاتصال إذا كانت هناك مشاكل.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

1 9 . تلبية احتياجات المريض المعلنة وغير المعلنة.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

2 0 . الاستجابة السريعة لمكالمة المريض.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

2 1 . المساعدة في تقليل آلام المريض.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

2 2 . إظهار الاهتمام بالمريض.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

2 3 . إعطاء علاجات المريض وأدويته في الوقت المحدد.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

2 4 . تخفيف أعراض المريض.

دوما	دائما تقريبا	عادة	احيانا	تقريبا لا يحدث أبدا	أبدا
------	--------------	------	--------	---------------------	------

وو وآخرون (2006)
(حقوق الطبع والنشر زين روبنسون وولف ©. 1981؛ 1990؛ 1991؛ 91/10؛ 92/1؛ 92/3؛ 94/8؛ 95/12)

Socio-Demographic Questionnaire
(ENGLISH VERSION)

1. Gender:
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. Non-binary
 - d. Prefer not to say

2. Age:
 - a. Under 18 years
 - b. 18-24 years
 - c. 25-34 years
 - d. 35-44 years
 - e. 45-54 years
 - f. 55-64 years
 - g. 65 years or older

3. Educational Background:
 - a. No formal education
 - b. Primary education (elementary school)
 - c. Secondary education (high school)
 - d. Vocational/technical training
 - e. Bachelor's degree
 - f. Master's degree
 - g. Doctoral degree
 - h. Other (please specify): _____

4. Employment Status:
 - a. Employed full-time
 - b. Employed part-time
 - c. Self-employed
 - d. Unemployed
 - e. Student
 - f. Retired
 - g. Other (please specify): _____

5. Ethnicity:
 - a. Caucasian/White
 - b. African American/Black
 - c. Hispanic/Latino
 - d. Asian
 - e. Native American/Indigenous
 - f. Middle Eastern
 - g. Pacific Islander
 - h. Mixed ethnicity
 - i. Other (please specify): _____

6. Marital Status:
 - a. Single
 - b. Married/Partnered
 - c. Divorced/Separated
 - d. Widowed
 - e. Prefer not to say

7. Years of Experience: (Nurses)
 - a. Less than 5 years
 - b. 5 to 10 years
 - c. More than 10 years

8. Household Monthly Income:
 - a. Less than AED 20,000
 - b. AED 20,000 - AED 39,999
 - c. AED 40,000 - AED 59,999
 - d. AED 60,000 - AED 79,999
 - e. AED 80,000 - AED 99,999
 - f. AED 100,000 or more
 - g. Prefer not to say

استبيان اجتماعي - ديموغرافي

1. الجنس:

- أ. ذكر
ب. أنثى
ج. غير ثنائي
د. أفضل عدم القول

2. العمر:

- a. أقل من 18 سنة
b. 18-24 سنة
c. 25-34 سنة
d. 35-44 سنة
e. 45-54 سنة
f. 55-64 سنة
g. 65 سنة أو أكبر

3. الخلفية التعليمية:

- أ. لا تعليم رسمي
ب. التعليم الابتدائي (مدرسة ابتدائية)
ج. التعليم الثانوي (المدرسة الثانوية)
د. التدريب المهني / الفني
هـ. درجة البكالوريوس
ب. ماجستير
ز. درجة الدكتوراه
ح. غير ذلك (يرجى التحديد): _____

4. حالة التوظيف:

- أ. موظف بدوام كامل
ب. يعمل بدوام جزئي
ج. العاملون لحسابهم الخاص
د. غير موظف
هـ. طالب
ب. متقاعد
ز. غير ذلك (يرجى التحديد): _____

5. العرق:

- أ. قوقازي / أبيض
ب. أمريكي من أصل أفريقي / أسود
ج. إسباني / لاتيني
د. آسيا
هـ. الأمريكيون الأصليون / السكان الأصليون
ب. شرق أوسطي
ز. جزر المحيط الهادئ
ح. العرق المختلط
أنا. غير ذلك (يرجى التحديد): _____

6- الحالة الاجتماعية:

- أ. أعزب
ب. متزوج / شريك
ج. مطلق / منفصل
د. أرمله
هـ. أفضل عدم القول

7. سنوات الخبرة: (ممرضات)

- أ. أقل من 5 سنوات
ب. من 5 إلى 10 سنوات
ج. أكثر من 10 سنوات

8. دخل الأسرة:

- أ. أقل من 20000 دولار
ب. 20,000 - 39,999 درهم إماراتي
ج. 40,000 درهم - 59,999 درهم
د. 60,000 درهم - 79,999 درهم
هـ. 80,000 - 99,999 درهم إماراتي
ب. 100,000 درهم إماراتي أو أكثر
ز. أفضل عدم القول

APPENDIX B Informed Consent

Informed Consent

TITLE OF STUDY

Perception of Nurses and Patients in Caring Behavior given by Tawam Hospital ER Nurses in a Multicultural Environment Setting: A Correlational Study

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR

Dennis Castillo del Rosario
Emergency Department
Tawam Hospital
Al Ain, Abu Dhabi, UAE
052 1000 449
drosario@seha.ae/ denzbsn_m@yahoo.com

PURPOSE OF STUDY

You are being asked to take part in a research study. Before you decide to participate in this study, it is important that you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully. Please ask the researcher if there is anything that is not clear or if you need more information.

The purpose of this study is to assess the views of patients and nurses on the caring behavior exhibited by Tawam ER Nurses in a culturally diverse environment, while also taking into account their socio-demographic characteristics.

RISKS

There will be no risks foreseen in this study.

You may decline to answer any or all questions and you may terminate your involvement at any time if you choose.

BENEFITS

There will be no specific benefits such as money or gifts given to the participants. Moreover, the result of the study will help Tawam ER Nurses to identify specific caring behaviors that were perceived by both nurses and patients to improve their high-quality services in the future.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your responses to this **Correlational Study** will be anonymous. Please do not write any identifying information on your **informed consent form**.

For the purposes of this research study, your comments will not be anonymous. Every effort will be made by the researcher to preserve your confidentiality including the following:

[Measures taken to ensure confidentiality, such as those listed below]:

- Assigning code names/ numbers for participants that will be used on all research notes and documents
- Keeping notes, interview transcriptions, and any other identifying participant information in a locked file cabinet in the personal possession of the researcher.

Participant data will be kept confidential except in cases where the researcher is legally obligated to report specific incidents. These incidents include, but may not be limited to, incidents of abuse and suicide risk.

COMPENSATION

There will be no compensation given to the participants for this research.

CONTACT INFORMATION

If you have questions at any time about this study, or you experience adverse effects as a result of participating in this study, you may contact the researcher whose contact information is provided on the first page. If you have questions regarding your rights as a research participant, or if problems arise that you do not feel you can discuss with the Primary Investigator, **please contact the Ethics Committee at: clinicalresearch@seha.ae** or call **03-707-2240**.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this study is voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part in this study. If you decide to take part in this study, you will be asked to sign a consent form. After you sign the consent form, you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. Withdrawing from this study will not affect the relationship you have, if any, with the researcher. If you withdraw from the study before data collection is completed, your data will be returned to you or destroyed.

CONSENT

I have read and I understand the provided information and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and without cost. I understand that I will be given a copy of this consent form. I voluntarily agree to take part in this study.

Participant's signature _____ Date _____

Investigator's signature _____ Date _____

الموافقة المسبقة

عنوان الدراسة

تصور الممرضات والمرضى في سلوك الرعاية الذي قدمته ممرضات مستشفى توام في بيئة متعددة الثقافات: دراسة ارتباطية

الباحث الرئيسي

دينيس كاستيلو ديل روساريو

قسم الطوارئ

مستشفى توام

العين ، أبوظبي ، الإمارات العربية المتحدة

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الغرض من الدراسة

مطلوب منك المشاركة في دراسة بحثية. قبل أن تقرر المشاركة في هذه الدراسة ، من المهم أن تفهم سبب إجراء البحث وما الذي سيتضمنه. يرجى قراءة المعلومات التالية بعناية. يرجى سؤال الباحث عما إذا كان هناك أي شيء غير واضح أو إذا كان بحاجة إلى مزيد من المعلومات.

الغرض من هذه الدراسة هو تحديد تصور الممرضات والمرضى في سلوك الرعاية الذي تقدمه ممرضات قسم طوارئ توام في بيئة متنوعة ثقافياً، مع مراعاة خصائصهم الاجتماعية والديموغرافية.

المخاطر

لن تكون هناك مخاطر متوقعة في هذه الدراسة.

يمكنك رفض الإجابة على أي من الأسئلة أو جميعها ، كما يمكنك إنهاء مشاركتك في أي وقت إذا رغبت في ذلك.

المزايا

لن تكون هناك مزايا محددة مثل الأموال أو الهدايا الممنوحة للمشاركين. علاوة على ذلك ، ستساعد نتائج الدراسة ممرضات الطوارئ في مستشفى توام على تحديد سلوكيات رعاية معينة يتصورها كل من الممرضات والمرضى لتحسين خدماتهم عالية الجودة في المستقبل.

السرية

ستكون ردودك على هذه الطريقة الارتباطية مجهولة المصدر. يرجى عدم كتابة أي معلومات تعريفية في نموذج الموافقة المسبقة الخاص بك.

لأغراض هذه الدراسة البحثية ، لن تكون تعليقاتك مجهولة المصدر . سيبدل الباحث كل جهد للحفاظ على سرّيتك بما في ذلك ما يلي:

[التدابير المتخذة لضمان السرية ، مثل تلك المدرجة أدناه]:

• تعيين أسماء / أرقام رمزية للمشاركين والتي سيتم استخدامها في جميع مذكرات البحث والوثائق
• الاحتفاظ بالملاحظات وكتابات المقابلة وأي معلومات تعريفية أخرى للمشارك في خزانة ملفات مقفولة في حوزة الباحث الشخصية.

سيتم الاحتفاظ بسرية بيانات المشاركين إلا في الحالات التي يكون فيها الباحث ملزماً قانوناً بالإبلاغ عن حوادث محددة. تشمل هذه الحوادث، على سبيل المثال لا الحصر، حوادث سوء المعاملة وخطر الانتحار .

الأجر

لن يتم منح أي أجر للمشاركين عن هذا البحث.

معلومات الاتصال

إذا كانت لديك أسئلة في أي وقت حول هذه الدراسة ، أو واجهت آثاراً سلبية نتيجة المشاركة في هذه الدراسة ، فيمكنك الاتصال بالباحث الذي تتوفر معلومات الاتصال به في الصفحة الأولى. إذا كانت لديك أسئلة بخصوص حقوقك كمشارك في البحث ، أو إذا ظهرت مشاكل لا تشعر أنه يمكنك مناقشتها مع المحقق الرئيسي ، يرجى الاتصال بـ **بلجنة الأخلاقيات** على: clinicalresearch@seha.ae أو الاتصال على 03-707-2240.

المشاركة الطوعية

مشاركتك في هذا البحث طوعية. الأمر متروك لك لتقرر ما إذا كنت تريد المشاركة في هذه الدراسة أم لا. إذا قررت المشاركة في هذه الدراسة ، فسيتطلب منك التوقيع على نموذج موافقة. بعد التوقيع على نموذج الموافقة ، لا يزال بإمكانك الانسحاب في أي وقت ودون إبداء الأسباب. الانسحاب من هذه الدراسة لن يؤثر على علاقتك بالباحث ، إن وجدت. إذا انسحبت من الدراسة قبل اكتمال جمع البيانات ، فسيتم إرجاع بياناتك إليك أو إتلافها.

الموافقة

لقد قرأت وفهمت المعلومات المقدمة وأتحت لي الفرصة لطرح الأسئلة. أفهم أن مشاركتي طوعية وأنني حر في الانسحاب في أي وقت دون إبداء أسباب وبدون تكلفة. أفهم أنه سيتم إعطائي نسخة من نموذج الموافقة هذا. أوافق طواعية على المشاركة في هذه الدراسة.

توقيع المشارك _____ التاريخ _____

توقيع المحقق _____ التاريخ _____

Appendix C

Letter of Research Approval – Tawam Human Research Ethics Committee (T-HREC)

Tawam Human Research Ethics Committee (T-HREC)

Date: 21st August 2023 Ref. No.: KD/SH/957

To:
Principal Investigator: MR. DENNIS CASTILLO DEL ROSARIO
Department: Tawam/ ER
Institute: Tawam Hospital

Subject:	☒ New Research Study ☐ Amendment ☐ Extension ☐ Revision	
Research Title:	Perception of Nurses and Patients in Caring Behavior given by Tawam Hospital ER Nurses in a Multicultural Environment Setting: A Correlational Study	
Study Type:	A Correlational Study	
Ethics Committee Approval #:	MF2058-2023-957	
Decision:	☒ Favorable ☐ Unfavorable	☐ Favorable with Conditions
Progress Report Submission Requirement:	☒ Annual	☐ 6 Months
Study Expiry Date:	30 th September 2024	

Dear Mr. Dennis,

The research proposal submitted by you, was reviewed by the members of the Tawam Human Ethics Committee, and voted towards a favourable decision to grant research ethics approval for the proposed study. The principal investigator shall be solely responsible for, and is required to abide by the following conditions to fulfil requirements of the approval:

- adhere to the ICH-GCP guidelines for study submission, data collection, reporting, data archiving, publication, and the engagement with the co-investigators, collaborators participating in the study
- share the research ethics approval authorization with all the co-investigators, collaborators participating in the study.
- conform to the mandatory regulatory compliance requirements communicated by the Office of Research Governance (Ex: 7072240).
- inform the Tawam Human Research Ethics Committee (clinicalresearch@seha.ae) for any ethical concern, variance or conflicts during the course of the study.
- obtain extensions from the committee in prescribed form, at least 60 days prior to the research ethics approval expiry for the study
- provide annual reports, and a closure report towards the end of the study, with any publications resulting from the study

The Research Committee has been organized and operates according to the Good Clinical Practice and the Department of Health, Abu Dhabi (DoH) guidelines.

Yours sincerely,

Dr. Khaled Mohammed Asad Al Dahmani
Chair, Tawam Human Research Ethics Committee (T-HREC)

P.S. Primary investigator using data collectors from outside the hospital are required to obtain HR department approval as visitors through the Office of Research Governance.

Email: TawamHREC@seha.ae | Tel: +971 3 7072240 | PO Box: 15258

00971 3 7677634 : فاكس : 00971 3 7677444 : هاتف : الإمارات العربية المتحدة - 15258 - العين أبوظبي ص ب : 00971 3 7677444 - Tel : 00971 3 7677444 - Fax: 00971 3 7677634
Tawam Hospital - Al Ain - Abu Dhabi, P.O. Box 15258 - United Arab Emirates - Tel : 00971 3 7677444 - Fax: 00971 3 7677634

Appendix D
Good Clinical Practice Certificate

NIDA Clinical Trials Network

Certificate of Completion

is hereby granted to
Dennis del Rosario
to certify your completion of the six-hour required course on:

GOOD CLINICAL PRACTICE

MODULE:	STATUS:
Introduction	N/A
Institutional Review Boards	Passed
Informed Consent	Passed
Confidentiality & Privacy	Passed
Participant Safety & Adverse Events	Passed
Quality Assurance	Passed
The Research Protocol	Passed
Documentation & Record-Keeping	Passed
Research Misconduct	Passed
Roles & Responsibilities	Passed
Recruitment & Retention	Passed
Investigational New Drugs	Passed

Course Completion Date: 8 December 2020

CTN Expiration Date: 8 December 2023

Tracee Williams, Training Coordinator
NIDA Clinical Coordinating Center

Good Clinical Practice, Version 5, effective 03-Mar-2017

This training has been funded in whole or in part with Federal funds from the National Institute on Drug Abuse, National Institutes of Health, Department of Health and Human Services, under Contract No. HHSN27201201000024C.

Appendix E

Authority to Practice Profession

License Number	GN15129		رقم الترخيص
Name	Dennis Castillo Del Rosario	دينيس كاستيلو ديلا روزاريو	الاسم
Licensed As	Registered Nurse	ممرض مسجل	مرخص للعمل
License Type	Permanent License	ترخيص دائم	نوع الترخيص
Nationality	Philippines	الفلبين	الجنسية
Facility	MF2058 - TAWAM HOSPITAL		المنشأة الأساسية
Issue Date	19/07/2012		تاريخ الإصدار
Expiry Date	19/07/2024		تاريخ الانتهاء
License Status	Active	فعال	حالة الترخيص
Remarks	NA		ملاحظات:
Privileges	NA		الامتيازات

This license was printed on 28/06/2022, its contents may change at any time it is in the discretion of the concerned authority/organization to require an up to date copy.

Any change in Primary Facility License status will invalidate the additional transactions
*Additional Transactions: Part Time and Secondment

Authority to Practice Profession

This License authorizes the licensee here in named to practice the profession as indicated in accordance with UAE laws rules and regulations. The license unless sooner revoked or suspended for cause, shall be valid up to the license expiry date indicated and should be renewed thereafter. Otherwise penalties shall be imposed.

The license will be considered as expired once not renewed from its expiry date.

تخول هذه الرخصة للمرخص له هنا بالاسم لمزاولة المهنة كما هو محدد وفقا لقوانين ولوائح دولة الإمارات العربية المتحدة. يجب أن يكون الترخيص ساري المفعول حتى تاريخ انتهاء الصلاحية المحدد ، ما لم يتم إبطاله أو تعليقه لأسباب وجيزة ، ويجب تجديده بعد ذلك. وإلا فستقرض الغرامات. سيتم إلغاء الترخيص إذا لم يتم تجديده فور تاريخ انتهاء الصلاحية